

Web Information Extraction with Editorial Feedback

A Master's Thesis

in the course

Wirtschaftsinformatik

by

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in cooperation with

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August 19, 2025

Abstract

Web Information Extraction (WIE) is an interesting field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to extract structured data from unstructured HTML. This thesis provides an insight into training a MUSTIE encoder and how to use it to extract data following a hierarchical schema from web pages using node tagging. MUSTIE is a multimodal web transformer working with different structural attention mechanisms to jointly encode a DOM tree and enable efficient scaling with website sizes. It is analyzed in detail using attention- and gradient-based methods. While the model shows promising results on classes with a sufficient amount of high-quality labels, there are also many classes with poor performance highlighting the importance of data. Furthermore, this thesis provides a framework using a Continual Model Refinement (CMR) approach in combination with Active Learning (AL) to efficiently improve the model with incoming labels from editors in a Human-In-The-Loop (HITL) setting. Lastly, the results are compared to the results of an LLM with structured output. It is recommended to use the latter for small projects. A guide for the correct use of structured output is also provided.

Kurzfassung

Web Information Extraction (WIE) ist ein interessantes Gebiet der Künstlichen Intelligenz (KI) zur Extraktion strukturierter Daten aus unstrukturiertem HTML. Diese Arbeit bietet einen Einblick in das Training eines MUSTIE-Encoders und dessen Verwendung zur Extraktion von Daten nach einem hierarchischen Schema aus Webseiten mithilfe von Node-Tagging. MUSTIE ist ein multimodaler Web-Transformer, der mit verschiedenen strukturellen Aufmerksamkeitsmechanismen arbeitet, um einen DOM-Baum zu codieren und eine effiziente Skalierung mit der Größe von Websites zu ermöglichen. Er wird detailliert mit aufmerksamkeits- und gradientenbasierten Methoden analysiert. Während das Modell vielversprechende Ergebnisse bei Klassen mit einer ausreichenden Anzahl hochwertiger Labels zeigt, gibt es auch viele Klassen mit schlechten Metriken, was die Bedeutung von Daten unterstreicht. Darüber hinaus bietet diese Arbeit ein System, das einen Continual Model Refinement (CMR)-Ansatz in Kombination mit Active Learning (AL) verwendet, um das Modell mit eingehenden Labels von Redakteuren in einem Human-In-The-Loop (HITL)-Umfeld effizient zu verbessern. Zuletzt werden die Ergebnisse mit den Ergebnissen eines LLMs, welches Structured Output verwendet, verglichen. Es wird empfohlen, letzteres für kleine Projekte zu verwenden. Ein Leitfaden für die korrekte Verwendung von Structured Output wird ebenfalls bereitgestellt.

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Acronyms

- AG** Attention Guidance. 14, 67
- AI** Artificial Intelligence. ii, vii, 1, 2, 6, 9, 10, 20, 35, 83, R
- AL** Active Learning. ii, 15, 20, 61, 81, 97, 98, 99, 100
- API** Application Programming Interface. 1, 82, 90, 91, 96, 97, O
- ASL** Asymmetric Loss. 16, 17, 58, 60, 70, 73, 94
- BCE** Binary Cross Entropy. 16, 19, 57, 60
- BU** Bottom-Up. xi, 25, 27, 28, 34, 49, 79, A
- CFT** Continual Fine-Tuning. 5, 6, 7, 15, 61, 63, 81
- CIT** Continual Instruction Tuning. 15
- CL** Continual Learning. 5, 15, 20
- CMA** Continual Model Alignment. 15
- CMLLM** Continual Multimodal LLM. 15
- CMR** Continual Model Refinement. ii, 5, 6, 15, 20, 61, 74, 81, 90, 97, 99, 100
- CNN** Convolutional Neural Network. 10, 11
- CPT** Continual Pre-Training. 15
- CSS** Cascading Style Sheets. 1
- DAP** Domain-Adaptive Pre-Training. 15
- DBR** Design-Based Research. 7
- DDP** Distributed Data Parallel. 61
- DOM** Document Object Model. ii, 1, 5, 10, 11, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 31, 32, 36, 44, 45, 46, 49, 50, 51, 52, 54, 55, 57, 62, 64, 65, 66, 67, 70, 76, 79, 97, C
- DP** Data Parallel. 61
- DPO** Direct Preference Optimization. 91
- DtD** DOM-to-DOM. xi, 14, 25, 26, 28, 30, 33, 34, 36, 38, 45, 46, 49, 52, 79, 81
- FF** Feed-Forward. 24, 29
- GAD** Grammar-Aligned Decoding. 19, 20
- GAN** Graph Attention Network. 14
- GCD** Grammar-Constrained Decoding. 19, 20
- GNN** Graph Neural Network. 10, 11
- HITL** Human-In-The-Loop. ii, 6, 7, 16, 58, 94

- HMC** Hierarchical Multi-Label Classification. 18, 20
- HTML** HyperText Markup Language. ii, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10, 11, 18, 20, 21, 23, 24, 32, 34, 35, 36, 39, 40, 42, 44, 46, 50, 66, 75, 76, 82, 83, 90, 93, 96, 98, 100, C
- IE** Information Extraction. 9, 20
- IR** Information Retrieval. 9, 20
- ITT** Intermediate Task Training. 40, 42, 44, 46, 52, 53, 57, 58, 60, 62, 63, 68, 69, 72, 73, 74, 100, D, J
- JS** JavaScript. 1
- JSON** JavaScript Object Notation. 19, 82, O
- LA** Local Attention. xi, 25, 27, 32, 34, 37, 38, 45, 46, 79, A
- LLM** Large Language Model. ii, 5, 6, 9, 15, 16, 19, 20, 43, 83, 85, 87, 88, 89, 90, 91, 92, 93, 94, 99, 100, S
- LM** Language Model. 10, 19, 27, 36, 37, 39, 55, 61, R
- LN** Layer Normalization. 24, 25, 34, 53, 55, 56, 67, S
- MCL** Max Constraint Loss. 18, 19, 57, 58, 72, 73, R
- MCM** Max Constraint Module. 18, 19
- MDM** Masked DOM Modeling. 51, 53, 56, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 94
- MHA** Multi-Head Attention. 12, 28
- MLC** Multi-Label Classification. 17, 18, 58, 60, 94
- MLM** Masked Language Modeling. 11, 14, 19, 50, 53, 54, 56, 62, 64, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 72, 94, R, S
- NLP** Natural Language Processing. 9
- NRP** Node Relation Prediction. 11, 53, 62, 64, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 94
- OCR** Optical Character Recognition. 24, 34
- PN** Positive-Negative. 17, 83, 85
- PU** Positive-Unlabeled. 17, 18, 58, 70, 83, 94, 95
- Regex** Regular Expression. 1
- RFT** Reinforcement Finetuning. 91
- RTF** Role-Task-Format. 83, 90
- SEO** Search Engine Optimization. 57
- SFT** Supervised Finetuning. 91, 92
- TD** Top-Down. xi, 25, 27, 28, 29, 32, 33, 34, 57, 64, 68, 70, 93, 95
- TF-IDF** Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency. 10
- TI** Text and Image. 21, 22, 24, 25, 27, 28, 31, 32, 33, 37, 44, 45, 46, 49, 50, 53, 55, 62, 77, 97
- URL** Uniform Resource Locator. 2, 3, 9, 10, 36, 39, 40, 41, 42, 85, 87

WDC Web Data Commons. 40, 57

WIE Web Information Extraction. ii, 1, 7, 9, 10, 20, 90, 93, 94, S

XPath XML Path Language. 1, 11

Chapter 1

Introduction

Gathering information from the internet can be cumbersome. Looking through different websites, searching for specific information, and ordering it can be exhausting and time-consuming for humans. As a solution, this process can be automated using web scraping. "Web scraping [...] refers to the procedure of automatic extraction of data from websites using software" (Khder 2021). Instead of going through websites manually, a program can gather the information for us. This is especially a good option when Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) are provided since the data is available in a structured, machine-readable way. But unfortunately, this is not always the case.

Since most of the information is only available via web pages which deliver their contents using HyperText Markup Language (HTML), it is usually semi-structured to unstructured. Furthermore, related content might also be distributed across different domains or web pages. Though HTML might provide some structure, which enables web scraping using various techniques like Regular Expressions (Regexes), Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) selectors, the HTML Document Object Model (DOM), or XML Path Language (XPath) (Gunawan et al. 2019), almost all websites present their elements dynamically using JavaScript (JS) (*Usage Statistics of Client-side Programming Languages for Websites, August 2025* 2025), which can change site structures on the fly based on the data. Furthermore, websites can change their internal structure, which makes old selectors obsolete. Having this, as well as a growing amount of domains to scrape, comes with growing analytical costs and maintenance. These three barriers of unstructured and distributed data as well as dynamic or changing website structures make it harder for machines to analyze and interpret modern web pages (Weerasinghe 2024).

AI-based web scraping addresses these problems and aims to provide a sophisticated way of collecting information automatically, for example by navigating through the web using AI agents or using AI models to deal with the unstructured nature of websites and extract structured data from them. Among many recent papers about this topic, Web Information Extraction (WIE), which is the task of extracting target fields of an object from web pages (Q. Wang, J. Wang, et al. 2023), is an emerging one, highlighting the actuality of it.

This work focuses on WIE in the scraping process and aims to research the use of AI

Figure 1.1: Summary of the desired web scraping process.

in it as well as the implementation of human feedback to continuously improve the model.

1.1 Problem and Goal of this Work

Together with the *Thünen-Institut für Regionentwicklung e.V.*¹, the *Clausohm-Software GmbH*² works on a project called *Landmaschine*³. This project intends to provide users with a search engine for projects, actors, and knowledge in rural areas. Currently, it is nearly impossible to get and maintain an overview of all the different projects and ideas because there is no central database or listing. The *Landmaschine* solves this problem.

The task of *Clausohm* in this project is to provide the data for the search engine. Since there is no extensive information about actors or organizations of rural projects available, the focus lies on gathering project information as well as tagging them with appropriate categories, which are already available in a database. To accomplish this, a web scraping process is required, which is shown in figure 1.1. First, workers of the *Thünen-Institut* add crawl jobs with a web address to the system. This is done via a frontend for editors and their editorial work regarding rural projects. This editor frontend is also provided by *Clausohm*, but is not in the scope of this thesis. After the Uniform Resource Locators (URLs) to scrape have been added, a crawler retrieves the HTML of the web pages under the given domains. These are analyzed using an AI model to extract project information and categories. Afterward, the extracted data is integrated into a database that contains all projects to serve the search engine.

Since the editor frontend uses *Directus*⁴ as the backend and data store, extracted projects should be saved there as drafts. After the scraping is done, editors can review the results and make changes if necessary. This is a mandatory step in quality assurance since "AI-based systems are accepted to be inherently 'defective'" (Felderer and Ramler 2021).

¹<https://thuenen-institut.de>

²<https://clausohm.de>

³<https://maschine.landlebtdoch.de>

⁴<https://directus.io>

Figure 1.2: System overview.

When the reviewed and eventually edited results get published, this feedback should be used to continually improve the model.

For a better understanding of the underlying system built for this work, figure 1.2 provides an overview of it. It consists of six main components:

Editor Frontend Via the editor frontend, editors can add crawl jobs, review and edit projects, as well as publish them. Furthermore, categories for projects can be added and edited.

Directus The backbone of the system. It is used to store all the data in a hub-and-spoke manner (Haynes 2022; Vinckier 1996; Calefato and Lanubile 2016) and functions as a backend.

Crawler Service The crawler service takes the URL from a crawl job as an entry point to crawl the web pages of the given domain. It saves all images as well as the raw HTML and a cleaned version of it in *Directus*.

Entity Extraction Service Reads the categories and cleaned HTML and sends both to the model to extract projects. After getting the result, projects are saved into *Directus* as drafts while avoiding duplicates.

Fine-Tuning Service Uses the feedback from editors to continuously refine the model and saves the new model file in *Directus*.

Model Service Is used to extract project information given a cleaned HTML as well as the

pool of categories. For this task, *OpenAI*⁵ is used and step-by-step complemented or replaced by an in-house model, which is researched in this thesis.

The focus of this thesis lies on the Model Service and the Fine-Tuning Service. To conclude, the goal of this work is threefold:

1. Show the use of *OpenAI* to extract project entities from HTML and label them with categories.
2. Gradually reduce costs and gain independence by developing a custom in-house solution with equal capabilities for the task.
3. Make the extraction process more accurate using human feedback.

1.2 Requirements

To come up with a useful result for the search engine that satisfies the stakeholders, the following points have to be considered for implementing the model:

1. The model should be able to extract available project information from any German web page, including texts, links, and images. This means that the maximum input size should be high enough to process large web pages. According to the downstream task dataset, this is around 2,048 text tokens to fit 90 % of the web pages completely (see table 5.5).
2. It should only map existing texts to the project schema and not create new texts.
3. A project should be tagged with all appropriate categories from the database. Furthermore, up to three of these categories should be designated as main categories. The ground truth for the labels comes from the editors.
4. The model should detect all projects on a page and return an array of them. Thus, the array can be empty for non-project pages, contain one project for project detail pages, or include multiple projects in case of a project listing page.
5. The model should be reliable because high accuracy is important to minimize editorial effort.
6. Feedback from editors should be used to continually improve the model's accuracy with time and more data.

The inference speed and data privacy are not relevant since the web scraping process runs in background and the status of the extraction is perpetually reported to the editors. In addition, all web pages are public and only partner websites of the *Thünen-Institut* are used, such that no privacy concerns arise.

⁵<https://openai.com>

1.3 Research Objectives

To implement such a model, MUSTIE (Q. Wang, J. Wang, et al. 2023), a **Multimodal Structural Transformer for Web Information Extraction**, is used as a starting point. It provides multimodal input, such as images and texts, for leaf nodes and comes with structural attention mechanisms to efficiently encode the HTML DOM. Furthermore, it has the size of average language models, like BERT (Devlin et al. 2018), and is thus applicable as efficient specialized model for the task in contrast to a Large Language Model (LLM), which requires way more resources. Since this model has its limitations paired with some strict requirements from the previous section, it is developed further to meet the needs of this project.

The field element as well as the decoder are removed since no texts should be generated. The extraction can solely rely on present information from DOM nodes. To accomplish this, a node-level classification task, also known as "node tagging" (B. Y. Lin, Sheng, et al. 2020), is used. This enables the extraction of multiple information from a web page in one run. To match the categories, a retrieval task is added for project nodes. Since only little project data is available yet, a pre-training is applied before fine-tuning on the main dataset to help the model generalizing over multiple domains. During the development and evaluation of the model, some more improvements are researched (see chapter 4).

To continually improve the model, a Continual Fine-Tuning (CFT) approach is chosen as it is the simplest and most efficient Continual Learning (CL) technique (Shi et al. 2024). With Continual Model Refinement (CMR), it directly leverages editorial supervised samples to fix errors and improve extraction accuracy, and it can do so incrementally without catastrophic forgetting while being efficient and easy to implement (Shi et al. 2024).

To sum up, this work will cover the following research contribution:

1. Analyze the applicability of MUSTIE using only the encoder for node classification to extract the project schema rather than a relying on a decoder to generate an answer for a searched field or question.
2. Introduce a retrieval task to match given project categories from the database.
3. Explore promising improvements of the MUSTIE model.
4. Implement a CMR approach for efficient fine-tuning with editorial feedback.

1.4 Definition of Success

Having all the requirements and research objectives set, this work is considered successful when the following criteria are met:

1. All the research objectives were examined, documented, and discussed.
2. A MUSTIE-based model was developed that can reduce the cost of the web scraping process while keeping similar or better results quality than the *OpenAI* baseline.

1.5 Content Overview

To properly address these goals, this thesis is structured as follows: The next chapter will describe the methodology of this work. After that, related work and important preliminaries are presented in chapter 3. With all basics set, chapter 4 directly dives into the developed model followed by chapter 5 explaining the data necessary for training. The following chapters deal with the experimental setup in chapter 6 and the results in chapter 7. Afterward, the use of *OpenAI* is discussed in chapter 8. Finally, this thesis finishes with chapter 9 about limitations and future work and concludes in chapter 10.

1.6 Recap

Gathering structured information from the internet can be a challenging task. Barriers like unstructured and distributed data as well as dynamic or changing website structures make rule-based extraction methods hard to apply and maintain. Luckily, AI can help with that. This thesis shows that using LLMs is possible and additionally develops a custom MUSTIE-based in-house model to extract information regarding projects in rural areas from HTML. That model aims to be more cost-efficient and step-by-step take over the tasks of the LLM. Since AI is error-prone, a Human-In-The-Loop (HITL) approach is used to check the extraction results. With the help of the feedback and CFT, this model should be steadily improved.

All in all, this thesis presents research results about the applicability of an edited MUSTIE-based model, adds additional tasks and improvements to it, and implements a CMR approach to utilize feedback efficiently.

Chapter 2

Methodology

After laying out all the details about the project and research, this chapter provides an overview of the research design, the steps taken, as well as the tools and materials used during the work. It also includes a description of the formattings utilized to enhance the clarity of the presented information.

2.1 Research Design

The main objective of this paper is to implement a multimodal structural transformer for WIE. Therefore, a developmental and experimental research design was chosen. The MUSTIE model (Q. Wang, J. Wang, et al. 2023) has been self-implemented since it was not possible to get the code from the authors. From this starting point, further customizations has been made for it to fit the needs of this project as described in chapter 4. Due to own experiments, evaluations, and customizations of it, this work mostly follows an inductive approach. By using *OpenAI* and following best-practices on how to use it for web extraction, there is a deductive part of this thesis too.

Regarding the CFT of the model, a HITL approach is employed within a Design-Based Research (DBR) cycle. There is an initial dataset built during this project, which seeds the model, and subsequent user feedback on live outputs is continuously incorporated to refine both, the dataset and the model.

To evaluate and compare the models, as well as to measure the success of this work, different metrics were collected during training, and testing. This allows a quantitative analysis and rating of the results as well as the comparison between different approaches. There is also a qualitative feedback from the editors of the *Thünen-Institut* to rate the extraction results from *OpenAI*.

2.2 Tools and Materials

For such a research and development project to work, a bunch of tools and materials are required. For development, *Jupyter*¹ notebooks were utilized in combination with a remote *Jupyter* server running inside a *Podman*² container. The university provided a GPU server to initially train the model on. It was equipped with an *NVIDIA*³ A100-PCIE-40GB GPU cluster, of which 7 GPUs were used to train the model. The *Podman* container uses `quay.io/jupyter/pytorch-notebook:cuda12-pytorch-2.6.0` as image from the *Quay Container Registry*⁴. The model itself was implemented in *Python*⁵ with *PyTorch*⁶ and is fully *Hugging Face*⁷-compatible. Therefore, the *Hugging Face* datasets and Trainer functionalities were used to handle data and training efficiently. *MLflow*⁸ helped with monitoring and evaluating the training runs.

For this setup, the python package *hf-mtask-trainer*⁹ was especially helpful because it provides a subclass of the *Hugging Face* Trainer that is designed for multitask learning. It enables the developer to add metrics from inside the model, like multitask losses and metrics which are calculated in the head, to the log of both, the Trainer and the *MLflow* run. The developed model and code, as well as the datasets created for this work, belong to the Clausohm-Software GmbH and will not be published.

2.3 Depictions and Notations

All figures are self-made with *Draw.io*¹⁰ if not stated differently. Some depictions use fictitious content generated with *OpenAI*'s ChatGPT. When used, this is explicitly stated below the depiction. In this paper, code as well as technical names and variables are displayed using a monospaced font and look like this: `This is code.`

Precision and recall are also denoted as P or R and micro and macro scores abbreviated with m or M, respectively.

2.4 Translations

Since the target language is German, some content displayed in this paper has been translated to English for demonstration purposes. To minimize personal bias, those texts were translated using *DeepL*¹¹.

¹<https://jupyter.org>

²<https://podman.io>

³<https://www.nvidia.com>

⁴<https://quay.io>

⁵<https://www.python.org>

⁶<https://pytorch.org>

⁷<https://huggingface.co>

⁸<https://mlflow.org>

⁹<https://github.com/zipzou/hf-multitask-trainer>

¹⁰<https://app.diagrams.net>

¹¹<https://www.deepl.com>

Chapter 3

Related Work and Preliminaries

Before diving into the details of this work, this chapter explains the technologies used throughout this paper and presents studies related the research. It starts at the root of this project, web scraping, and shifts to AI in it and the field of WIE. After that, more specific implementation details of models like sparse attention and web transformers are discussed. Finally, it comes to fine-tuning as well as quality assurance before moving on to the last topic of LLMs and structured output.

3.1 Web Scraping

As mentioned in chapter 1, web scraping is an important technique to automate data gathering from web pages and thus in the field of business intelligence (Khder 2021). Khder gives a definition of web scraping as well as an introduction to the topic including state-of-the-art techniques and applications. The author also includes legal concerns, which are quickly overlooked. While Gunawan et al. focus on static selector-based extraction methods, Khder further discusses the future of web scraping, which might involve AI. Web scraping is a three-fold process and consists of data fetching or Information Retrieval (IR), Information Extraction (IE), and transformation of the data to save it into a database (Khder 2021; Weerasinghe 2024). Weerasinghe discusses how AI might be used in web scraping to overcome its challenges. This includes the application of AI in all three stages. Regarding IR, AI can rank web pages to crawl or filter them before going to the next step. In the IE stage, AI can be used to classify web pages or content as well as to extract detailed structured information, like in WIE. Extraction and classification can be done using content-, URL-, or vision-based methods. Those topics are in the focus of the next sections. Finally, in the transform stage, AI-based algorithms can be used to transform the extracted data, e.g., by vectorizing the data using embedding models to store it in a vector database. Overall, Weerasinghe states that "AI techniques have significantly improved web scraping processes, enhancing accuracy, efficiency, handling dynamic websites, and scalability. Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a powerful tool for extracting structured data from unstructured web pages, while machine learning and computer vision techniques are effective in web page classification and parsing." (Weerasinghe 2024). Figure 3.1

Figure 3.1: Web scraping example a) without and b) with AI.

visualizes a possible web scraping process with opportunities of using AI.

3.2 Web Page Classification

Web page classification is the first step of extracting—in this case implicit—information from web pages. Several recent papers analyze this task, mainly using the website’s plain text contents, URL, title, and meta description. They show that using classifiers on top of pretrained Transformers (Vaswani et al. 2017) like BERT (Devlin et al. 2018) or RoBERTa (Liu et al. 2019) are more effective than Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) or traditional methods like Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) because Language Models (LMs) solve the polysemy problem (Artene, Tibeica, and Leon 2021; Yamoun, Guessoum, and Girard 2022; Nandanwar and Choudhary 2023). Yamoun, Guessoum, and Girard also show that the accuracy of multiple binary classifications is better than mono-multiclassification with the tradeoff to learn multiple classifiers. Another work further explores applying a Graph Neural Network (GNN), utilizing not only the website’s text contents but also its structure (T. Guo and B. Cui 2022).

3.3 Web Information Extraction

Using the website’s structure has proven beneficial as other studies show. It is particularly useful, or even necessary, when extracting specific data from a website, which is called Web Information Extraction (WIE) or sometimes web data extraction. FreeDOM (B. Y. Lin, Sheng, et al. 2020) is a two-stage model using a DOM node’s text, preceding tokens, and visual features like its HTML tag to classify nodes. It further adds a node-pair relation prediction stage to train the model to use global relations. Another study leverages inter-

page dependencies and uses context and path similarities to generalize over unseen web pages in the same vertical (Hao et al. 2011).

There are also works utilizing the website structure in the form of screenshots together with a CNN and Tesseract to identify page elements (Patnaik, Babu, and Bhave 2021). While vision might be useful to understand websites as humans do, this approach has some drawbacks. With visual-features, websites structure can be learned, but textual-information is harder to assess. Furthermore, this approach is prone to hidden elements, which might need user interaction to show up on screen. Other studies, which used visual features, but not screenshots as input, carefully crafted a GNN, taking into account content, structure, style, and visual features of page elements. (Jones 2022).

While all of them show that website structure is important and try to cope with noisy page content, they all use non-transformer architectures, but those have been very successful in the last few years.

3.4 Web Transformers

There are some transformer models specially designed to understand semi-structured or visually rich documents. MarkupLM (J. Li et al. 2021) extracts texts from a markup document like HTML and uses an XPath embedding instead of the sequence embedding BERT uses. For pretraining, tasks like title-page matching, Node Relation Prediction (NRP), and masked markup language modeling are used. DOM-LM (Deng et al. 2022) works similarly but uses a different technique for position embeddings. It still has a token position embedding but adds a position matrix containing the HTML tag of the element, its depth, parent node index, node index within siblings, and the overall node index. DOM-LM only uses Masked Language Modeling (MLM). Unfortunately, the authors don't provide any comparison with MarkupLM.

WebFormer (Q. Wang, Fang, et al. 2022) is the first transformer, known to the author at the time of writing, that encodes HTML tags too and uses structural attention to jointly encode them with the text tokens. It adds a special "Field" token in the tree to choose which information should be extracted by predicting the value range from the text tokens. Page classification is used as an auxiliary task. It further uses five different attention mechanisms to jointly encode the DOM, namely HTML-to-HTML graph attention, HTML-to-Text attention, Text-to-HTML full attention, Text-to-Text relative attention, and Field-to-HTML attention. These attention mechanisms are explained in greater detail in subsection 4.3. SMARTAVE (Q. Wang, Yang, et al. 2022) uses a similar architecture but for products and with hyper-tokens instead of HTML-tokens like "title", "description", and "image". Furthermore, it adds a decoder to generate the answer from the "attribute" token, which is the equivalent to WebFormer's "field" token, but keeps the sequential tagging task.

MUSTIE (Q. Wang, J. Wang, et al. 2023) fuses both models and represents a state-of-the-art web transformer. It encodes the DOM tree like WebFormer and uses multimodality for text and images as well as a field decoder like SMARTAVE while preserving the tasks from WebFormer as auxiliary tasks. MUSTIE is also the first model compared

to other models named in this section and performs better than FreeDOM, MarkupLM, and WebFormer. The authors further show that MUSTIE performs well in low-resource scenarios. As the architecture and results are promising, it is chosen as the base model for this work.

3.5 Attention

The advantage of those models is that they use structural and therefore sparse attention. Thus, they belong to the family of sparse or efficient transformers. This way, they don't have to compute the whole N^2 attention matrix, but only a fraction of it. Before diving into sparse attention, it is important to cover the default attention mechanism first:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (3.1)$$

This is the default attention formula used in the original transformer (Vaswani et al. 2017) with Q , K , and V being queries, keys, and values, respectively. Those matrices are linear projections of the token's embeddings. d_k is the dimensionality of the keys. A token's query queries the keys by forming a scaled dot product with them. This is a similarity or an importance measure. This score is passed through a softmax function to convert it into a probability distribution and then multiplied by the values to obtain the attention output.

In Multi-Head Attention (MHA), the embeddings' dimensionalities are divided by the number of heads. Thus, MHA divides the queries, keys, and values into h groups, where h is the number of attention heads. Each group is then processed separately through the attention mechanism. This allows the model to learn different attention patterns for each group, which is useful for capturing different aspects of the input. That's why all attention mechanisms in this work use MHA.

Figure 3.2 illustrates how the mechanism works. The example uses 4 dimensions with 2 heads and a sequence length of 5. In the picture, the embeddings are split along their dimensions for the two heads in a). This is then simplified in b), which summarizes the two dimensions for each head in one box for simplicity. The two heads are marked with gray and purple. In c), the embeddings are linearly projected to Q , K , and V while d) denotes the matrix multiplication of Q and K^T to get the attention scores. In the next step, e), the scores are passed through a query-wise softmax to get the attention weights, which are a probability distribution over the keys for each query. This way, each token decides to which other tokens it pays attention. These scores are then multiplied with the values in e). In f), the outputs, denoted as o_n , are concatenated again to the original shape.

Figure 3.2: Multi-head attention.

3.5.1 Guided Attention

One study makes use of the multi-head feature and the different attention patterns during pretraining a RoBERTa model. The authors introduce an Attention Guidance (AG) loss to a number of heads in each layer to learn non-linguistic patterns quickly (Deshpande and Narasimhan 2020). After analyzing BERT attention heads, the authors introduce patterns like attending to the previous, next, first, delimiter, or period token to train a RoBERTa model. They show that the MLM loss can be improved this way while also shortening the training time. Although this results sound promising for model pretraining, their probing analysis revealed that the heads were not able to perform coreference resolution. These findings question the interpretability of attention distributions and show that low MLM loss is not equal to good language understanding.

3.5.2 Sparse Attention

Since the attention scores are mostly retrieved by using self-attention, and therefore through a matrix multiplication of Q with K^T , the time and memory complexity of the attention matrix is $O(n^2)$. As a result, a valuable optimization is to reduce the size of the attention matrix and the number of computations. A number of studies have been done on this topic, including the Graph Attention Network (GAN) (Veličković et al. 2017) which introduced a graph-based self-attention and thus is the building block for MUSTIE’s DOM-to-DOM (DtD) attention mechanism. It can be seen as a restriction of the attention matrix to the neighbors of a token in a graph. Since those can be located anywhere in the input sequence, depending on the type of the graph, the resulting attention matrix is sparse and highly irregular. Thus, it is hard to apply speed-ups like Flash Attention (Dao et al. 2022) or Block Sparse Attention (J. Guo et al. 2024) to it. Subsection 4.4 provides a way of implementing highly irregular attention patterns.

Other studies like Longformer (Beltagy, Peters, and Cohan 2020), BigBird (Zaheer et al. 2020), and Landmark Attention (Mohtashami and Jaggi 2023) work in similar ways by changing the attention matrix and applying sliding window, random, or landmark attention patterns. Landmarks are representations for given blocks in the input and function as a gate to their tokens.

While those approaches remove entries from the attention matrix to reduce work, models like Reformer (Kitaev, Kaiser, and Levskaya 2020), Linformer (Sinong Wang et al. 2020), and Performer (Choromanski et al. 2020) approximate the attention calculation by re-expressing the same full interaction in cheaper math using hashing, kernel approximation, or compression, respectively.

3.6 Continual Learning

While all those models are useful in their particular way, they are trained and limited to the data they know. The ability to adapt to new data, e.g., from new domains, is important as it

saves costly retraining time and resources. In the case of this project, new labels for new domains are created over time and therefore the model have to be adapted to them. "To efficiently adapt LLMs to downstream tasks while minimizing performance degradation on previous knowledge domains, researchers employ the methodology of Continual Learning (CL), also known as lifelong learning or incremental learning" (Shi et al. 2024). Although the comprehensive survey of Shi et al. is focused on the application of CL techniques to LLMs, most of the ideas and terminologies are transferable to smaller models.

CL is a large field and thus should be broken down before continuing to specific techniques. It consists of vertical continuity, which is about the adaption of new domains, and horizontal continuity, which refers to adaption across time, and thus to new data, in known domains. Most CL techniques incorporate both directions to different extends. The vertical continuity axis includes the three stages Continual Pre-Training (CPT), Domain-Adaptive Pre-Training (DAP), and CFT. While CPT covers general shifts, like temporal, content, and language shifts, DAP is used to learn specific domains. CFT, on the other hand, does not extend pretraining, but fine-tunes the model on labeled data or instruction-style data for a concrete downstream task, keeping performance up-to-date while preventing catastrophic forgetting of earlier task data.

CFT can further be broken down into the concepts of Continual Instruction Tuning (CIT) for LLMs, CMR, Continual Model Alignment (CMA), and Continual Multimodal LLMs (CMLLMs). CIT focuses on prompt engineering and tuning them according to changes, while CMR and CMA are used to fine-tune the model on new data. In contrast to CMA, which focuses on new human values, CMR is used to fine-tune the model on new ground truths, which is exactly what is needed in this work. CMLLM, on the other hand, is used to improve the model's cross-modal skills.

CMR (B. Y. Lin, Sida Wang, et al. 2022) offers a setup or framework for efficient fine-tuning with lots of incoming data, of which not everything can be labeled by humans. It essentially is a pipeline for continual adaption of models. The authors suggest taking the most error-prone online examples, labeling them, and using the fresh labels to fine-tune the model. While this learns the new data points, old knowledge might be forgotten. Thus, methods are needed to keep the previously acquired knowledge and prevent overfitting on the new one. Those methods can be distinguished into regularization-based methods, which work via restricting how much a weight can change or penalizing large updates, and replay-based methods, which retain a small subset, the buffer, of past examples and mix them with the new data. While this is computationally more expensive because of the replaying, it is also more robust to forgetting because old labels are partly kept. Studies show that replay-based methods "have great potential to continually improve knowledge retention in the future" (B. Y. Lin, Sida Wang, et al. 2022).

3.7 Active Learning

While CMR provides the pipeline for continual adaption, Active Learning (AL) focuses on the selection of unlabeled data points for labeling. Most of the time, labeling required

significant cost and effort and cannot be done for all data points (J. Park, D. Park, and Lee 2025). One study, for example, shows that using the data point with the highest entropy in a HITL setup can notably improve the model’s metrics with only a few labeled examples (Vidra et al. 2024). Another study, which highlights the cost of human labeling, even shows that labeling can be done using an LLM (Shuohang Wang et al. 2021). While this approach still is worse than human feedback, it is cheap and might provide good and efficient results when mixed with human feedback.

3.8 Dealing with Unlabeled or Unbalanced Data

Nevertheless, models have to deal with unlabeled or unbalanced data sometimes. Especially in multi-label scenarios with only a few positives, negative labels dominate the loss. To mitigate this issue, Asymmetric Loss (ASL) (Ridnik et al. 2020) was introduced. When using the default Binary Cross Entropy (BCE) loss for such a scenario, `pos_weights` have to be used. But too high weights lead to exploding gradients and thus gradient overflow in half-precision training. Furthermore, studies show that naively "reweighting the loss by inverse class frequency usually yields poor performance" (Y. Cui et al. 2019). For this reason, Focal Loss (T. Y. Lin et al. 2017) was developed. It down-weights the loss assigned to well-classified examples, focusing on the hard ones. While this works great for binary or single-label classification tasks, it is not suitable for multi-label classification since "setting high γ , to sufficiently down-weight easy negatives, may eliminate the gradients from the rare positive samples" (Ridnik et al. 2020). To solve this issue, ASL decouples the loss for positive and negative labels, which can be weighted individually. It further introduces a *clip* value to ensure that the gradients of extreme negatives do not contribute too much.

A general form of a binary loss per label, y , is given by (Ridnik et al. 2020):

$$\mathcal{L} = -y\mathcal{L}_+ - (1-y)\mathcal{L}_- \quad \text{or} \quad \mathcal{L} = -[y\mathcal{L}_+ + (1-y)\mathcal{L}_-] \quad (3.2)$$

The following three equations show the BCE, focal, and ASL loss functions with N being the number of labels, σ the sigmoid function, and x and y the logits and the ground truth, respectively. p is the predicted probability, thus $p = \sigma(x)$. γ is a parameter to weight the loss, also called the *focusing parameter*.

$$\mathcal{L}_{BCE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^N -[y_n \log(p_n) + (1-y_n) \log(1-p_n)] \quad \begin{cases} \mathcal{L}_+ = \log(p) \\ \mathcal{L}_- = \log(1-p) \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{focal} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^N - [y_n(1-p_n)^\gamma \log(p_n) + (1-y_n)p_n^\gamma \log(1-p_n)] \quad (3.4)$$

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{L}_+ = (1-p)^\gamma \log(p) \\ \mathcal{L}_- = p^\gamma \log(1-p) \end{cases}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{ASL} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^N - [y_n(1-p_n)^{\gamma_+} \log(p_n) + (1-y_n)p_n^{\gamma_-} \log(1 - \min(1, p_n + clip))] \quad (3.5)$$

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{L}_+ = (1-p)^{\gamma_+} \log(p) \\ \mathcal{L}_- = p^{\gamma_-} \log(1 - \min(1, p + clip)) \end{cases}$$

With this formula, even highly unbalanced datasets can be trained. But sometimes, there are no real negatives. Either if not all the positives are known or if just a few, but not all positives, were labeled. For this case, instead of Positive-Negative (PN) labels, Positive-Unlabeled (PU) are used. Early works already discovered how classifiers can be learned from only positive and unlabeled data (Elkan and Noto 2008). Recent works further researched this topic and extended it to the multi-label setting (Yuan, K. Zhang, and Huang 2023). The authors propose a loss function that removes all negative labels in training and thus uses cleaner annotations. It additionally uses an adaptive re-balance factor like the Focal and ASL as well as an "adaptive temperature coefficient to better adapt PU learning in Multi-Label Classification (MLC) task, which achieves significant performance improvements, especially on small known label proportions" (Yuan, K. Zhang, and Huang 2023). The temperature coefficient makes any class prior unnecessary, which is good since "it performs poorly on the MLC task, as the task is more challenging and many categories have very small class priors" (Yuan, K. Zhang, and Huang 2023). Their final PU loss for a category or class c is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{PU}^{(c)} = p_c^\gamma \log \left(\frac{1}{|\mathcal{U}_N^{(c)}|} \sum_{s_u \in \mathcal{U}_N^{(c)}} \sigma \left(\frac{s_u}{\tau^{(c)}} \right) \right) - \frac{1}{|\mathcal{P}_N^{(c)}|} \sum_{s_p \in \mathcal{P}_N^{(c)}} \sigma \left(\frac{s_p}{\tau^{(c)}} \right) \quad (3.6)$$

with $\mathcal{U}_N^{(c)}$ and $\mathcal{P}_N^{(c)}$ being the unlabeled and positive labeled samples of class c , respectively. p_c^γ denotes the re-balance factor with

$$p_c = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{U}|} \sum_{s_u \in \mathcal{U}} \sigma(s_u) \quad (3.7)$$

being the mean probability of unlabeled samples, and γ is used to control the value of the factor like in Focal or ASL loss. $\tau^{(c)}$ is the temperature coefficient, defined as:

$$\tau^{(c)} = \min(\alpha \cdot \text{Std}(s_c), 1). \quad (3.8)$$

In this equation, α is a hyperparameter that controls the temperature by multiplying it onto the sharpness of each category, which is given by its standard deviation.

The authors further added a regularization term based on Mixup (H. Zhang et al. 2017) to the total loss to prevent overfitting and increase the robustness in PU learning. Since web pages have different sizes and the experimental setup (see chapter 6) doesn't allow two forward passes at once easily, this is not further elaborated upon.

3.9 Handling Hierarchical Data

But there is even more to take into account when it comes to MLC. Labels can have a hierarchy. This is particularly the case for hierarchical data, like HTML, with entity prediction tasks where entities have further information. The following two subsections show how to handle hierarchical labels and data effectively.

3.9.1 Hierarchical Labels

For example, there might be a class `person` and its subclasses `person.name`, `person.age`, and so on. Hierarchical Multi-Label Classification (HMC) exactly covers this case (Giunchiglia and Lukasiewicz 2020). Giunchiglia and Lukasiewicz provide a solution for coherent HMC networks, introducing a hierarchical layer and loss after the normal MLC task. For each class c , there needs to be a hierarchy \mathcal{H}_c that includes class c itself as well as all its descendant classes. Thus, the hierarchy for class `person.name` is just $\{\text{person.name}\}$ and the hierarchy for class `person` is $\{\text{person}, \text{person.name}, \text{person.age}\}$. Then, the probabilities from the MLC task, x , are used as inputs for the Max Constraint Module (MCM), which the authors introduced and calculates the probabilities for each class as follows:

$$MCM_c = \max_{i \in \mathcal{H}_c}(x_i) \quad (3.9)$$

Then, the Max Constraint Loss (MCL) is calculated similar to the general loss style from equation 3.2 with y_c being the ground truth for class c :

$$MCLoss_c = - \left[y \log \left(\max_{i \in \mathcal{H}_c}(x_i y_i) \right) + (1 - y) \log(1 - MCM_c) \right] \quad (3.10)$$

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{L}_+ = \log \left(\max_{i \in \mathcal{H}_c}(x_i y_i) \right) \\ \mathcal{L}_- = \log(1 - MCM_c) \end{cases}$$

"The output [...] ensures that no hierarchy violation happens, i.e., that for any threshold, it cannot be the case that MCM predicts that a data point belongs to [a descendant class, but not to the parent class]" (Giunchiglia and Lukasiewicz 2020). Furthermore, the authors highlight that the MCL guides the model in the right direction as its gradients align with the hierarchy in contrast to the default BCE loss.

3.9.2 Hierarchical Pretraining

During pretraining LMs, however, there are no supervised labels. Instead, MLM is used to teach the model a general understanding of the text it sees. With hierarchical data, simply applying BERT-style masking (Devlin et al. 2018) is not optimal. Studies show that masking whole subtrees, and thus respecting the structure of the data, yields better results (Deng et al. 2022; Gong, Elhoushi, and Cheung 2024). The already described DOM-LM uses this approach and masks entire subtrees while the total masking budget is still kept at 15 %. AST-T5 (Gong, Elhoushi, and Cheung 2024) applies a similar strategy to code, using code blocks as subtrees.

3.10 LLMs and Structured Output

Similar to hierarchical data is structured data, like JavaScript Object Notation (JSON). While JSON can have hierarchies too, in the context of LMs, it is considered as structured data or grammar. When using LLMs to generate structured data like JSON, the model needs to follow the grammar-specific rules during decoding. While LLMs are already trained to generate structured outputs and show impressive performance, they "still struggle with reliably generating complex output structures when not fine-tuned to follow the required output format exactly" (Geng, Josifoski, et al. 2023). When asking for structured data, the output has to be reliable and follow the grammar to 100 %.

To address this issue, methods like Grammar-Constrained Decoding (GCD) can be used to control the probabilities of generated tokens. Tokens that would violate the language-specific are forbidden and cannot be generated (Geng, Josifoski, et al. 2023). Grammar-Aligned Decoding (GAD), however, argues that GCD methods are respecting the grammar but "can distort the LLM's distribution, leading to outputs that are grammatical but appear with likelihoods that are not proportional to the ones given by the LLM, and so ultimately are low-quality" (K. Park et al. 2024). Following those works, the article *Introducing Structured Outputs in the API | OpenAI 2024* introduced structured outputs via the *OpenAI-API*. For this to work, the supplied JSON schema is converted into a context-free grammar, i.e., a set of rules that define a language. Those rules are then used to control the output probabilities of the LLM to follow the schema.

A very recent study evaluated the structured output compliance of different LLMs, showing that *OpenAI* is often matching the schema to 100 % (Geng, Cooper, et al. 2025).

3.11 Recap

This comprehensive chapter discussed the foundation of many important topics for this thesis.

Web scraping is essential for automating data collection and involves data fetching (IR), extraction (IE), and transformation. AI can help to improve scraping efficiency, especially in the extraction stage. For those tasks, transformers usually outperform traditional methods, and models that further leverage the web page’s structure have proven to enhance extraction quality for WIE tasks compared to models ignoring it.

From this starting point, a few transformers were introduced that target specifically the web and HTML structures. Recent studies developed structural attention mechanisms to jointly encode the DOM tree, like MUSTIE does, which performs reasonably well and thus, is chosen as a base model for this work. To encode huge web pages, it uses sparse attention to reduce the number of attention computations, reducing the memory and computational complexity.

Another part of this thesis is Continual Learning (CL). It is a huge field that contains CMR, a framework to improve a model over time using fine-tuning. Together with Active Learning (AL), which decides which new data to label first, powerful learning pipelines can be built.

Nevertheless, models have to deal with suboptimal labels sometimes. Therefore, section 3.8 provides a few new loss functions to deal with unbalanced and unlabeled data. Furthermore, to deal with hierarchical labels, HMC can be used to ensure coherent predictions. Regarding hierarchical data, studies have shown that it works best to mask whole subtrees during pretraining instead of single elements to follow the native hierarchical structure.

Similar to hierarchical data, structured data has its native rules, i.e., grammar, too. Methods like GCD and GAD can be used to control the output of LLMs to follow the grammar. *OpenAI*’s structured output is working this way and yields high reliability and compliance with schemas.

Chapter 4

The Model

This chapter presents the model developed during the course of this work. It describes the implementation of MUSTIE (Q. Wang, J. Wang, et al. 2023) and the details not mentioned in the original paper. Furthermore, it includes customizations made for this project as well as suggestions for potential improvements.

4.1 Overview

MUSTIE is a multimodal web transformer for web information extraction. It uses special structural attention patterns to jointly encode multimodal information and allow different modalities, like structure, text, and image, to communicate with each other. This further enables the model to scale efficiently even with large websites as the attention matrices are sparse, and the input tokens are not simply concatenated. As a full transformer model, it consists of an embedding layer, an encoder, and a decoder.

Since the model encodes DOM elements, texts, and images, the tokens can be of different types. There are DOM tokens representing the HTML nodes and Text and Image (TI) tokens representing the leaves of the nodes and carrying semantic information. As the handling of DOM tokens and TI tokens is a bit different, both token types are represented by their own sequences throughout the model. This makes the handling of them easier. The embedding of each DOM node can be seen as a summarization of the whole subtree under it. Thus, the `<html>` tag represents the entire document and can be used for web page classification, comparable to BERT's CLS token. Figure 4.1 shows an example of a tokenized web with the two token sequences.

The authors inject a special "Field" node into the DOM tree under the root which contains a text of the information to be extracted. For example, when the author should be extracted, the "Field" node contains the text "author". The decoder is used to decode, i.e., extract, the answer from the embedding of the "Field" node, which is encoded together with a web page. Since this project is only interested in tagging HTML elements to extract information from them, the decoder and the "Field" node are omitted in this implementation. This also enables the model to tag multiple elements of potentially different types at once without the need to encode other "Field" values with the same web page several times,

Figure 4.1: Example web page (fictitious content generated with ChatGPT) with a) the DOM token sequence and b) the TI token sequence.

removing one of the limitations mentioned in the paper.

Figure 4.2 shows the overall model architecture, which will be described in detail in the following sections.

4.2 Embedding Layer

To turn the input tokens into vectors, the embedding layer is the first layer of the model. It provides different types of embeddings, which are added up to obtain the final embedding of a token type. Specifically, DOM tokens are calculated using the sum of a type embedding, a tag embedding, and a position embedding. The TI tokens are calculated using the sum of a type embedding and a word or patch embedding, respectively, as follows:

Figure 4.2: Model overview.

$$\begin{aligned}
 E^{(D)} &= E_{type}^{(D)} + E_{tag}^{(D)} + E_{pos}^{(D)} \\
 E^{(T)} &= E_{type}^{(T)} + E_{word}^{(T)} \\
 E^{(I)} &= E_{type}^{(I)} + E_{patch}^{(I)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

All those embeddings are learnable vectors. The type embedding has values for each token type, i.e., DOM, text, and image tokens, and an additional padding vector for the padding token. Thus, its embedding count is 4. Padding is used when web pages in the same batch have different amounts of tokens to make them equally sized and create a tensor, which only allows matrices, i.e., a list of items of the same shape.

The position embedding learns absolute position vectors as in BERT and depends on the maximum input length configured for DOM tokens. The tag embeddings provide an embedding for each HTML tag, plus some special tags introduced by the preprocessor

(5.1), like "PAD", "MASK", "ALT", and "UNKNOWN". In total, it consists of 129 embeddings. The "PAD" tag is used for padding, "MASK" for masking (6.2.2), and "UNKNOWN" is used for tags that are not in the list of known HTML tags. The "ALT" tag is a special token that is injected under images that have a non-empty alt attribute. It is added as the first child inside the `` as an additional node with the attribute's value as text content. In the original paper, the authors also add an "OCR" tag that contains text recognized using Optical Character Recognition (OCR) on the image. This is not implemented in this project because most of the images in the target domain do not contain text. Rather, the images should provide context for the type of the page. Images containing landscape, for example, should yield a different page context than web pages with images of fashion.

The word embeddings are copied from BERT-base. The checkpoint used to obtain them is "bert-base-multilingual-cased", since the model should learn German and English content and cased vocabulary might help it to identify names, nouns, and proper nouns better. The word embedding count, therefore, is 119,547.

Finally, the patch embeddings are not a typical embedding. Rather, the last hidden state of ResNet101 (He et al. 2016) is used and projected to the configured hidden size. This means that each image is converted into 49 contextualized patch embeddings through ResNet and then projected through a linear layer to the model's hidden size. Thus, the resulting embedding count, i.e., linear layer input size, is 2048, which is the dimensionality of the patch embeddings.

The embedding layer additionally hosts learnable vectors representing the connection type between two nodes, i.e., self, parent, sibling, or child, resulting in 4 embeddings. These vectors are used inside the encoder and shared across all layers. At the end of the embedding layer, a configurable embedding dropout is applied to all embeddings.

4.3 Encoder

After obtaining all embeddings, they are passed to the encoder. The encoder is a stack of transformer layers, which contextualize the embeddings. An encoder layer consists of three modules: an attention layer, an intermediate or Feed-Forward (FF) layer, and an output layer.

4.3.1 Attention Module

The attention module is the heart of the model. It allows the multimodal information to communicate with each other and enriches the raw embeddings with context. The module itself is composed of three further modules: a Layer Normalization (LN), the structural attention module, and an output module.

Layer Normalization

First, the DOM and TI embeddings are layer normalized (Ba, Kiros, and Hinton 2016). That rescales and recenters the embeddings, which causes more stable gradients and faster

Figure 4.3: Structural attention overview.

convergence. It is applied first in a layer since this model follows the pre-LN architecture (Xiong et al. 2020) instead of the post-LN architecture used in the original transformer. This improves the benefits of LN even further, removing the need for extensive hyperparameter tuning and long warmup.

Structural Attention

After rescaling the embeddings, MUSTIE’s structural attention is applied. There are four attention mechanisms proposed by the authors; two for each type of token. DOM tokens attend to one another using DtD attention and to TI tokens using Bottom-Up (BU) attention. TI tokens attend among themselves with Local Attention (LA) and to DOM tokens with TD attention. These four mechanisms are described in detail below.

Figure 4.3 shows an overview of them for the example web page from figure 4.1. The DtD edges are shown for the `<body>` tag, while BU edges are drawn for the "Contact Us" `<h2>`. The token "Recent" visualizes the TD attention, and LA edges are created for the "contact" token. All arrows point from source to destination or query to key.

DOM-to-DOM attention lets DOM tokens attend to surrounding DOM tokens. This way, it transfers knowledge across the DOM tree locally. Surrounding tokens are a) the parent, b) the token itself, c) all children, and d) all siblings. Thus, this attention mechanism is a kind of graph attention across the DOM tree. When a token attends to another token, its query is querying the other token’s key. This key, in contrast to the default attention formula, is added to the learnable type vector from the embedding layer representing the

Figure 4.4: DOM-to-DOM attention matrix.

relation of the querying token to the attended token. This means that a token, which attends its parent, is querying the parent’s key plus the vector representing the parent relationship.

$$\begin{aligned}
 e_{ij}^{DD} &= \frac{x_i^D W_Q^{DD} (x_j^D W_K^{DD} + t_{ij}^{DD})^\top}{\sqrt{d}} \\
 a_{ij}^{DD} &= \frac{\exp(e_{ij}^{DD})}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{S}(x_i^D)} \exp(e_{ik}^{DD})}, \forall x_i^D \in X^D, \forall x_j^D \in \mathcal{S}(x_i^D)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.2}$$

Equation 4.2 formalizes this attention mechanism, where DD stands for DOM-to-DOM. e_{ij}^{DD} is the attention score and a_{ij}^{DD} the attention weight between DOM token x_i^D and x_j^D of DOM input sequence X^D while $\mathcal{S}(x_i^D)$ denotes all tokens x_j^D can attend to. W_Q^{DD} and W_K^{DD} are the learnable weights for query and key projections, respectively, and t_{ij}^{DD} is the learnable connection type vector from the embedding layer.

With $\mathcal{S}(x_i^D)$ being only a small fraction of all tokens (5.2.4), this attention mechanism is highly sparse and efficient and scales linearly with the number of DOM tokens because the average number of connections per node stays the same. The only exception is the attention between siblings. If an element like a list has many children, e.g., a thousand, the attention matrix is quadratic between them. That’s why a radius of 8 is added. This means that A DOM token can only see up to 8 DOM tokens on each side of it. Figure 4.4 visualizes the attention matrix for the example web page from figure 4.1.

While this attention is powerful and efficient to encode the structural modality along the natural graph, this mechanism only allows local attention to the neighboring tokens. With L being the number of transformer layers, a token could maximally attend to tokens that are L hops away. Therefore, for a 12-layer model, it is 12 hops. For deeply nested web pages, this might be problematic because a parent can have several wrapper descendants

before a semantic leaf occurs.

The next attention mechanism for DOM nodes is **BU** attention. It enriches the DOM tokens with semantics from their TI leaves. To do that, a DOM token x_i^D attends to all TI tokens x_j^{TI} that are direct children of x_i^D in the tree, which is denoted as collection $C_i = \{w_1^i, \dots, w_{n_i}^i\}$ where w_j^i is the j -th text or image token in C_i . Thus, $C = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ denotes all leaves of the input. The mechanism is formalized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{ij}^{BU} &= \frac{x_i^D W_Q^{BU} (x_j^{TI} W_K^{BU})^\top}{\sqrt{d}} \\ a_{ij}^{BU} &= \frac{\exp(e_{ij}^{BU})}{\sum_{k \in C_i} \exp(e_{ik}^{BU})}, \forall x_i^D \in X^D, \forall x_j^{TI} \in C_i \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

where W_Q^{BU} and W_K^{BU} are the weight matrices in BU attention. Note that each mechanism has its own learnable weights. That enables the model to learn different patterns for different modalities and "communication channels" between them.

Again, this attention mechanism is sparse since only DOM tokens containing TI tokens contribute to it and only attend to their own TI tokens. It scales linearly with the number of TI tokens from the input sequence X^{TI} because there is only one connection per TI token, namely to its parent. This is shown in the attention matrix, which is provided in figure A.2 in appendix A.

The TI tokens also have two attention mechanisms. The first one is **LA** between TI tokens. It functions like the classical self-attention in LMs. To keep it efficient, it is limited to tokens of the same leaf. Thus, the attention matrix is again sparse but scales quadratically with the number of tokens in a leaf. In the best case, leaves are small, as many in web documents are, and just contain a handful of tokens, e.g., a price or a name. In the worst case, an element, like a paragraph, contains almost all TI tokens from the input and thus forces the overall attention matrix to be full and quadratic again. To mitigate this, WebFormer uses a radius r , which means that a token can attend to a maximum of r neighbors to its left and right. This mirrors the sliding window used in Longformer. The authors of MUSTIE don't mention such a mechanism. Nevertheless, it is used in this implementation with a radius of 128, which means that a token can attend to 257 tokens in total: 128 on the left and right side, and itself. This collection of possible connections for x_i^{TI} is denoted as $\mathcal{R}(x_i^{TI})$ In signs:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{ij}^{LA} &= \frac{x_i^{TI} W_Q^{LA} (x_j^{TI} W_K^{LA})^\top}{\sqrt{d}} \\ a_{ij}^{LA} &= \frac{\exp(e_{ij}^{LA})}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{R}(x_i^{TI})} \exp(e_{ik}^{LA})}, \forall C_l \in C, \forall x_i^{TI} \in C_l, \forall x_j^{TI} \in \mathcal{R}(x_i^{TI}) \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

The attention matrix is supplied in figure A.1 in appendix A.

The last attention mechanism is **TD** attention. This mechanism connects every TI token with every DOM token, rendering it the only true full attention is the model. It

scales linearly with the number of DOM tokens and linearly with the number of TI tokens in the input. Thus, when both sequence limits are increased, the complexity increases quadratically. The TD attention lets every TI token retrieve high-level information from other DOM nodes and thus, let overall structure information flow from DOM to TI tokens. Padded tokens are excluded from the calculation.

$$\begin{aligned}
 e_{ij}^{TD} &= \frac{x_i^{TI} W_Q^{TD} (x_j^D W_K^{TD})^\top}{\sqrt{d}} \\
 a_{ij}^{TD} &= \frac{\exp(e_{ij}^{TD})}{\sum_{k \in X^D} \exp(e_{ik}^{TD})}, \forall x_i^{TI} \in X^{TI}, \forall x_j^D \in X^D
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.5}$$

This way, every DOM token can attend to every other DOM token and the overall document structure within two hops via its leaf tokens and BU attention, counteracting the limitations of the DtD connection. But it is questionable whether this is enough for them to get the site structure since the information flow would dilute and a TI token should focus on its semantical meaning in the web page context rather than the whole web page context. On the other hand, it might not be necessary for a DOM token to get the site structure since it represents its subtree and only needs to know what is below it with semantics enriched by the site’s context.

An attention dropout is applied to all attention weights a . The final representation z for the tokens is obtained by adding the two attention mechanisms per token type:

$$\begin{aligned}
 z_i^D &= \sum_{x_j \in \mathcal{S}(x_i^D)} a_{ij}^{DD} x_j^D W_V^D + \sum_{x_j \in C_i} a_{ij}^{BU} x_j^{TI} W_V^{TI} \\
 z_i^{TI} &= \sum_{x_j \in \mathcal{R}(x_i^{TI})} a_{ij}^{LA} x_j^{TI} W_V^{TI} + \sum_{x_j \in X^D} a_{ij}^{TD} x_j^D W_V^D
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.6}$$

Note that in contrast to the attention type-specific key and query weights, the value weights are shared between all attention types and only differ between DOM and TI tokens.

Attention Output

After calculating the attention representations, they are passed through the attention output. The output is a simple linear layer, which takes and outputs the same dimensionality, followed by a dropout and a residual connection (He et al. 2016) to the input of the attention module. The linear layer is needed because the attention outputs from the MHA are concatenated to restore the model’s original dimensionality. Thus, the head outputs are still separated inside the same vector. The linear layer mixes them and lets the model learn any linear combination of head information that might be useful.

4.3.2 Intermediate or Feed-Forward Module

After that, the attention output is passed through a feed-forward module, which consists of a layer norm again, a dense layer, and an activation function. The dense layer quadruples the dimensionality of the input. Together with the activation function, this adds depth and non-linearity to the model to learn more complex representations. GELU (Hendrycks and Gimpel 2016) is used as the activation function since it is used in BERT and is widely used in transformer models.

4.3.3 Output Module

The last encoder module is the output module. It takes the high-dimensional outputs from the FF module, projects them back to the original dimensionality, and applies a dropout as well as a residual connection to the attention outputs to obtain the final layer output.

With each layer, the embeddings become more contextualized. Those contextualized embeddings are also referred to as hidden states. The last hidden state is the final output of the encoder and is used for decoding or prediction tasks. In this case, several prediction heads are used, which are further described in chapter 6. Therefore, the final model output depends on the heads.

4.4 Implementation Details

To implement the attention patterns of this model, different approaches are used. The full TD attention uses *PyTorch*'s `scaled_dot_product_attention` function to calculate the attention outputs using flash attention (Dao et al. 2022). This way, it is still quite fast and efficient since it does not materialize the attention scores. A mask removing padded tokens is also given together the function.

For the sparse attention patterns, the procedure is different. The preprocessor (5.1) creates all possible edges for the different attention mechanisms, $E = \{E_1, \dots, E_n\}$ with E being the mass of all edges for one mechanism. A given edge consists of exactly two token IDs: the query and the key/value token ID. Thus, $E_i = (q_i, k_i)$. During the attention calculation, the list is separated into query indices, source, and key/value indices, destination, with $Src = \{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ and $Dst = \{k_1, \dots, k_n\}$. Figure 4.5 visualizes this mechanic and shows the sparse attention matrix together with the edge list. Edges belonging to the same query and thus are in the same group-index for the scatter softmax and scatter add operations are colored the same.

Since the length of the edge list is highly variable, it is not padded to a fixed length. Instead, all edges from the batch items are concatenated and another tensor, the *pointer*, contains the index to the first edge of each batch item to distinguish the edges of different batch items. With the help of the pointer, a `batch_idx` tensor can be created, which contains in-batch item index for each edge. Together with the edge list and the two lists `src` and `dst`, the queries, keys, and values participating in the attention can be selected by

Figure 4.5: Sparse attention matrix and edges.

using `query[batch_idx, :, src]`, for example, where the colon selects all heads. If a key bias is needed, like in DtD attention, it is also given to the attention function and added to the selected queries as it has the same length as E .

After selecting the queries and keys, the attention weights are calculated by using matrix multiplication, in this case the einsum or Einstein summation $ehd, ehd \rightarrow eh$, where e is the number of edges, h the number of heads, and d the dimensionality of the embeddings.

Flash attention cannot be used here since the edges come from different tokens and in-batch items, and thus, the softmax cannot be calculated as usual. Instead, a group-index is calculated by multiplying the `batch_idx` tensor with the length of the query sequence, N_Q , and adding the query indices, Src . To make it multi-head, the sequence is repeated h times while the index of the head is added to the group-index. This way, each querying token has a unique ID per batch item and per head. Figure 4.6 shows the calculation of the group-index with 10 edges from 2 batch items with a sequence length of 5 for 2 heads.

The resulting group-index is used to calculate the attention weights from the scores. The *Python* package *PyTorch Scatter*¹ provides functionalities to work with scattered operations based on a given group-index tensor. The function `scatter_softmax` is used to calculate the softmax over all scores with the same group-index, which works because the group-index is equal for all edges with the same query token. The final output is obtained by using another scatter function, `scatter_add`, which sums up the product of the attention weights and the values with the same group-index.

The scatter attention mechanism is provided completely in appendix ???. In general, the function can be formalized as:

¹https://github.com/rusty1s/pytorch_scatter

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9										
edges	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	2	2	src									
	0	1	3	2	0	1	2	1	2	4	dst									
batch pointer	0	4	10																	
batch_idx	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1										
* NQ	0	0	0	0	5	5	5	5	5	5										
+src	0	1	1	2	5	5	5	6	7	7										
2 heads	0	1	1	2	5	5	5	6	7	7										
* h + h	0	2	2	4	10	10	10	12	14	14	1	3	3	5	11	11	11	13	15	15

Figure 4.6: Group-index calculation.

$$\begin{aligned}
 src &= 0, \quad dst = 1 \\
 e_i &= \frac{Q_{i_{src}}(K_{i_{dst}} + b_i)^\top}{\sqrt{d}} \\
 a_i &= \frac{\exp(e_i)}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{E}(i)} \exp(e_j)}, \\
 z_i &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{E}(i)} a_j V_{j_{dst}} \quad \forall i \in E, \quad \mathcal{E}(i) = \{x | x \in E, x_{src} = i_{src}\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.7}$$

with b_i being an optional bias for the edge i and $\mathcal{E}(i)$ denoting the set of edges with the same source as i .

This kind of sparse attention with all possible pairs being represented by edges enables compute- and memory-efficient calculations. The complexity shrinks from $O(N^2)$ to $O(E)$, where the size of E depends on the specific mechanism as discussed in the previous section. Only a small overhead of storing E edges is required.

4.5 Suggestions and Improvements

Although MUSTIE renders promising results and an efficient model architecture for web documents, there might be changes that could further improve the model. This section presents some theoretical ideas for potential improvements.

4.5.1 Position Embeddings

In equation 4.1, only the DOM tokens get a position embedding. This way, however, the TI tokens inside the same leaf are treated like a bag of words and not like a proper sequence. While this might be sufficient for small leaves and node-tagging tasks, it doesn't cover complex semantical connections, especially in long leaves like paragraphs.

Furthermore, while one-dimensional absolute position embeddings might, they don't reflect the DOM tree's structure well. DOM-LM offers a comprehensive positioning matrix, which could be adapted for MUSTIE. All in all, the final position notation would be:

$$\begin{aligned} POS^D &= POS_{idx_d}^{(abs)} + POS_{depth} + POS_{sibling_{idx}}^{(parent)} + POS_{parent_{idx}}^{(abs)} \\ POS^{TI} &= POS_{idx_{ti}}^{(abs)} + POS_{idx}^{(leaf)} + POS^D \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

where the superscript part denotes the scope of the positioning. For example, $(parent)$ denotes the position inside the parent while (abs) means the absolute position across the whole document. All position elements get their own embedding table.

4.5.2 Semantic Connections

While position embeddings might help the model to better understand the structure of the DOM tree and thus, to use the semantics of text, they don't cover small leaves, like spans, which reference leaf tokens from a neighboring node or parent. For example, in the HTML snippet

```
<p>The price is <span>10 €</span> for adults and <span>5
€</span> for children.</p>
```

the tokens from the `` tags cannot directly attend to the tokens of the paragraph and vice versa. Thus, each span may know that it is price, but not for what exactly. To mitigate this, the preprocessor could further add edges between leaf tokens from different leaves up to the next semantical block, which can also be the hosting node itself. This way, it won't add many extra attention edges, which could potentially improve the semantic understanding while keeping the computational effort nearly the same. Semantical blocks are those DOM nodes with HTML tags like

```
<article>, <div>, <footer>, <header>, <img>, <main>, <nav>, <ol>,
<p>, <section>, <table>, <tbody>, <title>, <tr>, <ul>
```

because they usually host content that belongs together. Figure 4.7 shows the LA edges for the token "contact" from the example web page in figure 4.1 when using semantic connections.

4.5.3 Redefining the Tod-Down Attention

While one might think that fitting the structural information from the DOM tree into the TI tokens through TD attention, the authors of WebFormer found that those modalities are complementary and orthogonal (Q. Wang, Fang, et al. 2022). Thus, this attention mechanism is substantial.

However, it is full and computationally expensive, especially for large documents. That's why it might be possible for the model to exploit the DOM nodes' function as

Figure 4.7: Local attention with semantic connections for the token "contact".

subtree representations for more efficient TD attention using landmarks (Mohtashami and Jaggi 2023).

For this to work, the preprocessor has to mark certain nodes containing a configurable subtree size budget as landmark tokens. This process is recursive and requires excluding the subtrees of already created landmarks for equal landmark distribution across the tree. Then, it adds edges to the DtD attention from those landmark tokens to all of their respective descendant tokens, which are not already covered by the default DtD edges. To stay consistent with the key bias, the connection type embedding could get another embedding for "*landmark*" connections. Finally, during TD attention, TI tokens only have to attend to the landmarks since they already represent their whole subtree. Figure 4.8 shows the landmarks together with their subtree sizes and connections they are attending to for a maximum subtree size of 3. Note that the size of the landmarks is always greater than the maximum because setting them differently would result in marks that are too small.

This would dramatically reduce the number of attention computations. Let S be the maximum subtree size of a landmark and LM the number of landmarks in the document. If S is set to 32 and the maximum size of input X^D is 1024, a perfectly distributed tree would have $LM \approx 32$ landmarks. Even if the tree is not equally distributed, the number of total landmarks can be kept small. A landmark is only created when its subtree has at least 80% of the maximum size S , which is useful when a list, for example, has more than S elements. This way, even if the subtree size is greater than S , the landmark is created for the list and not for every item in it. Even with 8 times the perfect distribution ($LM = 256$) and 4 times larger landmarks, which has a theoretical capacity of 32,768 nodes, the number of attention computations is just one-fourth of the original TD attention for $|X^{TI}| = 2048$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_{Att}^{org} &= |X^D| \cdot |X^{TI}| \\
 &= 1024 \cdot 2048 = 2,097,152 \\
 C_{Att}^{new} &= LM \cdot S + LM \cdot |X^{TI}| \\
 &= 256 \cdot 128 + 256 \cdot 2048 = 557,056
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.9}$$

Figure 4.8: Landmarks with their subtree sizes and connections for a maximum size of 3.

with C_{Att}^{org} and C_{Att}^{new} being the number of attention computations for the original and proposed TD attention, respectively.

Although this would be a great saving, it is questionable if the accuracy would be sufficient and this two-hop mechanism would not dilute the information flow too much.

4.6 Recap

MUSTIE is a capable model for HTML documents. Through its 4 attention mechanisms, DtD, BU, TD, and LA, it efficiently encodes the different modalities of structure, texts, and images. This implementation omits the decoder, "Field" node, and OCR. It follows a pre-LN transformer architecture and implements a sliding window mechanism for LA. The vocabulary is taken from bert-base-multilingual-cased, while for images, ResNet101 is used. To implement the sparse attention mechanisms, a special scatter attention function was developed that takes a list of edges to efficiently calculate the attention outputs.

Furthermore, this chapter made some suggestions for *possible and theoretical* improvements. MUSTIE could use a more comprehensive position embedding, like in DOM-LM, semantic connections to improve LA context, or a more efficient TD attention instead of a full one.

Chapter 5

The Data

To use the model described in the previous chapter, this chapter is about the data used to train and evaluate it. At first, it provides an overview of the preprocessing pipeline every HTML document went through. After that, it presents the different datasets, including why and how they are created, as well as a detailed analysis.

5.1 Preprocessing

As an AI model needs clean and tokenized data, prepared with all the features needed, it cannot directly take the HTML of a web page. In the context of this work, the cleaning is usually done beforehand during inference. But for training, this is done after retrieving the datasets, as the training process runs separately.

5.1.1 Cleaning

Cleaning an HTML document is important as it removes noise and irrelevant content. Furthermore, it keeps the document as small and simple as possible to save disk space and processing time and increase prediction accuracy.

To clean an HTML document, certain tags are completely removed as they do not contain meaningful content for node tagging. These tags are:

```
<form>, <input>, <link>, <meta>, <noscript>, <script>, <search>,
<select>, <style>, <svg>
```

The `<svg>` tag is removed since its content produces a lot of unnecessary tokens and cannot be evaluated sophisticatedly anyway. Although some `<meta>` tags might provide valuable information, like a page description, it still is omitted because most of those tags introduce non-informative texts and noise. Furthermore, not all web pages contain meaningful descriptions or a description at all.

After eliminating unnecessary tags, unwanted attributes are removed. These are all attributes except `alt`, `href`, and `src`. The `alt` attribute is kept as an image description

and is injected into the DOM tree during tokenization (5.1.2) while the other two are kept to be able to restore a link's destination or an image's src after tagging.

The last cleaning step is to simplify the tree. It applies the following methods to do so:

- Remove all comments and DOCTYPE elements.
- Strip leading and trailing whitespace from all text elements or remove them if blank.
- Remove duplicate nodes. These occur because some websites support multiple device sizes by introducing the same content with different styling. Since the model does not see any styling, those duplicates are removed.
- Flatten all `<div>` nodes with just one child, i.e., replace them with their child node.
- Remove all empty nodes. A node is empty if it has no inner text or attributes.

5.1.2 Tokenization

After cleaning comes tokenization. That is the process of converting the cleaned HTML into small pieces, tokens, that the model can process and understand. Since MUSTIE needs a different set of inputs than other LMs, a custom preprocessor had to be implemented.

The input for the preprocessor consists of the URL of the web page and its cleaned HTML content. It uses *lxml*¹ to process the data efficiently. To work properly, it needs to traverse over the DOM tree twice: once for indexing and once for the actual tokenization.

During indexing, each node is assigned a unique index by walking down the tree. Unknown tags are replaced with the `<UNKNOWN>` tag. Furthermore, images are prepared. Their `alt` text is inserted under a special `<ALT>` tag inside the `` tag, and the image data is downloaded from its source, if available.

During tokenization, the preprocessor creates several `int`, `float`, and `bool` lists to be saved in the datasets. On each DOM node, it saves the following information of the node:

- The token ID, which is the index of the node tag in the tag list of available HTML tags. These are provided in appendix B.
- A list of DtD edges, containing the token's index as well as the other tokens' indices in the resulting sequence as well as the type of the connection as described in 4.2. That's one example of why the indexing is needed as indices of right sibling nodes are unknown otherwise because subtree sizes are unknown.
- If classes for classification are provided via a configuration, a list containing a `True` or `False` for each label is created, indicating whether the node contains the respective class in its `class` attribute.
- If categories are provided in the configuration, a list for them is created following the same procedure. Categories are used during finetuning for a retrieval task (6.3.4). This is also done for categories marked as "main".
- The depth of the node in the DOM tree.

¹<https://lxml.de>

- The sibling index of the node, meaning the index of the node in its parent.

On each text element or image, the preprocessor does the following:

1. It tokenizes the text or image by using `BertTokenizerFast` or `ResNet101`'s last hidden state, respectively.
2. It adds those tokens either to the list of text tokens or to the list of image tokens, respectively.
3. For each token, adds the index referencing the token in the two lists above to the list of TI token IDs. This is helpful because the two lists have different dimensions. The text tokens are just one ID, while the image tokens are the last hidden state from `ResNet101` and have a dimensionality of 2048. Thus, if a token is added to one of those lists, the preprocessor takes the index from that list and adds it to the list of TI token IDs.
4. For each token, adds the type, i.e., text or image, to the list of token types. Together with the list of TI token IDs, a token can now be identified in its respective list.
5. For each token, adds the index of the hosting node to the list of TI node indices. These nodes are also referred to as the respective parents of the TI tokens.
6. Finally, it calculates the LA edges for the tokens.

To sum up, the preprocessor provides a dictionary as output with keys and data types as shown in table 5.1.

Because `ResNet101` outputs 49 patch embeddings for each image, an image is represented by 49 tokens. To limit the number of image tokens per page, the preprocessor only processes the first 10 images. On the one hand, not many web pages provide more than 10 meaningful images. On the other hand, the benefit of having more images is lowering because the text input is proportionally decreasing. Furthermore, images that are smaller than 32 pixels on one axis or smaller than 100 pixels on both axes are ignored to reduce noise.

Figure 5.1 shows the preprocessor output for the example web page from figure 4.1. Enum values for token or edge types are provided in appendix B.

5.2 Datasets

Different datasets are used to train the model. Because there are no annotations in web documents for charitable projects from rural areas yet, a few are labeled by hand. Nevertheless, a transformer model like `MUSTIE` needs way more data than a few hundred web pages. Following Chinchilla's law, an LM should see 20 times more tokens than parameters (Hoffmann et al. 2022). Thus, the small dataset to detect projects, referred to as the finetuning dataset, is not enough. Furthermore, to be able to generalize over multiple web pages and domains, the model requires a more general understanding of web pages, including layout and semantics. This is the role of a pretrained model. Unfortunately, there

Table 5.1: Preprocessor output with keys and data types of the resulting dictionary.

Key	Data type
url	string
origin	string
dom_token_ids	Tensor(shape=(D), dtype=uint8)
node_depths	Tensor(shape=(D), dtype=uint8)
sibling_indices	Tensor(shape=(D), dtype=uint16)
text_tokens	Tensor(shape=(T), dtype=int32)
img_tokens	Tensor(shape=(I, 2048), dtype=float32)
ti_token_ids	Tensor(shape=(T + I), dtype=uint16)
ti_node_indices	Tensor(shape=(T + I), dtype=uint16)
ti_type_ids	Tensor(shape=(T + I), dtype=uint8)
dd_edges	Tensor(shape=(DE, 2), dtype=uint16)
dd_edge_types	Tensor(shape=(DE), dtype=uint8)
la_edges	Tensor(shape=(LE, 2), dtype=uint16)
Optional, if given:	
labels	Tensor(shape=(D, len(classes)), dtype=bool)
categories	Tensor(shape=(D, len(categories)), dtype=bool)
main_categories	Tensor(shape=(D, len(categories)), dtype=bool)

D, T, I, DE, and LE are denoting sequence lengths for the node, text, and image sequence lengths and DtD and LA edges, respectively.

```
{
  "dom_token_ids": [ 57,  53, 115, 18, 47, 84, 48, 120, 68, 2, 60, 127, 68, 2, 35, 48, 84, 2],
  "node_depths": [0, 1, 2, 1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 3, 4, 2, 3, 3, 4],
  "sibling_indices": [0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 4, 0, 1, 0],
  "text_tokens": [22091, 10106, 10105, 18888, 118, 23952, 39007, 37347, 22091, 10106, 10105, 18888,
    12865, 10301, 169, 10446, 118, 25081, 17583, 14616, 10114, 33992, 18314, 10114, 55911, 12286,
    117, 14943, 117, 10111, 17004, 22277, 10106, 18380, 25240, 119, 45459, 14300, 10107, 96013,
    10107, 12585, 169, 12286, 11206, 79657, 17702, 25325, 26393, 12952, 10142, 33543, 77562, 27582,
    11289, 35240, 131, 20637, 137, 14351, 119, 10733],
  "img_tokens": ["..."],
  "ti_token_ids": [0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22,
    23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10,
    11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34,
    35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48,
    49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61],
  "ti_type_ids": [2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2,
    2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3,
    3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3,
    2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2],
  "ti_node_indices": [2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 4, 4, 4, 4, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5,
    5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 6, 6, 6, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10,
    10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10,
    10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10,
    15, 16, 16, 16, 17, 17, 17, 17, 17],
  "dd_edges": [[0, 0], [0, 1], [0, 3], [1, 0], [1, 1], [1, 3], [1, 2], [2, 1], [2, 2], "..."],
  "dd_edge_types": [0, 2, 2, 1, 0, 3, 2, 1, 0, "..."],
  "la_edges": [[0, 0], [0, 1], [0, 2], [0, 3], [0, 4], [0, 5], [0, 6], [0, 7], [1, 0], "..."]
}
```

Figure 5.1: Preprocessor output for an example web page.

is no pretrained MUSTIE model yet. That's why a pretraining phase and dataset are added before running the finetuning.

Since the scope of this project is to extract projects from German web pages, all datasets are limited to German and English websites. English is chosen too because there is more English data available, and it might help the model because of language overlaps.

5.2.1 Pretraining Dataset

The pretraining dataset is used to train a general web transformer encoder, which is able to create precise vector representations for web documents. Thus, it needs a large amount of diverse data. The data is retrieved from two data sources: *Wikimedia Dumps*² and *Common Crawl*³.

The *Wikimedia Dumps* page provides dumps containing the HTML of *Wikipedia*⁴ articles in different languages. To use up-to-date data, the dump from 2025-03-20 is used. The data comes from namespace 0, which is the article namespace where the primary content resides (*API Schema & Data Dictionary - Wikimedia Enterprise* 2025). One file per language, German⁵ and English⁶, is downloaded. Those archives contain multiple files containing one article per line. Each line is parsed and preprocessed before adding it to the dataset.

To use the *Common Crawl* data, the *Hugging Face* datasets *Fineweb* (Penedo, Kydlíček, Allal, et al. 2024) for English data and *Fineweb2* (Penedo, Kydlíček, Sabolčec, et al. 2025) for German data are used. Each entry represents a web page from *Common Crawl* and contains the web page's URL, text, language, and *Common Crawl* WARC⁷ file reference. Here, the crawl from October 2024 is used: CC-MAIN-2024-10. For the *Fineweb* dataset, this crawl could be selected via the dataset name, while for *Fineweb2*, the data extraction is more complex. Since *Fineweb2* consists of multiple languages and only German is needed, the name of the dataset is `deu_Latn`. Unfortunately, there is no way to select the crawl here, as the name of the dataset defines the language. Thus, the dataset starts at a crawl from 2013 and ends with the latest crawls, but not necessarily in chronological order. Because it is neither possible to download the whole dataset nor desirable to completely iterate through it, the single Parquet files are analyzed to find the CC-MAIN-2024-10 crawl. The *Hugging Face* datasets library offers a way to specify `data_files` that should be used. This option is set to `"data/deu_Latn/train/003_00037.parquet"` as this file contains many web pages for the requested crawl.

Unfortunately, the data does not contain the HTML, as it is designed for usual LMs, but the HTML can be received from the WARC files. To keep the processing efficient, the

²<https://dumps.wikimedia.org>

³<https://commoncrawl.org>

⁴<https://wikipedia.org>

⁵https://dumps.wikimedia.org/other/enterprise_html/runs/20250320/dewiki-NS0-20250320-ENTERPRISE-HTML.json.tar.gz

⁶https://dumps.wikimedia.org/other/enterprise_html/runs/20250320/enwiki-NS0-20250320-ENTERPRISE-HTML.json.tar.gz

⁷The Web ARChive file format: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/WARC_\(file_format\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/WARC_(file_format))

dataset entries are grouped by WARC file, such that each file only needs to be downloaded and processed once. As soon as all HTMLs are collected, they are cleaned, preprocessed, and added to the pretraining dataset.

To put everything together, 200,000 web pages from Fineweb, 200,000 web pages from Fineweb2, and 75,000 web pages from *Wikimedia Dumps* for each language are collected as pretraining data. For each data source, the first pages are used up to the limit. The dataset is split by splitting each of the four sub-datasets and merging the related splits to keep them balanced and ensure each contains the same ratio of data from every data source and language. The splits follow an 80/10/10 train/dev/test distribution. The Fineweb and Fineweb2 sets are split by domains, ensuring that web pages from the same domain are in the same split to evaluate the model's ability to generalize over different and unseen domains. The split for *Wikipedia* pages is just a random split as splitting by domains is obviously not possible in this case.

5.2.2 Intermediate Task Training Dataset

Since there are works showing that continued pretraining and intermediate task training might be helpful for the final downstream task (Gururangan et al. 2020; Pruksachatkun et al. 2020), an Intermediate Task Training (ITT) is created to add a second training stage before finetuning. Since the finetuning set is very small, this is considered helpful.

For this stage, a task based on *Schema.org*⁸ annotations is defined (6.3.3). The data is provided by the Web Data Commons (WDC) dataset (Brinkmann, Primpeli, and Bizer 2023). The authors extracted the annotations from the *Common Crawl* data. Here, the newest extraction from the crawl from December 2024 is used. The annotations are provided in the N-Quads format. Thus, each line of the files contains a quad. The quads are parsed, and their URLs used to gather information like language and WARC file of the web pages from a local *Common Crawl Index Server*⁹. This server runs locally to avoid rate limits and speed up requests. With this information, the pages are filtered by language and grouped by their WARC files to fetch the HTML afterward like for the pretraining dataset.

The difference here is, that the annotations are added after cleaning and before the preprocessing step. Atomic fields are annotated by searching their value in the HTML and annotating the smallest, i.e., deepest, element that contains the value for each match. When it comes to objects, the smallest element containing all fields is annotated. The annotations are added as classes to the nodes. If a value is found in an alt attribute, the annotation is added with an "@alt" suffix to the image node's class list.

In total, the first 220,000 English and 25,000 German pages are retrieved. The dataset is not balanced because going through all pages and quads is computationally expensive and German pages occur at a rate of around $1 : 9 = 10\%$. The 80/10/10 splits are created by using a multi-label stratified k-folds cross-validation split to ensure that each fold contains

⁸<https://schema.org>

⁹<https://github.com/commoncrawl/cc-index-server>

Figure 5.2: ITT label distribution for splits.

around the same ratio of labels. Figure 5.2 shows the split results with evenly distributed labels. Appendix C additionally provides the complete label counts over all splits together with their page counts. Due to the great variety of labels and data, the encoder can really learn the meaning for many different labels and how they interact with each other, enabling more rich embeddings. This should help the model in the final project classification task.

Like for the pretraining dataset, all pages from the same domain still land in the same split. It is not important to remove duplicate URLs from the pretraining set or ensure that they are in the same split as before because the main task in this stage is new and different, and those splits serve to evaluate the generalization ability of the model. It will even help the model because it can now see new data.

5.2.3 Finetuning Dataset

Finally, the finetuning dataset is collected from selected partner websites of the *Thünen-Institut*. All pages are in German. Because the project pages under one domain always are quite similar, a selector-based approach is chosen to label them. For each domain, the web pages are analyzed, and for each path¹⁰ that contains projects, a list of label-selector pairs is created. Thus, most domains have three lists of those pairs, namely for the main page, the projects overview page, and for the project pages themselves. The selectors are *jQuery*¹¹ selectors to efficiently select the right nodes.

¹⁰The path is part of the URL after the domain.

¹¹<https://jquery.com>

Table 5.2: Finetuning dataset pages and label counts per domain.

Subject	coworkland.de	d-s-e-e.de	iba-thueringen.de	imwandel.net	land-und-leute.org	machen-wettbewerb.de	miteinanderreden.net	mobiliikon.de	neulandgewinner.de	zukunftsorte.land	Total
pages	373	2,614	156	276	29	425	414	657	179	140	5,263
project pages	142	1,373	34	181	27	415	393	181	169	85	3,000
project	282	2,658	65	248	105	826	788	889	346	1,183	7,390
.address	0	1,204	34	179	36	826	0	0	166	1,270	3,715
..city	280	0	0	0	0	0	781	0	0	0	1,061
..state	122	1,409	0	0	0	413	390	220	0	0	2,554
.description	790	4,405	33	179	18	413	391	8,916	334	418	15,897
.email	140	1,301	51	175	0	0	430	0	0	83	2,180
.image	1,289	973	403	531	138	610	432	878	833	2,067	8,154
..copyright	0	0	347	139	0	0	29	877	0	0	1,392
.link	274	4,765	217	570	97	994	1,200	1,445	484	2,792	12,835
.phone	140	1,163	0	141	0	0	0	0	0	61	1,505
.subtitle	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	167	82	282
.title	282	2,659	97	247	105	826	788	889	346	1,182	7,421
split	test	train	test	test	test	test	train	train	train	train	

The crawler then crawls through the labeled domains and collects the HTML of the web pages. They are labeled and cleaned on the fly. The labels for a node are saved into a special field attribute because the `class` attribute is removed during cleaning. It is later renamed to `class`.

Although there already is some project data in the current database, it could not be used for extraction. On the one hand, it does not contain URLs to the original web pages, and on the other hand, the data was edited and completed with information that is not present on the web page. This makes it very hard to match the data.

After gathering all web pages of the labeled domains, they are preprocessed and added to the finetuning dataset. In total, 10 domains are labeled, resulting in 5,263 pages, of which 3,000 contain projects. The splits are created as for the ITT dataset. But this time a 76/24 train/test split is created because the set is small, and no validation is done during training. Furthermore, it is unbalanced in terms of pages and labels per domain and thus, hard to find three proportionally sized splits for each class. Table 5.2 contains the distribution of page and label counts over all domains. Unfortunately, some fields are quite sparse on some websites or could not be labeled in detail and thus, have just a few labels. Labels that were only available in one domain have been excluded because they cannot be learned and tested simultaneously. Figure 5.3 further shows the label distribution for the train and test split.

In addition to the class labels, category labels are added to the project nodes by matching their title with the title of projects from the database or extracted by *OpenAI*

Figure 5.3: Label distribution for train and test split of the finetuning dataset.

Table 5.3: Finetuning dataset category label counts.

Metric	Category Assignments			Projects	
	Train	Test	Total	Categories	Main Categories
mean	233.2	23.4	256.5	4.8	2.2
min	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
median	67.5	6.0	81.0	3.0	3.0
max	2,778.0	334.0	3,010.0	45.0	15.0
no assignments	27	38	24	2,250	1,429

(see chapter 8) and using the attached categories. This is done because categories have to be labeled manually as it is a retrieval task instead of an extraction task. And either the projects are already in the database and these categories can be used, or the LLM creates them, which works quite well most of the time (8.2.5). The retrieved categories are labeled with the prefix "cat:" plus the category ID and added to the node's class list. For each project, there are up to three main categories, which are marked with an additional ":main" suffix.

Table 5.3 shows the labeled category counts per split and in total as well as categories and main categories assigned to projects. Over all categories, 24 are never assigned. Since the test split is smaller than the train split, lower category counts are expected. That's why the unused category counts in the splits are higher than in total as some rarely assigned categories land in the other split and thus, count as 0. There are some dominating categories. Only 4 of 202 categories are assigned more than 2,000 times in total, while there are 14 that are assigned more than 1,000 times.

On average, projects have around 5 categories and 2 main categories assigned. But there are also a lot of projects that have no categories. The number of projects without

Table 5.4: Dataset sizes summary.

Dataset	Source	Language	Items
Pretraining	Fineweb	English	199,389
	Fineweb2	German	199,062
	Wikimedia Dumps	English	75,000
		German	69,283
Total			542,734
Intermediate Task Training	WebDataCommons	English	220,477
		German	25,000
	Total		
Finetuning	Partner Websites	German	5,263

categories is expected to be higher than the number of projects without main categories because the latter is assigned before the former. 50 % of all projects have 3 categories as well as 3 main categories assigned. At maximum there are 45 categories and 15 main categories attached to one project.

5.2.4 Summary

Now that all datasets are described and collected, table 5.4 shows a summary of their data sources, languages, and sizes. Some pages could not be preprocessed properly because either the HTML was not parsable or the page was empty.

5.3 Analysis

This section provides some insights into the datasets created and lays out the basis for some training and configuration decisions. Table 5.5 gives an overview of the three datasets with their pages, domains, token counts, percentiles, and other DOM tree-specific characteristics.

Notably, most web pages come from different domains. Only a small fraction of domains provides multiple pages. When it comes to token counts, it is important not to use the total number of tokens but to take into account the model limits and calculate the usable number of tokens. This is essential to calculate the token amount for the training. During pretraining and ITT, around 75 % of the total vocabulary is used. For finetuning, that is only 16 % because it only contains German webpages with from a single vertical while the other stages focus on two languages and domain diversity.

The table further shows that choosing 1,024 DOM tokens and 2,048 TI tokens as a limit is a good choice since most, i.e., over 92 % and 78 %, of the pages fit in completely. In general, most DOM trees aren't too deep, with almost all of them having a depth of up to 32. The amount of siblings and TI tokens per leaf is interesting because of the radius used

Table 5.5: Overall dataset statistics.

Subject	Pretraining	ITT	Finetuning
train pages	488,599	196,628	4,004
validation pages	26,958	24,667	-
test pages	27,177	24,181	1,259
domains	278,831	180,939	10
mean pages/domain	2.1	1.4	526.3
pages/domain (99 %)	9.0	6.0	2,437.9
max pages/domain	144,318.0 ¹	533.0	2,614.0
total DOM tokens	203,549,022	111,460,112	973,375
usable DOM tokens ²	178,832,917	96,517,482	950,807
total text tokens	793,832,116	323,839,461	4,481,384
usable text tokens ²	618,556,741	251,807,265	3,645,582
different text tokens	97,015	90,607	20,377
total image tokens	19,024,720	10,525,343	401,704
usable image tokens ²	17,915,323	10,056,250	389,922
mean DOM tokens/page	375.0	454.1	185.0
percentile for 1,024 DOM tokens/page	94.82 %	92.30 %	98.86 %
mean TI tokens/page	1,497.7	1,362.1	927.8
percentile for 2,048 TI tokens/page	78.54 %	81.52 %	88.77 %
mean element depth	11.2	12.3	10.7
percentile for depth of 32	99.92 %	99.96 %	100.00 %
mean siblings	28.9	26.3	8.3
percentile for 128 siblings	97.91 %	98.17 %	99.75 %
max siblings	7,688.0	7,609.0	488.0
mean TI tokens/leaf	126.1	111.7	121.1
percentile for 128 TI tokens/leaf	66.49 %	78.02 %	69.95 %
max TI tokens/leaf	4,748	6,206	1,774.0
DtD connection/DOM node	6.3	5.97	5.0
LA edges/text token	51.5	42.5	60.0

¹ Wikipedia pages.² "Usable" refers to the actual number of tokens seen by the model when limiting X^D and X^{TI} to a length of 1,024 and 2,048 tokens, respectively.

in DtD and LA. In around two-thirds of all leaves, all leaf tokens can use full self-attention. Leafs with more tokens start to omit tokens at the edges while tokens in the middle of the leaf still see all tokens up to a leaf size of 256. For the DtD mechanism, the number of siblings is important. Almost all nodes have only up to 128 children where attention to all siblings would be possible. But for both DtD and LA, the maximum counts are very high and would let the attention matrices explode. That's why the radii are needed. When looking at the number of edges per token, it is visible that MUSTIE scales very well, with around 6 edges per DOM token and 50 edges per TI token. As explained earlier, attention scales linearly for both mechanisms. With these factors, the matrices are around $6|X^D| \times 2$

and $50|X^{TI}| \times 2$ in size.

To sum up, the datasets contain pages with similar token counts, complexity, and attention connections, which is good for consistency over the different training stages. The finetuning dataset tends to have smaller and simpler DOM trees than the other two sets, which is visible via the mean DOM and TI tokens per page as well as the mean siblings per node. But that should not be problematic as the model already learned with trees of comparable sizes. It would be different if the finetuning set was much more complex than the training data, which is fortunately not the case.

Figure 5.4 shows the overall distribution of HTML tags over all datasets and splits. The red line is drawn at the HTML tag, signaling 1 element per page. Everything above is occurring more than once per page while everything below is only present less. It's clear that the `<a>` tag followed by ``, ``, and `<div>` is the most common one. Above the line are elements that are often used inside texts to structure content and to style websites. Below are elements that are used for the overall page structure like `<head>`, `<body>`, `<header>`, and `<footer>` as well as elements that are only needed in rare cases.

5.4 Recap

Before the data can be used by the model presented in the previous chapter, it has to be cleaned and preprocessed. To do that, all unnecessary tags and attributes are removed from the DOM tree before stripping whitespace, removing empty and duplicate nodes, and flattening `<div>` tags with only one child. During tokenization, the preprocessor creates lists containing the DOM and TI token IDs, the types of the tokens, and additional tree-specific information like node depths, parents, and sibling indices. Furthermore, it adds all edges for DtD and LA.

The data itself is distributed over three datasets for different training stages. The pretraining dataset contains a large amount of German and English web pages and is used for general encoder training. The ITT dataset contains more English than German data, which is caused by the available data distribution, and includes *Schema.org* annotation to train the encoder to recognize elements with those annotations. Finally, the finetuning dataset is made up of the pages from partners of the *Thünen-Institut*. These web pages are all German and a bit smaller and less complex than from the other two datasets. The data comes with selector-based labels to detect project-specific elements and additional categories and main categories to retrieve for each project.

Figure 5.4: HTML tag distribution over all datasets and splits.

Chapter 6

Experimental Setup

This chapter explains how the model and the different training stages are set up and evaluated. It provides information about the data collator and masking and further shows which losses and parameters are used to train the model.

6.1 Configuration

After analyzing the data, the model is configured with the parameters shown in table 6.1. They are oriented as BERT's base parameters (Devlin et al. 2018) and complemented by specific parameters for this implementation of MUSTIE.

6.2 Data Collator

The data collator creates a batch of data from items of the dataset and prepares it for the model. It takes a list of dataset items as input and transforms them to a dictionary of tensors, which is directly given to the model. Figure 6.1 shows the data flow from the dataset to the model. The data sampler decides the order of the dataset. This is shuffled during training and sequential during evaluation. The data loader fetches mini batches from the dataset and feeds them to the collator.

Figure 6.1: Data flow from dataset to model.

Table 6.1: Model Configuration.

Parameter	Value
max DOM input length	1,024
max TI input length	2,048
hidden size	768
intermediate size	3,072
hidden layers	12
attention heads	12
hidden activation	GELU
embedding dropout probability	0.0
attention dropout probability	0.1
hidden dropout probability	0.1
max. node depth	32
max. sibling index	128

As for tokenization, a custom data collator has to be implemented to fit the needs of the model and the data.

6.2.1 Batch Creation

To create a batch, the collator creates an empty dictionary and takes the following steps:

1. **Extract implicit information.** In this step, it adds the BU edges and node parent indices to each input item. For the BU edges, it takes the `ti_node_indices`, which denote the parent node index of a TI token, and creates the edges from the parent index to the node index. To create the parent indices, it filters the DtD edges for parent relationships and uses the destination + 1 as the parent. The `<html>` tag has the parent 0.
2. **Stack features and apply max. lengths and padding.** Next, the preprocessor creates one tensor for a feature over all input items. It does that for features that are set as stack features, visible in figure 6.2. Because all items can have different tensor lengths, the collator first detects the maximum length and then caps it at a configurable maximum. For example, DOM tokens have a maximum length of 1,024 (6.1) that cannot be exceeded. Afterward, all tensors of the same feature are padded with zeros to the maximum length.
3. **Clamp max. values.** Furthermore, the collator clamps some values to configurable maximums, like `node_depths` and `sibling_indices`. `ti_node_indices` are also clamped such that TI tokens that would have no parent get the last DOM token as parent. This can happen when a DOM token is removed from the input due to exceeding the maximum input length while the TI tokens didn't reach the limit yet.
4. **Filter and concatenate edges and create batch pointers.** If tokens don't make it in the final batch, their edges are also filtered before concatenating the list features

```

{
  "stack_features": [
    "dom_token_ids", "text_tokens", "img_tokens", "ti_token_ids",
    "ti_type_ids", "ti_node_indices", "labels", "categories",
    "main_categories", "node_depths", "sibling_indices", "parent_indices"
  ],
  "list_features": ["dd_edges", "dd_edge_types", "bu_edges", "la_edges"]
}

```

Figure 6.2: Data collator features.

to avoid out-of-bounds errors. For list features, a batch pointer is created, containing the start and end index of each input item’s edges.

The resulting batch contains all tensors needed by the model.

6.2.2 Self-Supervised Labeling

For self-supervised learning tasks, which will be discussed in the next section, the collator creates two kinds of labels: masking labels and relationship prediction labels.

Masking

Masking text tokens is the basis for MLM and is widely used. RoBERTa has shown better results when using dynamic masking instead of static masking (Liu et al. 2019). But instead of duplicating the data, the data collator does it before giving the data to the model. During masking, the collator selects a configurable ratio of the tokens and replaces 80 % of them with a special MASK token, 10 % with a random token from the vocabulary, and 10 % are left unchanged but used for the prediction task. Works like AST-T5 have shown better performance when using a higher masking ratio like 25 % than the default 15 % as used in BERT, but diminishing returns on way higher ratios, like 50 % (Gong, Elhoushi, and Cheung 2024). Another study also claims that higher masking ratios yield better results, depending on the model size (Wettig et al. 2023). According to this study, the optimal masking rate for base models is 20 %. With these two findings, the masking rate in this work is set to 25 % because this model is a bit larger than the usual *base* models (6.1).

Because masking tokens not only trains the model to use context to predict them but also works as a regularization technique because it introduces some noise to the input, a higher masking ratio is considered helpful regarding overfitting and generalization. Furthermore, longer context windows provide more absolute context with the same masking ratio, which is another good reason to increase masking.

Since HTML is hierarchical data, the collator masks whole subtrees. This has been shown to be beneficial on similar tasks (3.9.2). As there are two types of input tokens, both DOM and TI tokens have to be masked. But for TI tokens, only text tokens can be masked because the image tokens already are hidden states vectors and would require a different treatment. While masking text tokens is called MLM, masking DOM nodes is

Figure 6.3: Example for a masked web page.

called Masked DOM Modeling (MDM). The masking budgets for DOM and text tokens are calculated separately.

To apply masking, the collator shuffles all non-padded DOM tokens and iterates over them. Then, it masks every subtree, including its root, that still fits in the remaining masking budgets. Masking a subtree means masking all DOM tags and all text nodes of that subtree. If there is still masking budget left for text tokens, the collator takes the non-padded text tokens that are not masked yet, shuffles them, and applies the masking to all first tokens until the masking budget is exhausted. Figure 6.3 shows an example for a 25 % masked web page from figure 4.1. One subtree is masked completely, and the remaining text tokens are selected randomly. Note that all tokens in the image are only replaced with MASK for simplicity and no random or original tokens were used.

Table 6.2 shows average per-page masking statistics with a masking ratio of 25 % for the different datasets and their splits. The metrics are around the same for all datasets. Since the finetuning web pages are a bit smaller and less complex, fewer subtrees are masked with less DOM tokens. On average, a masked subtree has around 3 DOM nodes, 8.5 text tokens, and a depth of 1.8. The effective masking rate for DOM tokens is 24 % because subtrees that would exceed the budget are not masked and therefore lower the effective masking rate. The effective masking rate for text tokens is 25 % of which 20 % are masked within subtrees and 5 % are masked randomly outside of them.

Table 6.2: Mean per page masking metrics for a masking ratio of 25 %.

Dataset	Split	Tree Nodes	Tree Text Tokens	Tree Depth	Tree Count	DOM Token Fraction	Text Token Fraction	Text in Trees	Single Text Fraction
Pre	train	3.22	9.63	1.85	30.92	0.24	0.25	0.19	0.06
	val	3.12	9.23	1.85	31.48	0.24	0.25	0.19	0.06
	test	3.12	9.62	1.84	31.18	0.24	0.25	0.19	0.06
ITT	train	3.43	7.57	1.87	33.19	0.24	0.25	0.21	0.04
	val	3.28	7.53	1.88	32.99	0.24	0.25	0.21	0.04
	test	3.38	7.87	1.87	32.62	0.24	0.25	0.21	0.04
Fine	train	2.90	8.97	1.79	16.69	0.25	0.25	0.19	0.06
	test	2.66	7.79	1.69	15.26	0.24	0.25	0.19	0.06
Overall		3.14	8.53	1.83	28.04	0.24	0.25	0.20	0.05

Relationship Prediction

Relationship prediction uses pairs of DOM tokens and predicts the relationship between them. The relationships are the same as in 4.1 plus one "unrelated" class. Instead of using all DtD edges for prediction, which causes more computation overhead per item, the collator chooses 12 % of them as positive samples and adds 3 % unrelated edges as negative samples. Since there is only one edge for parent and self per token, sibling and children edges are more likely to occur in the batch. Because the data shows that there are around 6 connections per token, which includes parent and self connections, this is not considered a problem as they don't dramatically outnumber the other edge types.

Other Tasks

There are a lot of other tasks that could be used during self-supervised learning for MUSTIE. For structure-level objectives, there are prediction tasks for subtree sizes, node depths, sibling order or shuffled children. Next node prediction or cross-node coherence, which predicts whether two nodes are from the same semantical block, could further improve content-level signals. For more robust embeddings, graph contrastive loss could be used because it encourages the representations of the two same but slightly edited or augmented views of a subtree to be similar.

But since there is no scientific evidence if they help MUSTIE and the downstream task in this work, they are not further investigated and left open for future work due to time and resource constraints.

6.3 Training Phases

Now that the model input is there, the model can be trained. This section explains the different training stages, which come with their own characteristics. It starts with the

general and completely self-supervised pretraining. After that, the model gets an extra supervised task during the Intermediate Task Training. Finally, it is finetuned on the downstream task and main objective of this work.

6.3.1 Pretraining

Since pretraining is completely self-supervised, it only uses the labels created by the data collator. This phase is used to learn tag and position embeddings. It also teaches the model to contextualize the embeddings, which means that the encoder is trained to understand the web pages. But it should not only understand the semantics of web pages but also the structure of them.

Tasks

Thus, there are three tasks for pretraining: MLM, MDM, and NRP. All tasks use a cross-entropy loss on the masked tokens or chosen edges after a linear projection. For all tasks, log loss and accuracy are reported on the test set. In addition, a confusion matrix is provided for both MDM and NRP because there are only 5 or 128 classes and not thousands. This stage also provides a pseudo perplexity (Salazar et al. 2021) value for MLM and MDM by masking every token separately and taking e to the power of the average loss. This metric expresses from how many equally probable tokens, on average, the model chooses when predicting the masked token. While this is usually a metric for generative models, the pseudo perplexity was designed for masked language models. Equation 6.1 shows the final loss function used for pretraining.

$$\mathcal{L}_{Pre} = \lambda_{MLM}\mathcal{L}_{MLM} + \lambda_{MDM}\mathcal{L}_{MDM} + \lambda_{NRP}\mathcal{L}_{NRP} \quad (6.1)$$

Initialization

In the beginning of this stage, the model is initialized completely randomly, except for the word embeddings. These are copied from the BERT as mentioned in 4.2. When the proposed position embeddings (4.5.1) are used, the absolute TI positions are also copied from BERT’s position embeddings and repeated to fit the input size. This is done in Longformer because BERT’s attention heads tend to attend to local context, and that local structure is preserved except at the partition boundaries (Beltagy, Peters, and Cohan 2020).

All other parameters are initialized like in BERT with a normal distribution around zero and a standard deviation of 0.02, denoted as $\mathcal{N}(0, 0.02)$, for linear and embedding weights. Biases are set to zero, and LN scales are set to one. This weight initialization is small enough to avoid exploding activations and training instability but large enough to avoid vanishing gradients.

Table 6.3: Pretraining Model Parameters.

Module	Parameters			
	MUSTIE w/o tying	MUSTIE w/ tying	MUSTIE w/o pos.	BERT
model	325.0 M	234.3 M	229.5 M	178.6 M
embeddings	98.3 M	98.3 M	93.5 M	92.2 M
encoder	134.7 M	134.7 M	134.7 M	85.1 M
layer	11.2 M	11.2 M	11.2 M	7.1 M
head	92.0 M	93.2 M	93.2 M	92.5 M
MLM projection	91.9 M	91.9 M	91.9 M	91.9 M

Parameter Count

The parameter count of this MUSTIE implementation compared to the BERT model, which is also used for the word embeddings, is shown in table 6.3. Unfortunately, the pretraining stage was implemented using only a linear projection on the hidden states before calculating the loss.

In original transformer implementations, like BERT, there is a transform module before projecting the hidden states using the word embedding weights. This means that the weights of the final projection are tied to the word embeddings. This is visible in the table because BERT’s parameter count is the sum of the embeddings, the encoder, and a few head parameters, but not the MLM projection. For the first MUSTIE implementation without weight tying, the parameter count is way higher because the MLM projection has separate weights. In the second implementation of MUSTIE in table 6.3, the MLM projection weights are tied to the word embeddings. Because of that, the model has 91.9 M fewer parameters. The design decisions and advantages of weight tying are discussed in more detail in subsection 6.3.2.

The third implementation does not use the proposed position embedding from subsection 4.5.1, which the first two implementations use. This way, it is possible to see where the new parameters come from compared to the BERT model. The original embeddings layer introduces new tag embeddings and token type embeddings as well as relationship embeddings. These make up around 1.3 M parameters. But the module, which really adds parameters, is the encoder. MUSTIE defines an efficient multimodal encoder that scales well with increasing input size. But this comes at the cost of extra parameters for the 4 attention mechanisms. They all have their own key and query weights, which adds around 4.1 M parameters in a layer and thus 49.5 M parameters in the whole encoder as shown in table 6.3. The head also has a few more parameters because of the new transform module for DOM tokens. As the transform modules are missing in the first implementation without tying, the head is even a bit smaller when looking past the unnecessary projection parameters.

Table 6.4: Pretraining Arguments.

Argument	Value
learning rate	1e-4
warmup ratio	1 %
max steps	100,000
optimizer	AdamW
weight decay	0.01
Adam β_2	0.98
mini batch size	1
gradient accumulation steps	64
batch size	64
eval & save steps	2,000
fp16	true
λ_{MLM}	0.5
λ_{MDM}	1
λ_{NRP}	2.5

Training Arguments

Finally, table 6.4 shows the arguments used for pretraining. Since only one web page fits on the GPU at once, the mini batch size is set to 1. This also works only because of mixed precision training with fp16, which reduces the size of floats from activations and gradients to 16 bits. The batch size is set to 64, as in the original MUSTIE, using gradient accumulation. Since it is common in the pretraining of other LMs, AdamW with a weight decay of 1 % is used as the optimizer. RoBERTa further suggests an Adam β_2 value of 0.98 to adapt changing gradient scales faster. Since the model uses pre-LN, the warmup ratio can be as low as 1 % of the final 100,000 steps with linear decay and a peak learning rate of 1e-4. The 100,000 steps are calculated using Chinchilla’s law (Hoffmann et al. 2022) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{tokens} &= 325\text{M parameters} \cdot 20 = 6.5\text{B tokens} \\
 \text{items} &= 6.5\text{B tokens} \div (375.0 + 1,497.7) \frac{\text{tokens}}{\text{item}} \approx 3,470,924 \text{ items} \quad (6.2) \\
 \text{steps} &= 3,470,924 \text{ items} \div 64 \frac{\text{items}}{\text{batch}} \approx 54,233 \text{ steps}
 \end{aligned}$$

The tokens per item are the mean DOM and TI tokens per page from table 5.5. The resulting number is generously rounded up to 100,000 and nearly doubled since other languages models are trained for 500,000 to 2 M steps. The model is evaluated and saved every 2,000 steps for regular checkpoints and generalization performance monitoring. The λ values are chosen such that their losses are in the same order of magnitude in the beginning of the training, which is around 5.

To make use of the copied word embeddings, they are frozen for the first 20 % of the training, such that the encoder can settle before messing up the learned embeddings.

Figure 6.4: MLM head without transform module and weight tying (left) and with transform module and weight tying (right).

6.3.2 Continued Pretraining

Because some issues arose after the first pretraining run, the model’s pretraining was continued for two more epochs with corrections. This saves the time of a completely new pretraining and verifies whether the encoder, which already learned something, can adapt to the correct architecture quickly.

Tied Weights

Using weight tying in the head for MLM and MDM projections has several advantages. First and most importantly, it reduces the parameter count and thus memory consumption as well as disk space needed to save the weights. Second, it works like a regularization and helps generalization because the model has to predict its embedding distribution. To do that, a transform module is added before the projection layer using the embeddings’ weights. The transform module consists of a linear layer followed by a GELU activation and an LN. This helps the model to turn the contextualized embeddings, which might not live in the same embedding space as the original embeddings, back to the original embedding space. It acts as a bridge between the encoder’s latent space and the word embeddings. Otherwise, it can be hard to predict the exact embedding distribution. Figure 6.4 visualizes the difference between the two implementations with and without weight tying and transform module in the MLM head.

Figure 6.5: Example visualization for different embedding spaces.

Figure 6.5 visualizes word vectors denoting word embeddings. One model could learn word embeddings like shown with the blue arrows while another could learn the yellow representations. The angles between the vectors are the same in the graphic, thus, the words have the same relationships to each other. But it is in a high-dimensional space and different models can learn different latent aspects to represent its tokens. This, if one

would try to match them linearly, the model can have a hard time to match those different aspects. While just rotating the vectors, like in the image, would be easy, understanding the relationships between different dimensions requires non-linear transformations. That's why the transform module helps.

Switched Dimensions

Another error which occurred was the accidental switch of the head and the sequence dimensions after the TD attention. This means that the attention mechanisms essentially returned nonsense and was not helpful for the model. That's why the dimensions were switched in a second continued pretraining run.

Training Setup

Because the encoder already learned something during the pretraining stage, it is possible to just add the transform module or switch dimensions and train it for a few more steps. The transform module's parameters are initialized as the other parameters were before pretraining. The training is done with 16,000 steps, which are around two epochs. For the transform module run, all other model parameters are frozen for 10 % of the training budget and then unfrozen for the remaining 90 % of the training. For the corrected TD attention, nothing is frozen, but the warmup is set to 10 %. The results are reported together with the pretraining results.

6.3.3 Intermediate Task Training

The Intermediate Task Training (ITT) is used to guide the model into a better understanding of *Things*. When it comes to Search Engine Optimization (SEO), *Schema.org* annotations are often used to give structured information for the unstructured web data. A *Thing* is the "most generic type of item."¹ Since the WDC dataset provides web pages enriched with *Schema.org* annotations, they are used to train the model to recognize elements with those annotations. There are many classes of which 274 are used for training because they have enough labels to occur in every fifth batch on average. Classes containing "ispartof", "position", and "sameas" are excluded because they do not contain visible content and cannot be extracted as their own entities.

Tasks

The tasks are the same as for pretraining plus a classification task for *Schema.org* annotations on DOM nodes. Since a node can have multiple labels, it is a multi-label classification. Since the annotations are hierarchical, like event and event.name for example, a hierarchical loss as proposed in the MCL (equations 3.9 and 3.10) is used. As the labels are very sparse and only a few nodes of all contain labels, the default BCE loss would converge to predict only zeros or lead to gradient overflow when weighting the

¹<https://schema.org/Thing>

positives accordingly. That’s why the ASL loss (equation 6.5) is used and combined with the hierarchical mechanism. Equation 6.3 shows the resulting loss function for the MLC task with c denoting a class and \mathcal{C} the set of all classes.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{L}_{MLC} &= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}|} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \mathcal{L}_{MLC}^c \\ \mathcal{L}_{MLC}^c &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^N -[y_n \mathcal{L}_+^c + (1 - y_n) \mathcal{L}_-^c] \quad (6.3) \\ \begin{cases} \mathcal{L}_+^c = (1 - p_+^c)^{\gamma_+} \log(p_+^c) \\ \mathcal{L}_-^c = (p_-^c)^{\gamma_-} \log(1 - \min(1, p_-^c + clip)) \end{cases} & \begin{cases} p_+^c = \max_{i \in \mathcal{H}_c} (x_i y_i) \\ p_-^c = 1 - MCM_c \end{cases}\end{aligned}$$

The MCL introduces other calculations for the probability of a class p_+ and p_- , while ASL adds asymmetric scaling factors $(1 - p)^{\gamma_+}$ and p^{γ_-} . These two proposals can be jointly combined to the used MLC loss.

The hierarchy is calculated beforehand such that each class c has a hierarchy containing itself as well as all descendants. For example, the hierarchy of `event` contains `event` and `event.name` while the hierarchy of `event.name` only contains `event.name`. The hierarchy is created as a matrix of size $|\mathcal{C}| \times |\mathcal{C}|$. This way, the loss calculation becomes parallelizable on a GPU.

For the MCL task, metrics like loss, precision, recall, and F1 score are reported on the test set. This includes macro and micro metrics to get an overview of the performance of all classes. Micro metrics measure the performance of all items while macro metrics take the mean over all classes. A huge mismatch between the two is a good indicator for highly unbalanced classes and class performances.

Since it is unknown whether the authors of the *Schema.org* annotations labeled all information on their specific websites, the labels can also be seen as PU labels. That’s why the recall is more important than the precision. It is better to catch all positives and have some unnecessary negatives because of the HITL approach, which can remove the false positives. It is more difficult to add undetected false negatives for a human. When dealing with PU labels, the one experiment implements the PU loss from equation 3.6, adds the hierarchical mechanism by using the same hierarchical logits as for ASL, and compares the results with the ones from using ASL.

The total loss for ITT can be calculated as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{ITT} = \mathcal{L}_{MLC} + \mathcal{L}_{Pre} \quad (6.4)$$

Table 6.5: ITT Arguments.

Argument	Value
max steps	10,000
epochs	≈ 3.2
warmup	10 %
learning rate	$5e-5$
eval & save steps	1,000

Initialization

The model is initialized using the best pretraining checkpoint. The new classification head is initialized with $\mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$. 0.01 is chosen to keep gradients smaller as otherwise, gradient overflow was observed when using fp16. It works with bf16 because it provides the same amount of bits for the exponent as in full precision training, but it is just half as fast as training with fp16 and is therefore avoided.

Training Arguments

The training arguments are the same as in the pretraining from table 6.4, except for the ones defined in table 6.5. The learning rate is set to $5e-5$, which is half the pretraining learning rate to avoid over-adjustment. The amount of steps is set to 3 epochs and rounded up to 10,000 steps, which results in around 3.2 epochs. This time, the warmup ratio is 10 % because the encoder should not forget what it already learned due to misleading early gradients from the randomly initialized classification head, and this is a commonly used warmup ratio. Evaluation and checkpoint saving is done every 1,000 steps.

6.3.4 Finetuning

The finetuning stage trains the model on the final downstream task of this work. Two experiments are conducted: predicting the labels like in the previous stage and predicting if a page contains one or more projects using its root node’s representation. Since a node represents its entire subtree, the root node or `<html>` tag should represent the whole web page (Q. Wang, J. Wang, et al. 2023). Furthermore, categories have to be retrieved for project nodes.

To retrieve categories, category embeddings are needed. They are created using a category’s title, group title, and description. Since the categories can be seen as documents and documents can be efficiently represented using sentence embeddings (Sannigrahi, Genabith, and Espana-Bonet 2023), the three fields are embedded separately and then combined using a weighted sum. This approach followed state-of-the-art retrieval techniques with multiple fields (M. Li et al. 2024) and provides solid category embeddings. The weights are not learned for simplicity but set to 1.0 for the title, 0.8 for the description, and 0.5 for the group title. As embedding model, `intfloat/multilingual-e5-base` is

used as it scores at a high rank of 35 on the MTEB leaderboard (Enevoldsen et al. 2025) and has a dimensionality of 768, which fits our model.

Tasks

For the first experiment, the model is trained and evaluated as in the previous stage. The only difference is the number of classes. Furthermore, the influence of pretraining objectives on the finetuning task is evaluated by removing them. For the page classification task, the BCE loss (equation 3.3) is used. For both tasks, the results on the test set are reported as for earlier classification tasks.

Since there is also the need to tag projects with categories, a category retrieval head is added to the label prediction experiments. It uses a transform module followed by a linear projection layer to calculate the cosine similarity between given category embeddings and the contextualized embedding of project nodes. The category embeddings are not learned or transformed to be able to change categories at inference time without the need of retraining.

The logits for this loss are then retrieved by dividing the similarity by a learnable temperature τ . This helps because with a small temperature, like 0.05, the similarity is rescaled from $[-1, 1]$ to $[-20, 20]$. On this range, the sigmoid function provides a range of near $(0,1)$. Furthermore, this method is superior to just rescaling the cosine similarity using $\frac{cos+1}{2}$ because sigmoid provides a smooth gradient scale with emphasis for uncertainty while rescaling results in constant gradients. The calculation of logits is shown in figure 6.6. With the logits, the loss can be calculated using a modified ASL as the category retrieval is a MLC task. The ASL is modified to give weight main categories more than normal ones and is denoted as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{WASL} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^N -[y_n w_n \mathcal{L}_+ + (1 - y_n) \mathcal{L}_-] \quad (6.5)$$

Where w_n is a weighting term that is 1 for categories and 2 for main categories. To calculate the metrics, the model chooses the 3 highest scoring categories as main categories as per definition, only up to three main categories are possible.

Training Arguments

The initialization and training arguments are analogous to the ITT stage. Table 6.6 shows the used training arguments. The only changes are the number of epochs and steps as well as the warmup ratio and learning rate. The learning rate is taken from the original MUSTIE paper and set to $2e-5$. τ is initialized with 0.05 as it provides a good starting range for the logits.

Figure 6.6: Category head.

Table 6.6: FT Arguments.

Argument	Value
epochs	7
max steps	805
learning rate	2e-5
warmup ratio	1 epoch
initial τ	0.05

6.4 Continuous Fine-Tuning

In addition to the finetuning runs, a CFT approach is conducted. It emulates domain-wise incoming data and how it can be used to improve the model’s performance. For this, a CMR approach is tested, which means that finetuning runs with data from new domains and a small replay buffer are conducted. The buffer is set to 15 % of the known labels and capped at amount of the new label amount. The effectiveness of AL as proposed by Vidra et al. 2024 is shown by emulating incoming labels only from the top 14 high-entropy examples from new domains. 14 item items are chosen because this is 2 items per GPU. Therefore, a batch size of 14 is used, which makes up to two batches per epoch with the replay buffer. All other training arguments are like in the finetuning stage. The same metrics are reported and complemented by entropy values.

6.5 Multi-GPU Training

Training an LM with over 200 M parameters for 100,000 steps requires a large amount of time. Therefore, multi-GPU training is used to speed up the training process. But there are some things to be aware of when using this implementation of MUSTIE. The *Hugging Face* Trainer collects input labels and output logits for evaluation and syncs them to the main process. But when using dynamic sequence lengths or numbers of edges, the collected tensors cannot be concatenated, and the process fails. This is because the tensors have different sizes. To mitigate this issue, the data collator adds a shadow label tensor of length 1, which the trainer collects. All metrics are directly calculated inside the heads. Because the metrics are always just a single number, there is no problem with multi-GPU training. In addition, the model returns a shadow logit tensor of length 1. This behavior can be configured and changed at inference time when the real logits are needed in the output. Without the shadow label and logit tensor, the Trainer would not call the evaluation function, which is necessary to calculate the mean of evaluation metrics and save the training checkpoint.

Multi-GPU is implemented using Distributed Data Parallel (DDP) instead of Data Parallel (DP) because it scales better over multiple GPUs and provides better performance. Each GPU has its own process instead of input and outputs being scattered and gathered, which makes the whole processing faster and easier to monitor. Figure 6.7 visualizes the

difference between both. Gray boxes denote processes. The following command is used to start multi-GPU training with a custom script on 7 GPUs stated inside the environment variable `CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES`:

```
torchrun --standalone --nproc_per_node=7 ./src/web_extraction/training/script.py
```


Figure 6.7: Comparison of DP (left) and DDP (right).

6.6 Recap

This implementation of MUSTIE follows the size of other *base* transformers with 12 layers, 12 heads, and a hidden size of 768. To train the model, the data collator creates batches from the dataset items by stacking tokens and padding or truncating them to a common sequence length or concatenating the edges and creating edge pointers. It further applies dynamic subtree masking on 25 % of the DOM and TI tokens and samples positive and negative edge examples for NRP.

The training is split into three phases: pretraining, Intermediate Task Training (ITT), and finetuning. Because the MLM weights were not tied during pretraining, another

experiment is conducted to see whether the results can be preserved when changing the architecture to use weight tying.

During pretraining, the model learns a general understanding of web pages, while the ITT stage teaches it the meaning of *Things*, which are *Schema.org* annotations. The finetuning stage trains on the final downstream task with project-label classification, category retrieval, and project page detection. Furthermore, a CFT approach is conducted, which emulates domain-wise incoming data to continuously finetune the model.

Chapter 7

Results

This chapter presents the results of this work. It contains metrics and analyses of all training stages and further provides insights into the model using case studies. For better understanding of the model, gradient- as well as attention-based methods are used to analyze it.

7.1 Pretraining

The pretraining stage was the longest and most complex stage. Different architectures were tested. The final results are shown in the next section while further experimental findings are reported afterward.

7.1.1 Final Metrics

Table 7.1 shows the final test results of the pretrained model. The final pretrained model after continued pretraining runs with tied weights and corrected TD attention shows strong performance in the MDM task with an accuracy of 95.4 %. This is impressive since on average, there are 3 DOM tokens masked together in a subtree. This means that the model is able to sophisticatedly recreate the DOM tree, which is also visible in the low pseudo

Table 7.1: Pretraining Results.

Task	Metric	Value
MDM	loss	0.150
	pseudo perplexity	1.129
	accuracy	0.954
MLM	loss	4.207
	pseudo perplexity	17.341
	accuracy	0.361
NRP	loss	0.746
	accuracy	0.714

Figure 7.1: Pretraining MDM confusion matrix.

perplexity score. The confusion matrix in figure 7.1 reflects this. The model almost always predicts the correct tag. Some rare tokens, in turn, show a confusion. On the one hand, it is understandable that a `<canvas>` can be confused with a `<figure>` to 100 % or a `<tfoot>` with a `<td>` to the thirds as these tags are very similar. It is also not too confusing that `<embed>` is often considered an `<iframe>` or that `<iframe>` is sometimes predicted as ``. On the other hand, very rare tags like `<progress>`, `<output>`, `<meter>`, `<item>`, `<tt>`, and `<menu>` are confused with completely different tags. This is probably those tokens are too rare to learn sophisticated embeddings for them. There are also a few tokens in the matrix that don't have any predictions, like `PAD` and `MASK`, which are never masked, or other tokens that were filtered out during preprocessing.

In contrast to MDM, there are more text tokens in a subtree than DOM token, namely 8.5 on average. This is reflected in the results too. The model shows a text token prediction accuracy of 36.1 % and a pseudo perplexity of 17.3. While this is already good and means that the model can predict over one third of the masked text correctly, even when whole leaves are masked, it also shows that this task is harder and more complex than the

Figure 7.2: Pretraining NRP confusion matrix.

MDM one. This is because more text tokens are masked next to each other and natural language is more diverse and has more tokens than HTML. Furthermore, the model would definitely benefit from longer pretraining as the training and validation losses both decrease consistently with more steps. The training progress becomes slower, but it doesn't plateau.

The NRP task is performing ambivalent. While the accuracy is around 71.4 %, this is mostly because there are more sibling connections than other connections, which are predicted near perfectly as shown in the confusion matrix in figure 7.2. The self connection type is never predicted correctly. Rather, it gets predicted as a sibling. This is not too surprising since the inputs of self- and sibling-connections are very similar. Siblings often share similar representations (7.5) and have the same position embeddings for depth and parent. Parent and child connections are predicted similar with a correct prediction rate of 51 %, a confusion with the sibling class of 15 %, and 32 % of the time being predicted as unrelated. The unrelated class is very confused too and 63 % of the times predicted as parent child or sibling. While these results look like there might be an error, the distribution of edge types over 1000 items reveals that every class is present. On average there are 24 self, parent, and child connections chosen per web page, while there are 178 sibling and 63 unrelated connections.

Thus, while the model already handles text and DOM tokens good to very good, these results show that the model is currently not sophisticatedly able to predict node relationships and suggest that there might be the need for a better head architecture. One possible solution could be to use the same idea as for MLM and MDM and predict the learned relationship embeddings from two tokens. This would require a transform module in the relationship head again, which transforms $2d$ -dimensional embeddings to d -dimensional embeddings, which are then projected through the learned relationship embeddings.

Figure 7.3: Pretraining runs.

7.1.2 Experimental Findings

Figure 7.3 shows the loss of the pretraining tasks for different configurations. With a simple masking strategy without subtree masking, the model overfitted every time and was not able to generalize. When masking subtrees, but only let the model predict its root, it was not able to learn well. Only with DOM-LM style subtree masking did the model learn well. This is probably because without it, it is too easy for a DOM tag to "look" what is under it to know what it is. Thus, it does not have to use outer context. This in turn allows the model to learn very specific patterns for both text and DOM tokens as subtree masking regularizes more. With it, the model has to use outer context to make an educated guess. And this also reflects in the training loss curves. When predicting only the root, the training signal is too low and again, too easy for the DOM nodes since they don't have to use long-range context to predict the root tag of a subtree.

Further experiments show that using pre-LN rather than post-LN helps the model, especially the MLM task. This is probably because of the improved gradient flow pre-LN offers. But adding the DOM-LM style position matrix as proposed in subsection 4.5.1 had even more impact. Of course, more parameters provide a higher data capacity and therefore adapt faster in the beginning. But figure 7.4 shows that the position matrix also stabilizes the training loss and causes less volatility. These two methods further improved the model's performance on the MLM task while simpler tasks like MDM and NRP were not really affected. This again shows that more complex tasks require better architectures while simpler tasks can be compensated with capacity.

One experiment was conducted to test AG. Using AG on local attention with one head per layer guided for the next and one for the previous token attention provides the exact

Figure 7.4: Pretraining runs losses.

same graph during first few thousand steps as the run using the position matrix. As it might not learn real meaning of text (Deshpande and Narasimhan 2020) it is not further pursued.

Figure 7.5 finally shows the three pretraining runs the model went through: 100,000 steps with the first architecture, and 16,000 steps with both the tied weights, and corrected TD attention improvements. It is visible that the continued pretraining with tied weight was successfully able to restore the model’s performance quickly. Furthermore, the correction of the TD attention did improve the model’s performance notably, especially for the MLM objective, which improved its log loss by around 0.7 or 14 % on the validation set. The performance of the MDM task improved by around 0.02 or 11 %. In contrast, the NRP task did not improve by much throughout all training runs. After the first 20,000 steps, its performance stagnated, highlighting an inferior head design.

Interestingly, the gradient norm increases steadily throughout the training after the first $\approx 8,000$ steps. This is probably because the gradients fight the weight decay the parameters are subject to. The learning rate shrinks which is why the optimizer needs larger gradients for the same update magnitude.

To conclude, these results already show a strong performance on the pretraining tasks and demonstrate that the model is able to generalize over unseen web pages and domains.

7.2 Intermediate Task Training

This section presents the results of the ITT stage. It is again divided into a subsection for the final results as well as a subsection for experimental findings.

Figure 7.5: Pretraining 100k.

7.2.1 Final Metrics

Table 7.2 shows the metrics on the test set of the final ITT training. The three pretraining metrics show similar results as in the pretraining stage. The MDM and NRP tasks performed a bit worse while the MLM task improved slightly.

The main objective of this stage, the classification task, shows interesting results. All scores, except for the macro precision, are intuitively a bit better without masking, although the loss is slightly higher. The micro values show that the model performs generally well on all classes with a micro F1 score of 76.5 %. On the other hand, the macro scores are quite low with a macro F1 of 35.5 %. This shows that there are dominating classes which score very good while there are many classes that underperform with fewer examples.

And this is the case. 29 out of 274 classes score a F1 over 95 %. That are 10.6 % of the classes, but they have around 19.3 % of the positive labels. 43 classes or 15.7 % score over 90 % but have 44.5 % of the positives. And 55 classes or 20.1 % score above the micro F1 score with 51 % of all positive labels. At the same time, 55 classes score a F1 score of 0. That are 20.1 % of the classes, but they have only 2.9 % of the positive labels. There are still a few underrepresented classes which perform okay. These classes are either labeled with high quality or their content follows very specific rules. For example, is this the case for the class `offer.gt.in` with only 612 labels over around 200,000 training pages. It has a F1 score of 83 % with a precision of 90.7 % and a recall of 76.5 %. All class results are reported in detail in appendix D.

Note that parents usually have higher recalls and F1 scores than their descendants. This is probably because they get their signals plus the ones from their descendants and thus learn better. Furthermore, due to the hierarchical loss, the model has to predict them in

Table 7.2: ITT Results.

Task	Metric	Value	
		w/ masking	w/o masking
MDM	loss	0.188	0
	perplexity	1.209	0
	accuracy	0.943	0
MLM	loss	4.097	0
	perplexity	62.727	0
	accuracy	0.375	0
NRP	loss	0.788	0.788
	accuracy	0.699	0.699
Classification	loss	0.071	0.072
	micro P	0.811	0.814
	micro R	0.723	0.727
	micro F1	0.762	0.765
	macro P	0.516	0.508
	macro R	0.324	0.328
	macro F1	0.353	0.355

order to predict their descendants, which further pushes them.

Interestingly, the precision of classes with low F1 scores is usually multiple times higher than the recall. This means that the negative ASL parameter could be chosen a bit higher.

All in all, the model creates astonishing results for the classification task regarding that it has to few labels and has to label every single DOM element over all web pages. Even a low precision of 10 % means that the model is *"only"* predicting 9 times more false positives than true positives, which is not too much having in mind that there are 24,000 test web pages with 96,517,482 usable DOM nodes (5.2.4). And a class, on average, only has a few hundreds to thousands labels. Thus, it is already filtering a great amount of tokens.

7.2.2 Experimental Findings

Figure 7.6 shows training and validation curves for different metrics and test runs. One test run was made after the tied weights correction and one after the TD attention correction. They were run with different ASL parameters, namely a negative weighting term of 1 and 2, respectively. Furthermore, the vPU loss was tested.

The vPU loss is not valuable in this setup as it cannot be used with a regularization term. Thus, the loss is very volatile and does not lead to good results. Rather, the model predicts 1 for everything.

The ASL parameter difference is clearly visible in the validation scores. While a higher negative weighting term lowers the micro precision and therefore the micro F1 score too,

Figure 7.6: ITT Runs.

Table 7.3: Finetuning runs comparison.

Run	loss	m-F1	M-F1	m-R	M-R
fr. ITT	0.139	0.679	0.259	0.795	0.281
w/o MLM	0.159	0.754	0.248	0.779	0.257
w/o MCL	0.155	0.592	0.232	0.797	0.275
fr. Pre	0.147	0.658	0.246	0.789	0.274
fr. Scratch	0.163	0.649	0.198	0.722	0.211
Categories					
fr. ITT		0.219	0.026	0.474	0.100
w/o MLM		0.207	0.029	0.499	0.115
w/o MCL		0.216	0.024	0.461	0.086
fr. Pre		0.145	0.055	0.581	0.221
fr. Scratch		0.121	0.027	0.582	0.166
Main Categories					
fr. ITT		0.149	0.004	0.189	0.016
w/o MLM		0.119	0.004	0.146	0.017
w/o MCL		0.141	0.005	0.174	0.016
fr. Pre		0.100	0.003	0.122	0.016
fr. Scratch		0.149	0.004	0.188	0.016

Bold indicates the best result over all fine-tuning runs in the column.

it boosts all the macro scores because rare positives get more weight compared to many negatives than with a lower weighting term. Therefore, classes with fewer labels get better scores. Overall, the model predicts more positives, which increases the recall and hurts the precision.

It is also visible that the model assigns high confidence values to its predictions. That's why the loss is so low as higher confidence leads to a lower loss. However, this also means that it is very confident about wrong predictions, which is a hint for overfitting or inconsistent labels over diverse domains. As an evaluation on the training data does not score better, it is the latter. It is possible that low scoring classes are labeled differently on different domains over the splits.

7.3 Finetuning

Table 7.3 shows a comparison of different finetuning runs using the checkpoint from the ITT or pretraining stage as starting point or training from scratch. Furthermore, two more runs were conducted, which use the ITT checkpoint and disable the pretraining objectives or hierarchical loss, respectively.

The results show that the model performs good on micro metrics, but worse on macro metrics. This again highlights unbalanced class performances, which is shown in table 7.4. Few fields with enough and good quality labels like project, title, image, and address

Table 7.4: Finetuning Class Results.

Class	P	R	F1
project	0.67	1.00	0.80
project (one per page)	0.63	1.00	0.77
project.title	0.55	0.70	0.62
project.subtitle	0.00	0.00	0.00
project.description	0.16	0.41	0.23
project.email	0.53	0.39	0.45
project.phone	0.80	0.40	0.53
project.link	0.34	0.32	0.33
project.image	0.95	0.86	0.90
project.image.copyright	0.29	0.12	0.16
project.address	0.82	1.00	0.90
project.address.street	0.00	0.00	0.00
project.address.zip	0.00	0.00	0.00
project.address.city	0.00	0.00	0.00
project.address.region	0.00	0.00	0.00
project.address.state	0.00	0.00	0.00

score well while the other fields are underperforming. This highlights the advantage of this architecture, but also shows that better labels are needed.

Furthermore, table 7.3 shows that training the model from the ITT checkpoint is superior to training it from the training checkpoint or from scratch. It achieves the lowest loss when pretraining tasks and the hierarchical MCL are used. This is because the ITT introduces even more context and understanding of real things to the model. Without the ASL, the model learns nothing and only predicts zeros because of too many negative samples. This shows the advantage of using ASL in this setup.

When looking at the categories, it is clear that more training is needed to learn a good transformation from the project embeddings to match them to the category embeddings. The scores are all very low, which is even worse for the macro scores because there are many categories, which are rarely used while a few are assigned more often.

Regarding page classification, using the representation of the `<html>` tag didn't lead to good results. Despite the model learned to predict project pages on the training set with a F1 score of 99.8 %, the performance on the test set is only around 55.6 %. This is worse than predicting a 1 for every web page as there are 95.8 % project pages in the test dataset. This means that either the model is overfitting or the representation of web pages in the test dataset is very different. As the test scores are already low after one epoch and rise to the 7th epoch, it is probably not overfitting but a mismatching page representation.

The last thing to note is that the previously initialized τ value was changed from 0.05 to 0.0432 during finetuning. This means that the model sharpens the logits distribution in order to predict more confident probabilities.

Table 7.5: Page classification results.

Epochs	P	R	F1
1	0.495	0.480	0.477
7	0.556	0.503	0.519

7.4 Continuous Model Refinement with Active Learning

After looking at the finetuning results, this section now presents a more efficient framework for a setting where labels come in with time to achieve nearly the same results.

Although the CMR setup uses very few samples, it provides astonishing results, which are presented in figure 7.7. The three runs, `domain_pre`, `domain_test`, and `all_test`, denote the evaluation on the new domain before training, after training, and the evaluation after training on all unseen data, respectively. The model quickly learns to adapt to new domains and reaches a score equal to the finetuning stage. The figure shows that the model uses has 133 labeled items at the end and uses a maximum of 28 items per round. With 7 epochs, these are only up to 14 steps per round or 133 steps in total. This finding proves the effectiveness of MUSTIE in a low-resource scenario that the authors of it promised and shows that the encoder is an effective few-shot learner. It is just important to have a few examples per class per domain to effectively train the model.

The figure further shows that the model successfully generalizes over unseen domains as the gap between the pre-training domain evaluation and post-training domain evaluation shrinks and the pre-training domain the overall test results improve with each round. Note that the domain-specific loss goes a bit up in the last few rounds as the labels' count and distribution as well as the web page complexity can differ to previous domains. The F1 scores show that those domains are improving too.

7.5 Model Analysis

This section takes a closer look at the insights of the model and tries to explain how it works for the purpose of explainability and interpretability.

7.5.1 Similarities to BERT's Word Embeddings

With more and more steps, the model's word embeddings become a bit more different to their starting point, BERT's word embeddings. After the first 100,000 steps, the row-wise cosine similarity was 0.921 while the final row-wise similarities are 0.830 after the last pretraining and 0.815 after the last ITT. While this is not alarming and the word embeddings are still very similar, it is interesting to see that the model starts to learn its own word embeddings.

For the rest of the analysis the model from the last ITT is used because it provides the best downstream task performance.

Figure 7.7: CMR Results.

7.5.2 Similarities of HTML Tags

When comparing the learned HTML tag embeddings, there are some interesting similarities. Table 7.6 shows the 4 most similar HTML tag embeddings for some chosen examples by calculating the cosine similarities between the tag embeddings. The MASK token quite is similar to all other tokens, especially less occurring ones. This similarity is probably because this way the token does not confuse the context too much as it is similar to many other tokens. The headings are also very similar to each other with some interesting differences. While the `<h1>` tag is also similar to `<title>` and `<hgroup>`, the `<h2>` tag is similar to a paragraph, which often follows this tag. `<h3>`, in turn, has a higher similarity to the bold tag, indicating that many level 3 headings are bolded.

Table 7.6: 4 most similar HTML tag embeddings for some chosen examples.

MASK	1.000	<h1>	1.000	<h2>	1.000	<h3>	1.000
<html>	0.613	<h2>	0.255	<h3>	0.327	<h2>	0.327
<meta>	0.536	<title>	0.161	<h1>	0.255	<h4>	0.307
<command>	0.535	<hgroup>	0.119	<h4>	0.214		0.139
<wbr>	0.532	<h3>	0.109	<p>	0.152	<h6>	0.129
<video>	1.000	<picture>	1.000		1.000	<a>	1.000
<audio>	0.554	<figure>	0.206	<menu>	0.212	MASK	0.456
<map>	0.337	<video>	0.206		0.184	<div>	0.360
<object>	0.273	PAD	0.170	MASK	0.151	<p>	0.336
<datalist>	0.268		0.144	<rp>	0.119	<title>	0.315
<header>	1.000	<footer>	1.000	<main>	1.000	<article>	1.000
<hgroup>	0.203	<figcaption>	0.132	<article>	0.159	<main>	0.159
<footer>	0.127	<header>	0.127	<menu>	0.154	<figure>	0.132
<sub>	0.106	<aside>	0.117	<bdo>	0.150	<dl>	0.112
<summary>	0.101	<main>	0.113		0.147	<header>	0.100

But those similarities do not only occur in text-related tags, but also in other areas. Remarkably, tags from the same category, like structure, text, depictions, and so on, are also very similar. This is also true for tags like <video>, <audio>, <figure>, and <picture>. The same dynamic is visible for the <header> and <footer> tags, which also show similarities to suitable tags like <hgroup> or <figcaption>. Also in the content area, tags like <main> and <article> or <article> and <figure> group close together.

This shows that the model seems to learn similar embeddings for similar tags and indicates that it is really understanding the structure of an HTML document.

7.5.3 Reconstruction of Masked Tokens

In the next few points, a case study is performed using the test webpage from figure 4.1. With the same mask as in figure 6.3, the model predicts the masked DOM token with an accuracy of 100 % and the masked text tokens with an accuracy of 31.25 %.

Table 7.7 shows the reconstruction of the masked text tokens. You can see that the model predicts tokens fitting to the context when not choosing the correct one. Surprisingly, it predicts 4 times the token "Community" inside the masked subtree.

7.5.4 Gradient-Based Analysis

While the analysis of attention heads is not sufficient to explain a model and should only be used as an indicator (Serrano and Smith 2019; Jain and Wallace 2019), gradient-based methods offer a reliable way to analyze what is important to the model for a certain prediction.

Table 7.7: Reconstruction of masked text tokens.

Masked token	Predicted token
profit	profit
to	to
education	clean
,	,
Recent	Our
Volunteer	Volunteer
##s	##ing
building	in
a	Community
water	Community
well	Community
Clean	Community
Water	for
Wells	Logo
@	@

Figure 7.8: Token-level gradient analysis of the masked `` DOM token.

Token Contribution

This can be done on different levels. The first is the token level. To calculate the importance of a token for a given output, the prediction for that output is derived from the input tokens. In this case, since the inputs are token IDs, the score is derived by the embeddings from the embedding layer. In the following example, the correct output of the masked `` token is analyzed.

Figure 7.8 shows which input tokens are important to the model when predicting the correct `` tag. Not surprisingly, it is the other list item, its sibling, and the list root, its parent. On the TI token side, the masked text tokens inside the `<a>` tag are most important.

Figure 7.9 further provides a visualization of the importances for the "clean" prediction of the "education" token. For this prediction, the previous "clean" token is very important,

Figure 7.9: Token-level gradient analysis of the masked "education" text token.

probably because it could introduce a list beginning with "clean".

Layer Contribution

In addition, the layer contributions can be analyzed by multiplying the gradient of a layer's output by its activation, which is its output. This way, the following layers are important to predict the correct `` tag or the wrong "clean" token:

For the tag token:	For the text token:
1. 9.5 %	1. 11.4 %
2. 10.4 %	2. 11.1 %
3. 11.3 %	3. 10.4 %
4. 10.8 %	4. 10.5 %
5. 10.4 %	5. 10.4 %
6. 9.5 %	6. 8.8 %
7. 8.9 %	7. 7.0 %
8. 7.9 %	8. 6.7 %
9. 7.2 %	9. 6.4 %
10. 6.2 %	10. 6.3 %
11. 4.6 %	11. 5.7 %
12. 3.2 %	12. 5.3 %

Interestingly, the first 5 to 6 layers are most important. From layer 4 on, the contribution scores steadily diminish.

Figure 7.10: Head-level gradient analysis of the masked `` DOM token.

Figure 7.11: Head-level gradient analysis of the masked "education" text token.

Head and Attention Mechanism Contribution

It is further possible to analyze how much the different heads of different attention mechanisms contribute to the output by multiplying the gradient of the attention score matrix by the score matrix itself. Figure 7.10 shows how much the heads of each layer and each attention mechanism contribute to the tag prediction. It uses a global normalization of all head scores to visualize the most important ones overall. It becomes clear that the model only uses a bit BU attention in the first layer followed by two very important DtD heads in the second layer to perform the prediction.

Figure 7.11 in turn shows the head contributions for the "clean" prediction of the "education" token. Here, the 8th head of LA of layer 2 seems to be the most important. This image is normalized per layer per mech for better visualization.

7.5.5 Analyzing Attention Heads

Looking at the activations in figure 7.12 of the two most highlighted attention heads, one can see that the DOM token to predict looks at its parent in head 2 and at its sibling in head 11 of layer 1.

Figure 7.13 shows the attention scores for the 8th head of LA in layer 2. The scores are barely visible, but the masked "education" token pays much attention to "clean" here.

Figure 7.12: DtD attention heads 2 (left) and 11 (right) of layer 1.

Head 8

Figure 7.13: LA attention head 8 of layer 2.

All in all, these methods help to understand the model's behavior and further detailed analysis of gradient flows and attention activations could be made to explain it. One DtD head, for example, explicitly pays attention so semantic tag, which contain content. While this analysis can be expanded endlessly, it should be enough for this thesis at this point.

7.5.6 Resource Utilization

The model was tested also on a single core of a CPU to measure RAM and CPU utilization during inference and CFT. A Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 5218 CPU @ 2.30GHz was used for the tests on the finetuning test dataset. With a CPU utilization of 100 %, processing one item in inference mode took around 6.4 seconds. The RAM usage of the model together with everything it needs like classes, category embeddings, config, and data collator, is around 923 MB while the whole process allocates around 1,749 MB RAM. During inference, the peak was at around 5,300 MB. When used for training, doing one step with a batch size of 1 takes around 23 seconds and the RAM peaks at 18,000 MB. This is important to not when using the CMR approach on a low-resource system as it needs enough RAM and $14 * 23 = 322$ seconds to do 14 steps on a new domain. Note that all RAM measurements can vary depending on the size of a web page.

7.6 Recap

All in all, this chapter has shown that the developed model is able to learn website structure and mix it with semantic information and learning during pretraining. It generalizes well over unseen web pages and domains and its representations can be further improved using a prediction task on *Schema.org* annotations. Regarding the downstream task, the model shows very good results for fields that are sufficiently labeled but performs poorly on other fields. In contrast to this finding, the model learned pretty fast in a low resource scenario using a CMR approach with AL. Furthermore, section 7.5 gives some interesting insights into the model and shows how it comes to its predictions in a small case study.

Chapter 8

Use of OpenAI

Finally, the model results can be compared with the *OpenAI* variant. This chapter shows how the extraction is done using the *OpenAI* API and evaluates the extraction results. It further compares these results with the results of the MUSTIE-based model. Ultimately, it offers a cost analysis and a short guide on what should be considered when choosing this option for extraction.

8.1 Setup

To extract information from HTML using *OpenAI*, structured output is used. The setup follows the official documentation (*Structured Outputs - OpenAI API* n.d.). A JSON schema is created, which informs the API about the structure and fields of a project. For each field, the type is given as well as if it is nullable or not. The schema also provides some guidance via field descriptions. On each new crawl job, all possible categories to tag projects with are loaded from the database and added to the schema. The full schema is provided in appendix E.

To let the model select from the categories, they are added as enum values, represented by a unique string to be matched to their original afterward. Since the categories from the database come with a title, a group title, and a description, which are natural texts the model can understand, it would be plausible to use them to represent a category. Unfortunately, when adding the descriptions, the schema size exceeds the API limit, as there are a lot of categories. Thus, a category is only represented by its group title and title like this: `<group title> - <title>`.

To retrieve structured output, a request is sent to the chat completions API containing the model, a system, and a user prompt, as well as the JSON schema. GPT-4.1 is chosen as the model as it is the latest and most capable non-reasoning model at the time of this writing as well as cheaper than GPT-4o (*Introducing GPT-4.1 in the API | OpenAI 2025*). Reasoning models are excluded because they are slower, and the reasoning tokens make them more expensive than the non-reasoning models.

The system prompt tells the model what to do and how it should behave. The most generic and important information regarding the extraction task is included. It follows the

Role-Task-Format (RTF) framework (Istwal 2023). It is a commonly known framework in the field of prompt engineering, and several articles were written about it, like the one cited, but unfortunately there is no scientific publication about it. The prompt first tells the model its role, setting the context for the task. Then, the task is explained, which tells the AI what to do with the user's prompt. Finally, some formatting guidelines are provided to ensure the model delivers the desired output in a way that aligns with the needs of the task. The prompt used in this work is the following:

```
You are an expert at structured data extraction.
You will be given unstructured html from a website and should convert
it into the given structure.
Your targets are charitable projects from rural areas.
If you can't find an information, return an empty string or null.
Never use placeholders for empty information!
Only extract information that you are sure about.
```

The last missing piece of the request is the user prompt. It simply is the cleaned HTML of the web page from the crawler.

8.2 Results

With everything set up, the responses are evaluated on the finetuning dataset (5.2.3). The pages are only extracted once to save costs. Of course, publicly available LLMs are non-deterministic. Thus, the response can vary each time for the same request. Since there are a few thousand pages and labeled projects, this is considered not to be a problem to get reliable results for project extraction and sufficiently labeled fields with at least 100 labels. For specific single pages, however, these extraction results cannot be seen as a single source of truth.

For each response, the extracted project list is matched with the labeled project list by matching the projects' titles. Then, for each labeled field, the exact match precision, recall, and F1 score of the matches are calculated. For lists, like images, these scores are calculated over all list elements. Some descriptive texts are further evaluated using the normalized Levenshtein similarity to match the texts. Tables 8.1, 8.2, 8.3, and 8.4 show the results.

8.2.1 Labeling Approach Weakness

Remarkably, the recall is nearly always higher than the precision. This is because the model outputs more values than were labeled. This is not bad in all cases since some labels should be considered to be PU labels instead of PN ones. Therefore, the precision is no useful metric for those cases as it is unknown whether there are more positives and the labels cover everything. This is because of the node tagging approach to make labeling

Table 8.1: Field-wise results in % for the OpenAI model.

Field	P	R	F1	Label Count ¹
project	59.3	52.1	55.4	7,319
project (one per page) ²	58.9	99.4	74.0	2,929
project.title	96.9	96.9	96.9	3,810
project.subtitle	30.1	83.9	44.3	280
project.description	32.8	33.1	33.0	3,397
project.description (soft) ³	99.3	87.5	93.0	3,397
project.email	88.5	98.8	93.4	2,020
project.phone	96.6	99.2	97.9	1,445
project.links.title	77.4	82.4	79.8	6,742
project.links.url	80.2	84.3	82.2	6,835
project.images.url	64.2	72.5	68.1	5,219
project.images.copyright	35.9	55.3	43.5	832
project.address	8.5	8.0	8.2	4,141
project.address (soft) ³	34.7	33.1	33.9	4,141
project.address.street	7.9	90.0	14.5	140
project.address.zip	5.7	100.0	10.9	122
project.address.city	14.0	73.2	23.5	530
project.address.region	13.5	56.1	21.8	171
project.address.state	11.3	31.2	16.6	1,058
project.properties.tool	0.0	0.0	0.0	6
project.properties.tool (soft) ³	0.0	0.0	0.0	6
project.properties.vision	0.4	15.4	0.8	26
project.properties.vision (soft) ³	1.1	42.3	2.2	26
project.properties.activeEntity	0.7	81.2	1.5	16
project.properties.activeEntity (soft) ³	0.9	93.8	1.7	16
project.properties.strategy	0.0	0.0	0.0	8
project.properties.strategy (soft) ³	0.1	12.5	0.3	8

¹ Only counts for matched projects, except for project metrics themselves.

² Instead of comparing every project, only the first project per page is considered. This helps the recall because some detail pages contain references to other projects, which are mostly not extracted.

³ Soft means that the normalized Levenshtein score is used instead of exact matching. A similarity above or equal to 0.7 is considered correct.

feasible. The more correct approach would be to extract the specific text sequences from project pages. But this would result in massive labeling work. Due to this label design, the model can predict more or even more correct information than the simple selector-based extraction. Therefore, uncertain scores have been marked with gray.

8.2.2 Projects

But the labels are still useful to evaluate the recall of the results. For example, the model seems to extract only 52.1 % of the projects. But when comparing only the first project per page, the recall jumps up to 99.4 %. This is because some pages contain references to other

Table 8.2: Extracted vs. labeled projects on overview pages.

Overview Page URL	Extracted	Labeled
https://coworkland.de/de/spaces/	1	141
https://foerderdatenbank.d-s-e-e.de/	1	25
https://iba-thueringen.de/projekte/	5	32
https://miteinanderreden.net/projekte/	1	390
https://neulandgewinner.de/projektuebersicht/	3	167
https://wendland.imwandel.net/projekte/	58	58
https://wissen.zukunftsorte.land/orte/	10	82
https://www.machen-wettbewerb.de/wettbewerbssrunde-2023/	1	206
https://www.machen-wettbewerb.de/wettbewerbssrunde-2024/	1	207

projects, which the model is mostly missing. Otherwise, it nearly gets all projects right. But this also means that not all projects are extracted from overview pages as table 8.2 shows. Only the projects of one overview page got fully extracted. Because all the projects in this work have a separate detail page the crawler can retrieve, this is not a problem for now.

In the case of the project field, the labels are really PN ones since the project pages can be labeled effectively. Note that the precision is around 59 %, which is exactly the ratio of project pages to all web pages in the labeled dataset, namely around $2929 : 5045 = 58.1 \%$. The model tries to predict projects for nearly every single page, resulting in many false positives. The ratio of empty predictions is just $93 : 5045 = 1.84 \%$. This is probably because LLMs are trained to be helpful (Ouyang et al. 2022). Thus, they tend to hallucinate or extract uncertain information instead of giving an empty output. Furthermore, the model might not fully get the meaning of the word "project" in this context yet and may need further guidance. Interestingly, it is very capable of giving no output in the case of the project fields. Table 8.3 shows that there are many fields that are empty most of the time. Being empty means being equal to one of [None, "", " ", ".", ",", "/", {}, []].

8.2.3 Descriptive Fields

Regarding other fields, it is visible that non-descriptive fields yield way higher recall values than descriptive ones or fields with a variable representation, like address. This is because the model does not output an exact match every time. That's why there are also soft scores in table 8.1, which use a normalized Levenshtein score greater than or equal to 0.7 as a correct prediction instead of exact matching. The Levenshtein distance is the smallest number of single-character insertions, deletions, or substitutions that turn one string into the other and therefore a good similarity metric. To normalize it, the distance is divided by the length of the longer string and subtracted from 1 to get a metric between 0 and 1. The soft scores always achieve a higher recall than the exact matches. There are still mismatches, which are not real mismatches because either the labeled element contains a long text the model shortens, or it formulates it differently and thus does not produce a match.

This is especially the case for most of the properties. These fields are text fields, and

Table 8.3: Overview of extracted objects and empty fields.

Object Type	Extracted	Field	Empty (abs)	Empty (%)
pages	5045			
project	6,424	title	13	0.2
		subtitle	4,993	77.7
		description	656	10.2
		foundationyear	4,322	67.3
		visitOptions	6,173	96.1
		email	2,401	37.4
		phone	3,804	59.2
		links	337	5.2
		images	2,074	32.3
		address	1,207	18.8
		properties	2,594	40.4
categories	596	9.3		
project.links	13,007	title	1	0.0
		url	1	0.0
project.images	7,988	url	29	0.4
		copyright	5,898	73.8
project.address	5,217	street	2,340	44.9
		zip	1,805	34.6
		city	1,045	20.0
		region	4,260	81.7
		state	1,141	21.9
		country	958	18.4
project.properties	3,830	activeEntity	1,260	32.9
		partner	3,248	84.8
		financing	2,104	54.9
		vision	2,027	52.9
		strategy	2,525	65.9
		tool	3,265	85.2
project.categories	39,253	category	0	0.0
		isMainCategory	0	0.0

Red indicates that fields are empty despite they shouldn't be. **Green** indicates that fields are not empty, as they should be.

only a few pages report them separately. This is visible in the low label count. Thus, the model writes something itself or mixes it with information from other texts, which does not always match the labels. Remarkably, the field `project.properties.activeEntity` is scoring well, indicating that the model really extracts the right parts instead of writing something new.

In case of the address field, a string is created from its sub-fields if it is not already a string and then matched. Because of missing fields or display differences of extracted strings, the scores are quite low compared to the sub-fields' performances.

8.2.4 Non-Descriptive Fields

That is because it is easier to rate stricter fields like its sub-fields, `phone`, or `email`. The last two are predicted nearly perfectly because they follow known patterns and are thus easy to extract for LLMs. All in all, it is clear that non-descriptive fields score better because their output either follows given patterns or depends more on the exact input and cannot be rewritten, like for URLs or very short texts as titles. There is no field the LLM really struggles with.

8.2.5 Qualitative Results

Since the quantitative analysis is not always the best to evaluate generated outputs, a qualitative evaluation is important too. There is feedback from the editors for the first few extraction runs. They took a closer look at some projects and gave feedback for one example and an overall statement:

“When I look at the categories, the space resources ‘Individual rooms’ and ‘Buildings’ are often assigned. That would not be relevant here, for example, as it is primarily about a ship. Many categories are great, but then there is ‘Trial living,’ for example, even though that does not appear in the text at all. [...] Overall, I think the hit rate is really quite good. The properties/details are now also very well filled in.” (The Editors, translated to English.)

Since there are no labels for categories yet, the only feedback on them is the qualitative look of the editors. It became clear that most of the categories are assigned quite well. But there are some projects for which the categories are not matching the content. However, the other fields of a project are filled in properly. Although the model writes some new text, it is close enough for the editors to be considered correct. All in all, they are satisfied with the results.

8.2.6 Task Alignment

Furthermore, the problem of hallucinating and filling in too much, like for the project list itself, is not visible here. As table 8.3 shows, there are many empty fields and it seems like a reasonable fill-in rate. This is good because the model was told to only respond with

Table 8.4: Categories extraction result description.

	Count	Main Categories
mean	6.74	2.71
std	4.49	0.72
min	1	1
25.0 %	3	3
50.0 %	6	3
75.0 %	9	3
97.8 %	18	3
max	47	15

Red indicates that the number of main categories is above the requested limit of 3.

information it is certain about. However, there are still some misalignments with the task. For example, all optional fields are also nullable in the schema. While the model follows the schema nearly every time, there are fields that should not be empty but are empty sometimes. This is because there is no way to tell the model that a string should not be empty. Thus, the only way of avoiding empty fields is to write it in the field's description. And although the model is told not to use placeholders, it still provides them. 1.1 % of empty values are placeholders like "-", "/", or ".".

Interestingly, subtitles often have leading and/or trailing slashes. As well as the placeholders, those can be removed programmatically, but they shouldn't occur in the first place because the inputs don't provide them. The subtitle is the only field where this happens.

It followed the schema only *nearly* every time because in rare cases, inline base64 encoded images produced so many tokens that the output just stopped in the middle of the string. Those should be removed to increase accuracy and reduce tokens and thus, cost.

Finally, the model does a good job at matching the categories. As told, it picks a variable amount of categories from the list with 184 items and designates up to three of them as main categories. Table 8.4 shows that the model does it correctly for 97.8 % of the projects. The rest has more than the requested main categories. Interestingly, GPT-4.1-mini was not able to assign a variable amount of categories to a project while GPT-4.1 could understand the task.

8.3 Comparison

Table 8.5 compares the field-wise extraction results of the structured output method with the developed in-house model. For comparison, the whole metrics and not only the project matches are reported for the LLM. This way, it is easier to compare the final results of the in-house model experiments with the *OpenAI* extraction results.

It is clearly visible that the custom model is able to predict project more accurately than the LLM. While considering only whether a page contains projects or not helps the LLM

Table 8.5: Comparison of field-wise results in % over all labels.

Field	<i>OpenAI</i>			In-House		
	P	R	F1	P	R	F1
project	59.3	52.1	55.4	0.67	1.00	0.80
project (one per page)	58.9	99.4	74.0	0.63	1.00	0.77
title	57.6	50.5	53.8	0.55	0.70	0.62
subtitle	13.7	83.9	23.5	0.00	0.00	0.00
description (soft)	55.5	59.6	57.7	0.16	0.41	0.23
email	49.0	98.7	65.5	0.53	0.39	0.45
phone	53.5	99.1	69.5	0.80	0.40	0.53
links.title	42.5	50.7	46.3	0.34	0.32	0.33
links.url	44.1	46.0	45.0			
images.url	47.6	49.7	48.6	0.95	0.86	0.90
images.copyright	24.4	33.3	28.1	0.29	0.12	0.16
address (soft)	26.6	20.5	23.1	0.82	1.00	0.90
address.street	4.3	89.4	8.3	0.00	0.00	0.00
address.zip	3.6	99.2	6.9	0.00	0.00	0.00
address.city	9.3	36.6	14.8	0.00	0.00	0.00
address.region	9.2	56.1	15.7	0.00	0.00	0.00
address.state	8.1	16.3	10.8	0.00	0.00	0.00
properties.tool (soft)	0.0	0.0	0.0			
properties.vision (soft)	0.6	42.3	1.2			
properties.activeEntity (soft)	0.6	3.9	1.0			
properties.strategy (soft)	0.1	12.5	0.2			

performance and reveals how its extraction works, the in-house model does not benefit from this method. Furthermore, the developed model is better at predicting project titles, images, and addresses. This highlights the strengths of the model architecture and training data as it can compete with an LLM. On the other side, it performs worse at predicting all other fields. This is because the good performing fields have enough labels, which are of high quality, while the other fields suffer from a lack of labels or low quality.

Furthermore, the LLM is able to extract information from inside of texts while the labeling technique is not optimized for this task. It is superior on fields with low labels because the model did not have enough guidance and the LLM does not need that to perform good.

All in all, these results show that the investigated model is able to compete with the *OpenAI* baseline if there is enough high-quality training data. On the other hand, the LLM shines through in poor data quality scenarios and when information has to be extracted with a finer granularity. Furthermore, using structured output enables to switch the schema on the fly while a custom model has to learn new classes before being able to predict them. The same applies for categories. Chapter 7 has shown that the model was not able to match the category embeddings only during finetuning. With LLMs, this problem does not exist.

When it comes to cost, time, and efforts, the comparison depends on the specific use

case. For small setups, developing and training a custom model is not worth the effort. One has to go through the whole pipeline of data retrieval, cleaning, preprocessing, model training, evaluation, deployment, and monitoring. This is not worth it if the throughput does not lead to high API costs.

On the other side, if the hardware is available, and the developed model runs on a 1 core CPU with around 24 GB of RAM, it is possible to reduce costs when requirements change rarely. When using the proposed CMR framework, the model can be improved with just a few training examples over time with manageable time required for training. The in-house model is also faster during inference with a response time of around 6.4 seconds compared to 12.8 seconds when using the *OpenAI* API.

Although it might be nice to have a custom in-house solution, the strengths of it does not counteract its weaknesses enough and do not justify the cost and effort compared to using the *OpenAI* API. The results speak for themselves, because even if the model is able to predict certain fields better, it is missing out on many others.

8.4 Guide

Finally, this section provides a short guide for using LLMs for WIE tasks like this.

8.4.1 Data Preparation

As always, the data is the most crucial part. It has to be as clean and short as possible to save tokens and thus reduce cost. Therefore, the same cleaning strategy as proposed in this work (5.1.1) should be applied. It successfully flattens the HTML and removes unnecessary tags and attributes. Exceptions to this are narrow domains where certain attributes are known to be helpful. In this work, the headers and footers were kept for comparison. During the course of this work, a general web encoder for node classification was trained, which might need those tags. But when it is clear that these tags are not needed, they should be removed too. Furthermore, page analysis algorithms should be used to remove unwanted content like cookie banners. The model in this chapter rarely struggled with the task because of long inline base64 encoded images. Long and non-language strings like these should be eliminated as well.

Of course, it depends on the specific task and domain, but in general, you should clean and remove as much as possible to gain the highest extraction accuracy.

8.4.2 Prompt

Next, to let the model know what it should do, a prompt is needed. It is simple yet effective to follow the RTF framework for the system prompt and refine it as needed. Be as clear as possible when it comes to keywords or the output format.

Furthermore, a schema has to be defined. There are good libraries to specify a schema efficiently in a programming language of choice. This schema should have descriptions

where needed to give further guidance for a field. This can be information like where to find it, how to format it, what it means, etc. In addition, the schema should be as strict as possible to avoid unwanted outputs.

8.4.3 Evaluation Pipeline

Then, the model is ready to extract results and can be evaluated. To evaluate the model, a kind of ground truth is needed. At best, the dataset is created by human labelers, but an algorithmic approach like the one used in this thesis can also get most of the points, depending on the task, data, and schema. For categorical fields there are metrics like the precision, recall, and F1 score, while numerical fields can use the exact match rate, mean absolute error, or mean squared error. For textual fields, exact match metrics work well for short and predictable texts, as shown in section 8.2, but for longer or descriptive texts, similarity thresholds should be used to match them. Also check for empty fields or fields with placeholders or leading and trailing characters.

Tip: For batch processing and when the results are not needed immediately, the *OpenAI* provides a batch API, which only costs half the original price.

8.4.4 Refinement

If anything is not as desired, it is easiest to change the prompt first. For general errors or task misunderstandings, change the system prompt. If certain fields are not performing well, refine their description in the schema. Sometimes it can even help to rename them and give them a more understandable name. When being as clear and precise as possible, the model should perform quite well on most tasks. Also, always double-check if the data is as good as you can make it.

Furthermore, cosmetic errors, like placeholders, can be easily fixed by a post-processing step. With it, outputs can be cleaned, brought to the right format if not already, filtered, and even retried.

When the task is very complex or the domain and data quite special, one option to further improve the accuracy of the LLM is to finetune it with labeled data. Since the dataset used for this evaluation is not of the preferred quality, finetuning is not considered helpful for this work. Data to finetune an LLM should be human-labeled and of high quality to get the most out of it. Otherwise, extraction results might even become worse. Furthermore, each finetuning run creates extra cost, and the resulting model is twice as expensive. Therefore, a good strategy is to finetune a smaller and less capable model such that it is still cheaper than the larger one. Then, both variants have to be compared with each other to choose the best one.

There are different types of finetuning techniques to select from: Supervised Finetuning (SFT), Direct Preference Optimization (DPO), and Reinforcement Finetuning (RFT). As this work is about an extraction task, the SFT technique is the most suitable one. While DPO takes correct and incorrect examples for a prompt to learn more subjective human preferences, RFT adapts reasoning models to create outputs that are more likely to get

better scores from a grader. In contrast, SFT can correct classification errors and instruction-following failures and is trained with correct responses to prompts (*Model optimization - OpenAI API* n.d.).

In this case, for example, empty lists for web pages without extractable projects and detailed project results for web pages with project information should be included in the dataset. If the model fails at certain aspects or edge cases, those should especially be included. Furthermore, the dataset should still be balanced and contain diverse items. If only training on project pages or no project pages, the model quickly learns to satisfy just one side. The same is true when only training with certain edge cases.

To sum up, finetuning can help and even dramatically improve the accuracy of the model, especially for complex tasks. However, it has to be done carefully and with high-quality data. Furthermore, when new models are published, the data shifts, or the schema changes, a new finetuning run is needed to change the base model or adapt to the new schema or data. Thus, finetuning should be the very last option when instruction tuning is failing.

8.5 Recap

This chapter has shown how the structured output feature of *OpenAI's* gpt-4.1 model is set up and used. The results provide an insight into how the model works, highlighting the need to be helpful and therefore a low precision for project pages. This problem is not so serious for project fields, which are also empty very often. Overall, the results are of good quality. Furthermore, this chapter compares the extraction results with the prediction results of the model, revealing the strengths and weaknesses of each method. Lastly, this chapter also includes a guide on how to tackle extraction tasks with LLMs.

Chapter 9

Limitations and Future Work

Web Information Extraction using specialized models is a subject that can be substantially expanded. This paper only covers a few possible techniques and comes with many limitations and possibilities for future work.

9.1 Data

The most important limitation of this work is the lack of web pages of the vertical under investigation with high-quality labels. This made the training process harder and required self-labeling some domains. But these labels are neither enough nor of the best quality. Selector-based labeling enabled the labeling of many web pages per domain, but due to the dynamic nature of websites, they easily miss some information. Especially for small classes, like a postal code of an address, it is hard to tag them if they are just occurring in a paragraph. That is where the abilities of LLMs shine through.

Furthermore, there are no datasets suitable datasets yet. In this work, datasets were created from different data sources. But this is time-consuming and error-prone. It would be great to have high-quality datasets with HTML content that is clean and ready to use. Datasets for downstream tasks like the node tagging investigated in this thesis are missing too. Those datasets would help with a more general evaluation of web transformers and present a great opportunity for future work.

To sum up, better and more data is required to build a state-of-the-art web transformer. This thesis provides a first step in the right direction, uncovering ways of creating web datasets and showing the potential of pretraining a MUSTIE encoder with them.

9.2 Model Architecture

Although the implementation of the MUSTIE encoder already provides an efficient architecture, there are still a few possible improvements. Section 4.5 discusses some of them. While the position matrix was implemented and has shown better results, other methods like semantic connections between leaves, a restructure of the TD attention, or the introduction of landmarks are still open for further investigations.

Furthermore, no smaller models were trained during this work, which may have helped in terms of memory use, training and convergence time, and regarding the low amount of data.

9.3 Training

A model as large as the one implemented here would most probably benefit from longer pretraining. Unfortunately, this was not possible for time reasons. Another drawback of the training process is the lack of further tasks to guide the model, like page classification or span extraction (Q. Wang, J. Wang, et al. 2023). There are many other possible self-supervised losses to investigate, as stated in subsection 6.2.2. Furthermore, the NRP head could be improved.

The multimodal training of the model could also be improved with suitable tasks. Image patches, for example, have no task that directly guides them. They are only trained via the MLM and MDM losses by giving context or via some *Schema.org* labels on their image node. The most potential source of patch training in this work is masking neighboring texts of the image, like the <ALT> tag or a paragraph, which includes descriptions of the image, but this could certainly be improved in the future.

This thesis also takes a short look at the PU loss to detect unlabeled positives. Due to memory constraints, this could not be tested in combination with important regularization methods like Mixup. Still, using a PU loss is a technique worth keeping in mind for web classification tasks, as labels could easily be missing, especially for MLC. In return, ASL was used. Its parameters could be further optimized to improve the results, especially for classes with very few labels.

9.4 HITL Implementation

Unfortunately, the HITL approach was only implemented for the *OpenAI* extraction results. While this was helpful to refine the prompt and system, it didn't help the training of the in-house model. Due to time constraints and lack of performance, it was not possible to implement the model in the system on time. Since the whole system was still under development, the feedback was more on a system level rather than on an item level. While there was qualitative feedback, there was no useful feedback to train the model with.

9.5 Other Techniques

Although this thesis focuses on state-of-the-art web transformer models and also presents the use of LLMs for the WIE tasks, there might be other models worth investigating for WIE. It was possible to get some insights from the company *oxylabs*¹, which successfully does WIE at scale. Their new tools use LLMs to create extraction tasks, but their extraction

¹<https://oxylabs.io>

core still relies on an XGBoost model. This is a way more lightweight solution for the task and easier to implement with fewer resources. However, it comes with the cost of huge labeling efforts and heavy feature engineering.

9.6 Recap

While MUSTIE shows great potential, as shown in this work, there are still many limitations and possibilities for future work. The data basis could be better and richer. There are missing optimized datasets for web transformers, and the labeling approach used for the finetuning dataset is not optimal. This work also provides some possible improvements for MUSTIE's architecture, especially regarding the full TD attention. Since this implementation does not include smaller models, the pretraining could probably benefit from longer training with more data and other tasks that guide the model better. Specialized tasks for multimodality, especially for image patches, are missing too. While this thesis didn't show promising results using the PU loss, it might be worth investigating it further for incomplete label scenarios. Finally, while transformers are the state-of-the-art models, simpler models like XGBoost can be thought of when facing resource constraints and having the necessary data at hand.

Chapter 10

Conclusion

This chapter finally assesses the statements from the introduction and summarizes the results and findings of this work before finishing this thesis.

10.1 Assessment

This section covers the fulfillment of goals (G), requirements (R), and research objectives (RO). Each item refers to the associated point from sections 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3.

10.1.1 Goals

One goal of this work was met while one was not and another only partially met.

G1 - Use OpenAI

The use of *OpenAI*'s API to extract project entities from HTML has been successfully shown in chapter 8. Projects can be extracted and matched to the labeled ones. Furthermore, the projects are labeled with categories from a database. According to the editors, the results of both the extraction and category labeling are of good quality on average.

G2 - Gradually Reduce Costs

Unfortunately, the cost could not be lowered using an in-house solution. The performance of the developed model does not meet the quality of the *OpenAI* baseline. Furthermore, as the page throughput for this use case will expectedly not increase in the future, upgrading the hardware to meet the needs in terms of RAM and maintaining a custom model and continually improve and monitor it might not reduce costs at all.

G3 - Utilize Human Feedback

Human feedback was partly used during the course of this work. Due to some constraints, the editors only gave qualitative feedback sometimes. This was used to improve the prompts for the structured output and led to better extraction results. On the other hand, no

new labels were added for the developed model. Therefore, there is only the simulation from section 7.4, which adds a few labels per domain in AL style to a CMR loop. Thus, the goal was not completely achieved.

10.1.2 Requirements

This section shows how well the single requirements have been met.

R1 - Context Length

Through the efficient design of MUSTIE, a sufficient context length can be provided to the model. It was trained with an input length of 3,072 tokens, of which 1,024 are DOM tokens and 2,048 are TI tokens. As of table 5.4, this is enough to fit most webpages. When using the *OpenAI* API, the context window is always large enough.

R2 - Mapping Instead of Generation

The requirement of only mapping texts present on web pages to the schema has been met using the developed model. Since it uses classification, the text can be directly extracted from predicted nodes afterward. When using structured output, this requirement is partly met. Sometimes, the model writes own text, especially for descriptive fields. But the editors didn't find this problematic (8.2.5).

R3 - Category Tagging

It has been shown how categories can be retrieved such that they can be changed at inference time. The performance of the model is currently not sufficient for this task. But there is also no human labeled ground-truth and not much data. Therefore, learning the category embeddings is currently a hard task, but could be improved with more high-quality data. On the other hand, it is much easier when using structured output. Since using the categories' descriptions would exceed the API size limit, only the group and title are used. While this works usually well, some cases would probably benefit from more details. This requirement is theoretically met with both, but only the structured output solution is currently able to fulfill it sophistically.

R4 - Detect All Projects on a Page

The model offers a 100 % recall on projects. Thus, it detects all of them, also multiple per page. *gpt-4.1* in contrast, only returns one project per page in many cases, also for pages which contain no or multiple projects. Thus, this requirement is achieved with the custom model, but not with the *OpenAI* baseline.

R5 - Reliability

The current results of the custom model are only sufficient for some fields like `project` and `project.address`. Other fields show too poor performance to be reliable. The editorial effort could be reduced by a AL approach where only the examples with the highest entropy are being labeled. The *OpenAI* results are not completely reliable too. While project information is generally of good quality, too many projects are extracted from pages, which do not contain projects. This requirement is not considered sufficiently met.

R6 - Utilize Human Feedback

Section 7.4 has shown an efficient framework to use human feedback to improve the model's performance. Unfortunately, there was no labeled feedback during the time of this work. Qualitative results have been used to improve the prompts for the structured output, but labeled future labeled feedback could not be used with this method when not using finetuning. Therefore, this requirement has been met with the data that was available and is shown to be fulfillable in the future.

10.1.3 Research Objectives

All research objectives have been examined.

RO1 - Applicability of MUSTIE

The application and effectiveness of a MUSTIE-based encoder has been shown throughout this work. While the results for many *Schema.org* labels and some finetuning classes are promising, results show that further efforts have to be made in terms of data quality. In total, this work shows that it is possible to extract hierarchical schemas from HTML using node tagging.

RO2 - Category Retrieval

A retrieval task has been introduced and analyzed. While the setup enables the change of categories at inference time, the results are currently not strong enough to say that it works well.

RO3 - MUSTIE Improvements

Section 4.5 introduced some theoretical improvements for MUSTIE. The DOM-LM position matrix has been applied to the model and shown to stabilize the training loss as well as improve the model's performance.

RO4 - CMR Approach

A CMR approach with AL has been implemented. It successfully shows that using only a small fraction of the labeled data is sufficient to learn and generalize over other domains and provides comparable results to the finetuning stage.

10.2 Success

While all research objectives were examined and a MUSTIE-based model successfully developed and tested, it was not able to reduce the costs of the web extraction process. The current solution would be to use a hybrid system with a custom model that filters project pages before giving them to *OpenAI*. But this would require more RAM on the target machine and maintenance of the custom model, which is probably not worth the effort with respect to the low use of this system. Thus, cost cannot really be reduced when including all factors.

10.3 Recommendation

While the results of the developed model are promising that great results can be achieved with more and high-quality labels, using an LLM performs better currently. Furthermore, this project does not have a high throughput and is therefore not worth the effort of developing and maintaining a custom model as this would require data retrieval, checking, cleaning, preprocessing as well as training and monitoring the model and providing the necessary hardware. The model can also not adapt to new classes without retraining. While the old classes can be preserved by copying their weights, new classes has to be initialized randomly. This project suffers from few labels and low data quality, which deflate training results. Additionally, extracting text from whole nodes has some weaknesses like missing detailed information in a paragraph. These problems are not given when using an LLM.

That's why the recommendation for this project is to stick with the use of structured output and to improve the prompts over time. The schema can be changed on the fly and the model is improved by another company. According to the editors feedback, finetuning an LLM is probably not necessary except when the model should explicitly be trained on giving no project outputs for non-project pages.

For large project setup with a high throughput the efforts of training and maintaining a custom model are probably worth it. Many webpages create cost with every request to the LLM, which could be dramatically reduced with a custom model. But this presupposes enough labeled data. If enough data is coming in with time, the introduced CMR framework can be used.

10.4 Summary

This thesis dealt with the extraction of project information from web pages using their HTML. A MUSTIE-based encoder has been trained, improved, and evaluated to show the effectiveness of a web transformer architecture with structural attention. To extract information from web pages, node tagging has been used together with hierarchical labels. It was shown how to pretrain the model and how important subtree masking is. Furthermore, an ITT stage was introduced and has proven to help the model's performance on the downstream task. Finally, while the results for some extraction fields are good, there is insufficient data amount and quality to learn other fields sophisticatedly.

A framework utilizing a CMR approach combined with AL has been introduced and showed strong performance as a low-resource scenario compared to the finetuning stage.

The developed model was compared to an *OpenAI* baseline using gpt-4.1 with structured output. While not perfect and extracting projects for non-project pages as well as only one project for project listing pages, using an LLM has shown several benefits and is recommended to use for small works like this.

To conclude, this thesis took a deep dive into web transformers, sparse attention, hierarchical and unbalanced data and has shown how to obtain data and implement and train a MUSTIE-based encoder. It provides improvement ideas and extensively analyzes the results of using an LLM with structured output. While the results are promising, there is much room for future work. This thesis provides a good foundation for further investigation of web transformers.

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Appendix *A*

Attention Matrices

This appendix provides the full attention matrix examples used for LA and BU attention for the example web page from figure 4.1.

Figure A.1: LA attention matrix.

Figure A.2: BU attention matrix.

Appendix *B*

Tokenization Details

This appendix provides some details about the tokenization vocabulary and enum values. The following is the map of possible HTML tags to their DOM token IDs. Since the IDs only go up to 128, the DOM token IDs can be saved as uint8 sequence.

```
{"PAD": 0, "MASK": 1, "a": 2, "abbr": 3, "acronym": 4, "address": 5, "applet": 6,
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 100, "strong": 101, "style": 102, "sub": 103, "summary": 104, "sup": 105, "svg":
 106, "table": 107, "tbody": 108, "td": 109, "textarea": 110, "tfoot": 111, "th":
 112, "thead": 113, "time": 114, "title": 115, "tr": 116, "track": 117, "tt":
 118, "u": 119, "ul": 120, "var": 121, "video": 122, "wbr": 123, "main": 124,
 "picture": 125, "item": 126, "ALT": 127, "UNKNOWN": 128}
```

Enum values for tokens and edge types are provided below:

```
class TokenType(Enum):
```

```
    PAD = 0;
    DOM = 1
    TEXT = 2
    IMAGE = 3
```

```
class DDType(Enum):
```

```
    SELF = 0
    PARENT = 1
    CHILD = 2
    SIBLING = 3
```

Appendix C

Schema.org Labels in ITT

The following tables provide the complete label counts for the ITT dataset. "Total" is the total amount of labels over all pages while "Pages" is the amount of pages containing the specific label.

Table C.1: Schema.org labels in ITT dataset (A).

Label	Train		Val		Test	
	Total	Pages	Total	Pages	Total	Pages
aggregateoffer	1,215	1,128	160	145	146	146
aggregateoffer.highprice	862	370	178	48	100	46
aggregateoffer.lowprice	1,163	469	229	67	130	59
aggregaterating	3,130	2,968	402	355	353	324
aggregaterating.bestrating	1,399	630	172	75	183	77
aggregaterating.ratingcount	1,703	895	241	95	285	102
aggregaterating.ratingvalue	3,514	1,584	441	204	449	189
aggregaterating.reviewcount	2,133	1,000	421	122	254	111
aggregaterating.worstrating	1,231	630	113	49	113	49
airport.iatacode	1,302	23	9	1	128	2
answer	4,122	1,194	617	172	562	128
answer.text	4,147	998	595	150	580	111
answer.upvotecount	851	181	33	10	38	13
article	21,933	21,770	2,693	2,649	2,586	2,572
article.articlesection	34,861	11,094	4,264	1,397	4,125	1,394
article.author	12,957	12,856	1,616	1,603	1,651	1,637
article.commentcount	4,601	1,544	667	188	963	219
article.copyrightholder	813	798	98	98	98	91
article.description	815	678	103	88	136	104
article.headline	36,107	17,248	3,329	2,093	3,322	2,066
article.image	8,201	8,055	1,018	991	997	987
article.keywords	6,384	4,235	771	547	783	523
article.mainentityofpage	15,525	15,466	1,943	1,939	1,914	1,911
article.name	6,601	3,401	530	320	571	337
article.publisher	13,627	13,476	1,713	1,699	1,707	1,689
article.thumbnailurl	5,615	4,846	768	595	637	580
article.url	1,084	1,073	125	125	145	145

Table C.2: Schema.org labels in ITT dataset (A - H).

Label	Train		Val		Test	
	Total	Pages	Total	Pages	Total	Pages
autodealer.name	921	329	105	41	120	45
autodealer.telephone	852	209	112	27	128	27
blogposting	6,406	6,122	757	736	769	752
blogposting.articlesection	2,542	844	402	101	390	107
blogposting.author	4,071	4,029	467	463	497	494
blogposting.headline	10,423	5,226	1,171	611	1,258	639
blogposting.image	1,120	1,078	130	129	152	139
blogposting.mainentityofpage	2,226	2,187	259	249	271	269
blogposting.name	1,384	943	163	104	154	117
blogposting.publisher	3,010	3,000	354	353	368	367
brand	14,003	13,591	1,747	1,729	1,716	1,694
brand.name	27,723	11,738	3,334	1,509	3,040	1,463
breadcrumblist	99,532	95,006	12,328	11,824	12,466	11,912
breadcrumblist.itemlistelement	99,315	94,812	12,306	11,808	12,445	11,892
collectionpage	19,852	19,807	2,422	2,418	2,486	2,478
collectionpage.breadcrumb	14,030	14,015	1,699	1,698	1,777	1,777
collectionpage.image	6,102	6,100	740	740	776	776
collectionpage.name	10,102	6,553	1,166	791	1,265	829
collectionpage.primaryimageofpage	6,101	6,100	740	740	776	776
collectionpage.thumbnailurl	3,871	3,468	477	421	502	446
collectionpage.url	16,550	16,550	2,031	2,030	2,064	2,064
collegeoruniversity	262	94	264	28	315	43
collegeoruniversity.name	335	56	442	26	478	40
comment	1,083	636	117	82	116	76
comment.author	848	510	80	57	112	63
comment.upvotecount	893	331	114	49	76	39
comment.url	789	471	107	60	81	56
contactpoint	1,782	1,630	211	191	217	202
contactpoint.telephone	2,007	1,107	304	136	280	144
discussionforumposting	1,097	1,097	137	137	184	184
discussionforumposting.articlesection	1,458	472	127	68	271	81
discussionforumposting.author	1,021	1,013	128	128	146	146
discussionforumposting.headline	1,526	1,025	185	128	208	144
event	5,074	3,548	554	435	640	447
event.description	819	489	64	58	103	72
event.image	1,814	771	248	90	254	102
event.location	2,859	2,449	319	301	397	315
event.mainentityofpage	758	758	106	106	96	96
event.name	11,725	2,874	969	347	2,220	363
event.organizer	905	839	108	104	120	115
event.url	918	918	123	123	113	113
faqpage	1,638	1,608	225	223	177	177
faqpage.mainentity	1,602	1,574	221	219	173	173
hotel.name	778	145	270	22	39	11
howtostep	1,970	385	343	47	204	44
howtostep.name	1,467	228	192	32	132	27
howtostep.text	2,300	360	375	44	223	42

Table C.3: Schema.org labels in ITT dataset (I - M).

Label	Train		Val		Test	
	Total	Pages	Total	Pages	Total	Pages
imageobject	88,541	63,724	10,984	7,917	11,197	7,988
imageobject.caption	70,990	30,248	9,669	3,737	8,619	3,802
imageobject.contenturl	42,561	28,027	4,963	3,433	5,287	3,477
imageobject.height	1,096	557	129	67	98	68
imageobject.name	14,127	5,447	1,722	666	1,805	659
imageobject.url	52,373	34,356	6,173	4,157	6,581	4,305
imageobject.width	960	476	93	54	91	60
interactioncounter	1,620	1,228	194	149	208	165
interactioncounter.userinteractioncount	3,694	1,227	372	149	561	165
itemlist	1,266	1,209	146	140	125	124
itemlist.itemlistelement	1,140	1,088	133	128	113	112
itempage	1,828	1,826	234	234	227	223
itempage.breadcrumb	1,330	1,329	155	155	167	167
itempage.image	685	675	76	76	80	80
itempage.name	1,256	939	137	111	143	113
itempage.potentialaction	683	683	79	79	88	88
itempage.primaryimageofpage	730	730	84	84	88	88
itempage.url	1,232	1,231	153	153	152	151
jobposting	730	730	81	81	90	90
jobposting.title	1,193	624	135	72	208	74
legalservice	569	264	454	51	38	36
legalservice.telephone	554	121	646	35	37	18
listitem	219,030	107,874	28,042	13,454	27,474	13,515
listitem.description	751	55	406	20	304	10
listitem.item	71,238	31,195	8,423	3,754	8,470	3,767
listitem.name	328,537	85,003	42,152	10,664	42,375	10,774
listitem.nextitem	1,753	1,667	210	202	219	202
listitem.previousitem	1,863	1,857	222	221	229	229
localbusiness	3,989	3,557	526	514	536	442
localbusiness.address	1,454	1,290	237	235	162	159
localbusiness.image	1,053	672	101	91	129	80
localbusiness.name	5,093	2,141	700	336	761	275
localbusiness.telephone	2,627	1,337	294	156	348	168
localbusiness.url	834	819	105	105	93	93
locationfeaturespecification.name	734	58	143	5	25	5
menuitem.name	713	14	2	2	138	1
monetaryamount.value	910	393	77	47	70	42
musicgroup.name	622	139	218	26	17	11

Table C.4: Schema.org labels in ITT dataset (N - P).

Label	Train		Val		Test	
	Total	Pages	Total	Pages	Total	Pages
name	143,566	24,532	17,564	2,971	17,366	2,983
newsarticle	8,102	8,022	1,040	1,021	1,009	967
newsarticle.articlesection	9,661	2,776	1,307	329	1,153	374
newsarticle.author	5,729	5,656	706	695	703	694
newsarticle.creator	1,002	722	100	74	67	47
newsarticle.description	1,715	1,514	181	158	183	170
newsarticle.headline	11,178	6,751	1,406	886	1,358	804
newsarticle.image	1,881	1,831	207	205	231	217
newsarticle.keywords	1,597	856	120	91	245	137
newsarticle.mainentityofpage	2,128	2,125	251	251	261	259
newsarticle.name	1,701	1,068	215	151	260	141
newsarticle.publisher	4,392	4,374	502	499	510	507
newsarticle.url	656	653	77	77	81	81
newsmediaorganization	1,098	1,070	106	105	138	137
newsmediaorganization.name	792	432	43	36	140	61
offer	24,621	21,752	3,020	2,729	3,010	2,619
offer.gtin	612	276	61	36	115	38
offer.name	9,596	2,109	1,553	253	1,007	249
offer.price	10,683	4,592	1,335	554	1,280	546
offer.pricecurrency	6,189	2,217	1,075	270	931	272
offer.pricSpecification	4,120	4,090	505	505	518	502
offer.seller	11,944	11,850	1,436	1,436	1,457	1,440
offer.sku	3,697	3,077	437	382	455	368
offer.url	8,041	7,647	914	903	964	928
organization	80,084	76,635	9,857	9,529	9,876	9,518
organization.address	1,072	1,010	101	100	139	138
organization.alternatename	1,060	606	240	93	175	87
organization.contactpoint	1,070	1,066	125	125	136	136
organization.description	762	591	84	75	80	72
organization.email	981	624	89	73	112	71
organization.image	27,919	27,825	3,505	3,483	3,471	3,461
organization.legalname	1,024	583	108	65	93	67
organization.logo	34,814	33,378	4,281	4,104	4,371	4,156
organization.name	73,727	42,333	8,940	5,260	8,574	5,255
organization.telephone	1,085	666	265	86	155	95
organization.url	8,866	8,821	1,055	1,041	1,093	1,085
person	38,629	33,364	5,293	4,266	5,157	4,169
person.description	2,347	2,194	294	285	279	267
person.image	17,034	16,214	2,315	2,044	2,195	2,102
person.jobtitle	774	409	102	57	55	38
person.name	77,866	31,752	11,523	4,084	9,780	3,983
person.telephone	336	224	489	54	78	38
person.url	2,013	1,915	357	280	268	262
person.worksfor	791	744	92	91	94	92

Table C.5: Schema.org labels in ITT dataset (P - Q).

Label	Train		Val		Test	
	Total	Pages	Total	Pages	Total	Pages
place	4,240	3,464	494	448	561	442
place.address	2,171	1,784	266	253	286	213
place.name	6,662	2,372	756	289	843	309
postaladdress	7,044	5,849	1,069	847	772	696
postaladdress.addresscountry	1,933	1,284	324	175	193	135
postaladdress.addresslocality	8,277	3,750	1,490	581	1,224	456
postaladdress.addressregion	4,302	2,260	640	322	570	262
postaladdress.postalcode	3,662	2,323	659	347	426	276
postaladdress.streetaddress	4,887	2,942	696	395	495	372
price	7,814	3,441	1,008	422	991	434
pricecurrency	2,155	330	298	40	315	44
pricespecification.price	736	262	82	34	67	29
product	47,883	45,090	5,945	5,571	6,056	5,531
product.aggregaterating	1,780	1,757	196	189	192	183
product.brand	26,387	21,828	3,125	2,732	3,347	2,706
product.category	6,435	2,335	777	292	810	301
product.color	1,199	426	199	63	138	51
product.description	8,955	6,260	1,008	769	1,087	814
product.image	13,588	11,322	1,699	1,390	1,815	1,386
product.mainentityofpage	906	906	113	113	113	113
product.manufacturer	1,618	894	193	126	184	107
product.model	678	394	74	53	70	48
product.mpn	2,328	1,631	352	213	416	210
product.name	77,384	35,362	9,694	4,353	9,686	4,297
product.offers	21,763	21,219	2,615	2,582	2,631	2,552
product.review	961	901	140	128	112	105
product.size	489	95	21	13	119	12
product.sku	11,934	9,917	1,389	1,212	1,627	1,201
product.url	8,666	8,552	1,028	1,012	1,046	1,045
productgroup	1,133	1,128	139	138	132	132
productgroup.brand	770	767	94	94	87	87
productgroup.name	1,881	728	216	88	194	83
profilepage	757	757	136	135	97	97
profilepage.name	663	238	86	30	89	27
propertyvalue	952	480	115	51	195	65
propertyvalue.name	909	277	532	27	82	32
propertyvalue.value	1,224	330	829	37	255	46
quantitativevalue	1,061	793	130	107	113	94
quantitativevalue.minvalue	785	320	109	45	83	35
quantitativevalue.value	942	449	105	59	97	53
question	8,700	2,205	1,217	269	1,102	244
question.acceptedanswer	3,784	1,036	599	158	536	118
question.name	9,535	2,052	1,398	256	1,162	223

Table C.6: Schema.org labels in ITT dataset (R - W).

Label	Train		Val		Test	
	Total	Pages	Total	Pages	Total	Pages
rating	929	767	139	122	129	103
rating.bestrating	1,515	430	388	75	373	56
rating.ratingvalue	2,157	605	546	95	578	81
rating.worstrating	1,123	306	208	44	121	39
readaction	52,971	52,966	6,478	6,478	6,651	6,650
readaction.target	53,139	52,963	6,476	6,476	6,649	6,649
recipe.name	984	456	133	58	117	59
review	2,316	1,547	384	208	228	185
review.author	3,130	1,054	548	136	490	126
review.name	1,475	395	179	48	160	46
review.reviewbody	1,805	518	341	65	202	65
review.reviewrating	811	761	125	122	110	104
service	782	487	134	115	82	59
service.name	865	109	70	17	100	12
sitenavigationelement	6,901	1,312	734	162	1,581	147
sitenavigationelement.name	13,382	1,285	1,280	160	4,297	146
sitenavigationelement.url	1,159	125	25	12	19	14
sportsteam.name	871	82	50	8	59	10
thing	8,514	7,202	886	820	835	757
thing.name	15,315	6,283	1,599	713	1,437	656
videoobject	2,031	1,661	300	238	233	194
videoobject.description	1,031	526	133	64	117	67
videoobject.name	2,462	1,279	384	193	253	148
webpage	70,485	66,531	8,648	8,143	8,728	8,275
webpage.about	626	625	72	72	76	75
webpage.author	8,142	8,138	978	978	1,049	1,049
webpage.breadcrumb	45,262	45,200	5,551	5,541	5,633	5,624
webpage.description	2,825	2,178	295	241	312	263
webpage.discussionurl	644	644	73	73	81	81
webpage.headline	3,098	1,547	420	225	291	162
webpage.image	20,638	20,531	2,510	2,503	2,577	2,563
webpage.mainentity	830	827	109	109	114	114
webpage.mainentityofpage	990	989	110	110	125	125
webpage.name	56,113	28,641	6,940	3,429	6,878	3,546
webpage.potentialaction	51,619	51,619	6,299	6,299	6,460	6,460
webpage.primaryimageofpage	21,856	21,803	2,649	2,645	2,727	2,725
webpage.publisher	2,213	2,213	260	260	266	266
webpage.thumbnailurl	17,937	15,307	2,129	1,865	2,128	1,909
webpage.url	56,920	55,772	6,941	6,809	7,086	6,965
webpageelement	812	41	3	3	8	8
webpageelement.name	1,819	9	1	1	0	0
website	71,356	70,131	8,654	8,529	8,934	8,772
website.alternatename	1,433	907	203	118	179	116
website.description	12,772	10,391	1,518	1,245	1,549	1,300
website.name	64,451	36,519	7,740	4,471	7,649	4,494
website.publisher	34,222	34,209	4,235	4,232	4,304	4,297
website.url	6,628	6,602	792	786	825	818

Appendix *D*

ITT Class Results

This appendix provides class-wise results for the ITT with the amount of training labels.

Table D.1: ITT Class Results 93–100 %.

Class	F1 in %	Precision in %	Recall in %	Label Count
localbusiness	100.0	100.0	100.0	3,989
videobject	100.0	100.0	100.0	2,031
productgroup	100.0	100.0	100.0	1,133
itempage	100.0	100.0	100.0	1,828
propertyvalue	100.0	100.0	100.0	952
webpageelement	100.0	100.0	100.0	812
sitenavigationelement	99.9	100.0	99.8	6,901
quantitativevalue	99.8	100.0	99.5	1,061
blogposting	99.6	99.3	100.0	6,406
answer	99.5	98.9	100.0	4,122
newsarticle	99.1	98.3	100.0	8,102
aggregateoffer	98.8	98.1	99.4	1,215
article	98.6	97.3	100.0	21,933
event	98.6	97.2	100.0	5,074
person	98.4	96.8	100.0	38,629
listitem	98.3	96.7	100.0	219,030
question	98.3	96.6	100.0	8,700
aggregaterating	98.1	96.3	100.0	3,130
rating	97.5	95.1	100.0	929
event.name	97.2	99.2	95.3	11,725
discussionforumposting	97.1	94.4	100.0	1,097
offer	96.3	93.0	100.0	24,621
blogposting.headline	96.3	100.0	92.9	10,423
place	96.0	93.3	98.9	4,240
webpage.name	95.9	100.0	92.1	56,113
name	95.7	98.8	92.9	143,566
newsarticle.headline	95.4	100.0	91.2	11,178
review	95.3	91.1	100.0	2,316
collectionpage	95.3	91.0	100.0	19,852
article.headline	94.6	98.2	91.3	36,107
listitem.name	94.6	97.6	91.8	328,537
product.brand	93.8	92.7	94.9	26,387
product.description	93.6	100.0	88.0	8,955
article.name	93.3	100.0	87.5	6,601
organization	93.0	86.8	100.0	80,084

Table D.2: ITT Class Results 47–93 %.

Class	F1 in %	Precision in %	Recall in %	Label Count
imageobject	92.9	86.7	100.0	88,541
price	92.3	85.8	100.0	7,814
website.description	91.8	100.0	84.9	12,772
website	91.8	84.8	100.0	71,356
postaladdress	91.6	84.4	100.0	7,044
offer.price	91.0	83.9	99.5	10,683
person.name	90.7	98.1	84.3	77,866
product	90.1	81.9	100.0	47,883
webpage	89.6	81.2	100.0	70,485
brand	89.1	95.5	83.6	14,003
brand.name	86.5	94.4	79.9	27,723
thing	86.5	90.5	82.8	8,514
videoobject.name	84.7	100.0	73.4	2,462
thing.name	83.4	88.2	79.0	15,315
offer.gtin	83.0	90.7	76.5	612
localbusiness.name	81.0	100.0	68.1	5,093
webpage.mainentity	80.2	78.6	81.9	830
website.name	78.4	75.2	82.0	64,451
comment	77.2	62.8	100.0	1,083
website.alternatename	76.9	100.0	62.5	1,433
organization.name	76.4	77.6	75.3	73,727
newsmediaorganization	76.4	96.6	63.1	1,098
product.name	75.0	70.5	80.2	77,384
imageobject.caption	75.0	82.5	68.8	70,990
organization.alternatename	73.7	100.0	58.4	1,060
offer.name	73.4	99.8	58.1	9,596
imageobject.name	72.1	67.6	77.3	14,127
interactioncounter	70.7	68.1	73.5	1,620
howtostep	69.2	65.5	73.4	1,970
newsmediaorganization.name	68.3	95.0	53.4	792
legalservice	67.3	100.0	50.7	569
interactioncounter.userinteractioncount	67.2	64.5	70.2	3,694
profilepage	67.2	100.0	50.6	757
product.sku	66.2	71.9	61.4	11,934
comment.upvotecount	63.2	47.1	96.1	893
discussionforumposting.author	60.9	75.5	51.0	1,021
productgroup.name	59.4	100.0	42.2	1,881
postaladdress.postalcode	58.5	58.1	58.8	3,662
offer.pric specification	57.4	63.4	52.5	4,120
webpage.mainentityofpage	57.4	58.8	56.0	990
review.name	55.4	98.3	38.6	1,475
webpage.discussionurl	54.7	45.8	67.9	644
postaladdress.addresscountry	54.5	86.9	39.7	1,933
webpage.headline	53.8	70.0	43.7	3,098
jobposting	53.2	76.4	40.8	730
service	51.5	100.0	34.6	782
pricecurrency	50.8	45.1	58.1	2,155
offer.pricecurrency	50.2	54.8	46.2	6,189
rating.bestrating	48.1	74.8	35.5	1,515
howtostep.name	47.9	54.9	42.4	1,467
offer.sku	47.6	64.4	37.7	3,697
organization.legalname	47.6	100.0	31.2	1,024
postaladdress.streetaddress	47.5	64.7	37.5	4,887
discussionforumposting.headline	47.1	80.2	33.3	1,526

Table D.3: ITT Class Results 18–44 %.

Class	F1 in %	Precision in %	Recall in %	Label Count
readaction	43.8	40.2	48.1	52,971
readaction.target	43.8	40.2	48.1	53,139
postaladdress.addressregion	43.5	49.9	38.6	4,302
place.name	43.1	75.5	30.2	6,662
recipe.name	42.0	73.9	29.3	984
contactpoint	41.9	99.0	26.6	1,782
webpage.potentialaction	41.9	43.0	40.9	51,619
collectionpage.name	41.9	67.5	30.4	10,102
webpage.url	41.3	43.7	39.2	56,920
imageobject.width	40.0	61.9	29.5	960
howtostep.text	40.0	44.9	36.0	2,300
comment.url	38.7	30.5	53.1	789
imageobject.height	38.1	56.0	28.9	1,096
person.telephone	37.7	62.5	27.0	336
localbusiness.url	36.2	91.3	22.6	834
breadcrumblist	35.9	45.7	29.6	99,532
breadcrumblist.itemlistelement	35.8	45.5	29.4	99,315
blogposting.author	35.4	83.5	22.5	4,071
rating.ratingvalue	35.4	79.0	22.8	2,157
webpage.publisher	34.6	53.6	25.6	2,213
person.description	34.6	50.3	26.4	2,347
place.address	33.7	76.3	21.6	2,171
product.color	32.7	83.9	20.3	1,199
product.image	31.2	50.0	22.7	13,588
comment.author	30.3	40.9	24.1	848
event.description	30.1	58.8	20.2	819
autodealer.name	30.0	75.0	18.7	921
event.image	29.9	79.3	18.4	1,814
imageobject.url	29.2	41.2	22.6	52,373
postaladdress.addresslocality	28.7	55.4	19.3	8,277
review.author	28.6	63.6	18.4	3,130
faqpage	28.3	100.0	16.5	1,638
webpage.breadcrumb	27.9	49.6	19.4	45,262
listitem.item	27.4	50.1	18.9	71,238
webpage.thumbnailurl	27.2	39.4	20.8	17,937
imageobject.contenturl	26.8	40.0	20.2	42,561
aggregateoffer.lowprice	26.5	87.0	15.6	1,163
itemlist	26.1	100.0	15.0	1,266
jobposting.title	23.8	47.1	15.9	1,193
webpage.author	22.9	58.0	14.2	8,142
collectionpage.thumbnailurl	22.3	43.8	14.9	3,871
collectionpage.primaryimageofpage	22.2	45.0	14.8	6,101
aggregaterating.reviewcount	22.1	67.4	13.2	2,133
localbusiness.address	22.1	90.9	12.6	1,454
webpage.primaryimageofpage	22.0	38.0	15.5	21,856
collectionpage.breadcrumb	21.5	48.5	13.8	14,030
event.location	21.4	55.4	13.2	2,859
webpage.image	21.3	37.7	14.9	20,638
person.image	21.2	42.4	14.1	17,034
collectionpage.image	20.9	45.2	13.6	6,102
newsarticle.author	20.3	73.2	11.8	5,729
answer.upvotecount	19.5	100.0	10.8	851
newsarticle.description	19.1	39.0	12.6	1,715
aggregaterating.bestrating	18.6	65.4	10.8	1,399

Table D.4: ITT Class Results 0–16 %.

Class	F1 in %	Precision in %	Recall in %	Label Count
monetaryamount.value	18.2	100.0	10.0	910
aggregateoffer.highprice	16.7	64.3	9.6	862
aggregaterating.ratingvalue	16.0	60.7	9.2	3,514
collegeoruniversity	15.0	95.2	8.1	262
person.jobtitle	14.8	57.1	8.5	774
article.thumbnailurl	14.7	32.8	9.5	5,615
quantitativevalue.value	14.1	100.0	7.6	942
question.name	12.9	53.3	7.3	9,535
article.image	9.9	35.2	5.8	8,201
website.publisher	9.9	40.8	5.6	34,222
autodealer.telephone	8.2	57.1	4.4	852
website.url	7.7	29.3	4.4	6,628
organization.logo	7.5	39.4	4.2	34,814
organization.image	7.5	37.6	4.2	27,919
organization.url	7.3	48.8	3.9	8,866
newsarticle.articlesection	6.4	70.4	3.3	9,661
article.articlesection	5.9	41.1	3.2	34,861
review.reviewbody	5.7	13.0	3.6	1,805
product.url	5.2	59.6	2.7	8,666
rating.worstrating	5.1	60.0	2.7	1,123
article.mainentityofpage	4.9	44.5	2.6	15,525
offer.url	4.7	71.9	2.5	8,041
discussionforumposting.articlesection	4.7	75.0	2.4	1,458
product.mpn	4.7	17.1	2.7	2,328
product.offers	3.4	60.8	1.8	21,763
offer.seller	3.2	79.3	1.6	11,944
question.acceptedanswer	3.0	77.8	1.5	3,784
newsarticle.creator	2.9	33.3	1.5	1,002
article.author	2.9	53.3	1.5	12,957
answer.text	2.7	53.8	1.4	4,147
aggregaterating.ratingcount	2.3	37.5	1.2	1,703
newsarticle.name	2.2	30.0	1.2	1,701
article.keywords	1.8	70.0	0.9	6,384
videoobject.description	1.7	100.0	0.9	1,031
article.commentcount	1.7	42.1	0.9	4,601
contactpoint.telephone	1.5	66.7	0.8	2,007
collegeoruniversity.name	1.3	60.0	0.7	335
blogposting.name	1.3	50.0	0.7	1,384
collectionpage.url	1.2	36.1	0.6	16,550
product.manufacturer	1.2	100.0	0.6	1,618
article.publisher	0.5	66.7	0.2	13,627
blogposting.mainentityofpage	0.0	0.0	0.0	2,226
productgroup.brand	0.0	0.0	0.0	770
faqpage.mainentity	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,602
newsarticle.publisher	0.0	0.0	0.0	4,392
article.copyrightholder	0.0	0.0	0.0	813
itempage.primaryimageofpage	0.0	0.0	0.0	730
blogposting.publisher	0.0	0.0	0.0	3,010
article.description	0.0	0.0	0.0	815
itempage.breadcrumb	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,330
product.mainentityofpage	0.0	0.0	0.0	906
itempage.url	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,232
localbusiness.telephone	0.0	0.0	0.0	2,627
propertyvalue.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	909

Table D.5: ITT Class Results 0 %.

Class	F1 in %	Precision in %	Recall in %	Label Count
article.url	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,084
webpageelement.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,819
product.aggregaterating	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,780
organization.description	0.0	0.0	0.0	762
event.mainentityofpage	0.0	0.0	0.0	758
sitenavigationelement.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	13,382
airport.iatacode	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,302
product.size	0.0	0.0	0.0	489
person.worksfor	0.0	0.0	0.0	791
newsarticle.url	0.0	0.0	0.0	656
newsarticle.mainentityofpage	0.0	0.0	0.0	2,128
blogposting.articlesection	0.0	0.0	0.0	2,542
itempage.potentialaction	0.0	0.0	0.0	683
profilepage.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	663
listitem.description	0.0	0.0	0.0	751
blogposting.image	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,120
event.organizer	0.0	0.0	0.0	905
listitem.previousitem	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,863
listitem.nextitem	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,753
organization.address	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,072
product.category	0.0	0.0	0.0	6,435
locationfeaturespecification.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	734
itemlist.itemlistelement	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,140
legalservice.telephone	0.0	0.0	0.0	554
webpage.description	0.0	0.0	0.0	2,825
quantitativevalue.minvalue	0.0	0.0	0.0	785
menuitem.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	713
sportsteam.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	871
service.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	865
product.model	0.0	0.0	0.0	678
aggregaterating.worstrating	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,231
pricespecification.price	0.0	0.0	0.0	736
organization.contactpoint	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,070
sitenavigationelement.url	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,159
itempage.image	0.0	0.0	0.0	685
organization.email	0.0	0.0	0.0	981
organization.telephone	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,085
webpage.about	0.0	0.0	0.0	626
hotel.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	778
product.review	0.0	0.0	0.0	961
review.reviewrating	0.0	0.0	0.0	811
itempage.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,256
propertyvalue.value	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,224
musicgroup.name	0.0	0.0	0.0	622
newsarticle.keywords	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,597
event.url	0.0	0.0	0.0	918
newsarticle.image	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,881
localbusiness.image	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,053
person.url	0.0	0.0	0.0	2,013

Appendix \mathcal{E}

Using Structured Output

This appendix adds the full JSON schema used for the structured output from the *OpenAI*-API.

```

1  {
2    "type": "json_schema",
3    "json_schema": {
4      "name": "project_extraction",
5      "strict": true,
6      "schema": {
7        "type": "object",
8        "properties": {
9          "projects": {
10         "type": "array",
11         "items": {
12           "type": "object",
13           "properties": {
14             "title": { "type": "string" },
15             "subtitle": {
16               "type": "string",
17               "nullable": true,
18               "description": "A sub title for the project, if present. Never a path. Don't use
19                 placeholders."
20             },
21             "description": { "type": "string", "nullable": true },
22             "foundationyear": { "type": "string", "nullable": true },
23             "visitOptions": {
24               "anyOf": [
25                 {
26                   "type": "string",
27                   "enum": [ "none", "duringCertainTimes", "byArrangement", "always" ]
28                 },
29                 { "type": "null" }
30               ],
31               "description": "Use null if there are no visit options available."
32             },
33             "email": { "type": "string", "nullable": true },
34             "phone": { "type": "string", "nullable": true },
35             "images": {
36               "type": "array",
37               "items": {
38                 "type": "object",
39                 "properties": {
40                   "url": { "type": "string" },
41                   "copyright": { "type": "string", "nullable": true }
42                 },
43                 "required": [ "url", "copyright" ],
44                 "additionalProperties": false
45               }
46             },
47             "properties": {
48               "type": "array",
49               "items": {
50                 "type": "object",
51                 "properties": {
52                   "key": {
53                     "type": "string",
54                     "enum": [ "activeEntity", "partner", "financing", "vision", "strategy", "tool" ]
55                   },
56                   "value": {
57                     "type": "string",
58                     "description": "Find a suitable description for the key from the input. If
59                       there is no suitable description, omit the property."
60                   }
61                 },
62                 "required": [ "key", "value" ],
63                 "additionalProperties": false

```

```

62     }
63   },
64   "address": {
65     "anyOf": [
66       {
67         "type": "object",
68         "properties": {
69           "country": { "type": "string", "nullable": true },
70           "state": { "type": "string", "nullable": true },
71           "region": { "type": "string", "nullable": true },
72           "zip": { "type": "string", "nullable": true },
73           "city": { "type": "string" },
74           "street": { "type": "string", "nullable": true }
75         },
76         "required": [ "country", "state", "region", "zip", "city", "street" ],
77         "additionalProperties": false
78       },
79       { "type": "null" }
80     ]
81   },
82   "links": {
83     "type": "array",
84     "items": {
85       "type": "object",
86       "properties": {
87         "url": { "type": "string" },
88         "title": { "type": "string" }
89       },
90       "required": [ "url", "title" ],
91       "additionalProperties": false
92     }
93   },
94   "categories": {
95     "type": "array",
96     "items": {
97       "type": "object",
98       "properties": {
99         "category": {
100           "type": "string",
101           "enum": [
102             "Status - Im Aufbau", "Status - In Planung", "Status - Weiterentwicklung", "Status - Etabliert",
103             "Status - Beendet",
104             "Partner - Unternehmen", "Partner - Politik/Verwaltung", "Partner - Kommune", "Partner
105             Förderkreis", "Partner - Förderkreis", "Partner - andere Projekte", "Partner - Verbände",
106             "Partner - Forschungseinrichtungen/ Universitäten",
107             "Organisationsform - Verein", "Organisationsform - Genossenschaft", "Organisationsform - Freie
108             Gruppe", "Organisationsform - Netzwerk", "Organisationsform - Initiative", "Organisationsform -
109             Sozialunternehmen",
110             "Aktive - Einzelperson(en)", "Aktive - Kleiner Kern (<10)", "Aktive - Großer Kern (>10)",
111             "Aktive - Regelmäßige Unterstützer*innen", "Aktive - Familie", "Aktive - Freunde", "Aktive -
112             Dorfgemeinschaft", "Aktive - Kinder und Jugendliche",
113             "Finanzierung - Spenden", "Finanzierung - Förderungen", "Finanzierung - Vereinsbeiträge",
114             "Finanzierung - Eigenmittel", "Finanzierung - Patenschaft", "Finanzierung - Ko-Finanzierung
115             der Gemeinde", "Finanzierung - Wirtschaftliche Tätigkeit",
116             "Raumressource - Einzelne Räume", "Raumressource - Gebäude", "Raumressource - Großes Haus/Hof",
117             "Raumressource - Besondere Immobilie", "Raumressource - Besonderes Fahrzeug", "Raumressource -
118             Landwirtschaftliche Fläche", "Raumressource - Garten",
119             "Wirkungsraum - Dorf", "Wirkungsraum - Gemeinde", "Wirkungsraum - Kleinstadt", "Wirkungsraum -
120             Region", "Wirkungsraum - Landesweit", "Wirkungsraum - Bundesweit",
121             "Vision - Anders Leben, anders Arbeiten", "Vision - Demokratie stärken", "Vision -
122             Gemeinschaft", "Vision - Gutes Leben für Alle", "Vision - Zukunft durch Innovationen", "Vision
123             - Kunst und Kultur stärken", "Vision - Kultur des freudvollen Machen", "Vision - Lebendigkeit",
124             "Vision - Nachhaltigkeit", "Vision - flächendeckende Daseinsvorsorge", "Vision - Solidarität",
125             "Vision - Feminismus", "Vision - Transformation der Wirtschaft", "Vision -
126             LGBTQIA*-Aktivismus", "Vision - Degrowth",
127             "Strategie - Ländliche Räume stärken", "Strategie - Altersübergreifende Projekte", "Strategie -
128             Allmende / Gemeingüter", "Strategie - Alltagsorte öffnen", "Strategie - Arbeit mit Kindern &
129             Jugendlichen", "Strategie - aufsuchende Formate", "Strategie - Begegnungsorte", "Strategie -
130             Beteiligungsstrukturen", "Strategie - Bildung", "Strategie - Perspektiven von Außen einladen",
131             "Strategie - Energieautarkie", "Strategie - Experimentieren", "Strategie - Gemeinde einbinden",
132             "Strategie - Handlungsräume ausloten", "Strategie - Infrastrukturen Selbermachen", "Strategie -
133             Integration voranbringen", "Strategie - Konflikte lösen", "Strategie - Kooperationen
134             schmieden", "Strategie - Künstlerische Interventionen", "Strategie - Leerstandsaktivierung",
135             "Strategie - lokales Handwerk stärken", "Strategie - Neue Narrative", "Strategie - neue
136             Traditionen etablieren", "Strategie - Ungewöhnliches kombinieren", "Strategie - Öffentlichkeit
137             schaffen", "Strategie - Position beziehen", "Strategie - Region vernetzen", "Strategie -
138             Ressourcen sparen", "Strategie - Um-/Zwischennutzen", "Strategie - Wissen teilen", "Strategie -
139             Mobilität fördern", "Strategie - Regionale Wertschöpfung", "Strategie - Angebote für Senioren",
140             "Strategie - Umwelt schützen", "Strategie - Digitalisierung nutzen", "Strategie -
141             Interkulturelle Arbeit", "Strategie - Rückkehrer unterstützen", "Strategie - Selbermachen",
142             "Strategie - Umweltbildung", "Strategie - Aktivierung von Engagierten", "Strategie -
143             Engagierte stärken", "Strategie - Geschichte bewahren", "Strategie - Transformatives Lernen",
144             "Strategie - Gründer*innen fördern", "Strategie - Interessenvertretung", "Strategie - tauschen
145             und teilen", "Strategie - Sichtbarkeit",

```

```

111 "Werkzeug - Archiv", "Werkzeug - Aufräumaktion", "Werkzeug - Ausstellung", "Werkzeug - Beirat",
    "Werkzeug - Beherbergung", "Werkzeug - Bürgerbus", "Werkzeug - Café", "Werkzeug - Co-working",
    "Werkzeug - Dorfauto", "Werkzeug - Direktvermarktung", "Werkzeug - Fest", "Werkzeug -
    Führungen", "Werkzeug - Garten", "Werkzeug - Gastronomie", "Werkzeug - Gemeinschaftshaus",
    "Werkzeug - Gemeinschaftliches Wohnen", "Werkzeug - Kunst- & Kreativkurse ", "Werkzeug - Kino",
    "Werkzeug - Gemeinsames Kochen", "Werkzeug - Kneipe", "Werkzeug - Jugendparlament", "Werkzeug -
    Jugendtreff", "Werkzeug - Dorfladen", "Werkzeug - Landwege", "Werkzeug - Landwirtschaft",
    "Werkzeug - Lebensmittelverarbeitung", "Werkzeug - Markt", "Werkzeug - Mikrobiologie",
    "Werkzeug - Mitfahrangebote", "Werkzeug - Museum", "Werkzeug - Proberäume", "Werkzeug - Radio",
    "Werkzeug - Regionalinitiative", "Werkzeug - Schaufensterbespielung", "Werkzeug - Sommercamp",
    "Werkzeug - Schwimmbad", "Werkzeug - Skatepark", "Werkzeug - Beratung", "Werkzeug - Tanzen",
    "Werkzeug - Probewohnen", "Werkzeug - Theater", "Werkzeug - Tiny Häuser", "Werkzeug -
    Treffpunkt", "Werkzeug - Veranstaltungsort", "Werkzeug - Veranstaltungsreihe", "Werkzeug -
    Vernetzungsveranstaltung", "Werkzeug - Dorfwerkstatt", "Werkzeug - Wanderung", "Werkzeug -
    Offene Werkstatt", "Werkzeug - Workshops", "Werkzeug - Dorfzeitung", "Werkzeug - Tiere",
    "Werkzeug - Digitale Plattform", "Werkzeug - Musik ", "Werkzeug - Reparaturcafé", "Werkzeug -
    Zeitzeugencafé", "Werkzeug - Crowdfunding", "Werkzeug - Offener Dialog", "Werkzeug -
    Nachhaltiges Bauen ", "Werkzeug - Kulturveranstaltungen", "Werkzeug - Freibad", "Werkzeug -
    Seminarbetrieb", "Werkzeug - Fernsehen", "Werkzeug - Bibliothek", "Werkzeug - Sport",
    "Werkzeug - Informationsveranstaltung", "Werkzeug - Infostand", "Werkzeug - Pressemitteilung",
    "Werkzeug - kollegiale Beratung", "Werkzeug - Lernreisen", "Werkzeug - Förderung", "Werkzeug -
    Politische Handlungsempfehlungen", "Werkzeug - Bürgerenergiegenossenschaft", "Werkzeug -
    Stadtentwicklung", "Werkzeug - Schule und Kindergarten in freier Trägerschaft"
112     ],
113     },
114     "isMainCategory": { "type": "boolean" }
115     },
116     "required": [ "category", "isMainCategory" ],
117     "additionalProperties": false
118     },
119     "description": "Identify all relevant categories from the available options that
    apply to the project - there is no limit on the total number. Return all matching
    categories as part of your output. Additionally, designate up to 3 of these
    categories as 'main categories', with the remainder labeled as normal ones."
120     }
121     },
122     "required": [
123     "title", "subtitle", "description", "foundationyear", "visitOptions", "email",
    "phone", "images", "properties", "address", "links", "categories"
124     ],
125     "additionalProperties": false
126     },
127     "description": "If multiple projects are available on a page, extract all of them. If none
    is available, return an empty array."
128     }
129     },
130     "required": [ "projects" ],
131     "additionalProperties": false,
132     "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#"
133     }
134   }
135 }

```

Lessons Learned

This additional chapter does not add any more scientific content to this thesis but rather reflects my personal findings in developing AI-supported systems and a custom MUSTIE-based model.

Instead of asking, “What have I learned?”, it would be easier to ask “What did I know before?” because many things were new to me and I learned a lot. Nevertheless, I try to list some of the most important things.

L^AT_EX. I learned how to write a L^AT_EX document and how to use it to create a thesis. Through VS Code extensions, I was able to write where I code, which was a pleasant experience. It was good to set up a document and style in the beginning and only refine details during the writing process.

Sparse attention. The implementation of MUSTIE’s attention mechanisms was not easy at first. I had to think through and understand sparse attention mechanisms and how to implement them. It took quite some time before I came up with the edges and the scatter attention mechanism for the highly irregular attention matrix. During this process, I understood attention, which I learned around one year ago, on a deeper level: how tokens query other tokens and how their values together with the residual connections create contextualized embeddings.

Handling Hierarchical Data and Labels. Furthermore, I found it interesting to deal with hierarchical data and labels. The greatest findings here were subtree masking and the MCL loss.

The 3 Ds of machine learning: data, data, data. As always, data is the most important thing when it comes to training a model. Often, I have a rough understanding of the data and search for a model for the specific use case. After implementing the model, I check how to preprocess the data. But sometimes, like this time, I realize that the data I thought I would have is not as good as it seemed. Thus, it’s critical to check the data and its quality before implementing the model. Before submitting to a model and a task, I should first check if I have the data for it and whether it has the expected quality. Furthermore, I learned that gathering and preprocessing data is a time-consuming process and requires much disk space when the datasets become thousands of items large.

(Pre-)training LMs. This amount of data and even more is needed when training an LM. It was a great experience to analyze the pretraining process and see how the MLM helps the model to understand its inputs. I also learned what metrics are useful to measure it, like perplexity, accuracy, and log loss and what they mean. Additionally, I

understood the importance of weight initialization and learning rate scheduling, as well as the differences between pre-LN and post-LN. Furthermore, to be able to put everything onto a GPU, I have to use mixed precision. During this work, I learned what fp16 is, how bf16 differs from it, and how they cause or prevent (gradient) overflows. The whole gradient mechanic got clearer to me, and how analyzing attention (for interpretability?) and gradient-based explanation methods differ.

Patience. But pretraining came with its own unique challenges for me. The biggest of them was patience. I always want to be faster than I am and see results immediately. With pretraining, even *only* for 100,000 steps, this was not possible. The metrics improved so slowly that I couldn't watch them. I really had to learn patience because it caused a lot of frustration when analyzing the loss curves and wondering why the MLM plateaus at around 7. But in fact, it was decreasing, just very slowly.

Using *Hugging Face*. Using *Hugging Face* for datasets and training was one of the best decisions. It saves so much work by providing everything needed for training, logging, and evaluating the model. This way I learned how to integrate a custom model and its config into the *Hugging Face* framework.

Visualize and check thrice. Early. Building a visualization tool for MUSTIE or analyzing its inside didn't only help to better understand the model but also uncovered some implementation errors. This tool was even more helpful as a bug finder than for the visualization itself. Mistakes like not tying the MLM head weights or switched dimensions after attention and other small things, have shown me that I have to check the code twice or even thrice and that visualizations are very important early on. And it should happen early to be able to fix errors accordingly. Some errors just happened too late.

Gradients and embeddings space. During the analysis of the model, I did some analyses using gradients. This way, I learned how they are calculated. Furthermore, I understood the embedding space and that contextualized embeddings, for example, can live in a very different space than word embeddings or category embeddings, which requires the use of a transform module.

Simplicity with LLMs. I find it great as well as annoying that using *OpenAI* provided such good results. I am always aiming high with custom solutions, but sometimes I have to admit that using existing products is simpler, less error-prone, and less time-consuming. All in all, it was a great experience for me to work on this project and develop a custom model for Web Information Extraction. I am grateful for the opportunity to learn and grow with this thesis and, as last time, happily finish this thesis with the following quote:

Our greatest glory is not in never
failing, but in rising every time we fail.

Confucius

Statutory Declaration

I hereby declare that I have written this thesis independently and without the help of others.

I further declare that I have not used any sources and aids other than those indicated. All passages in this thesis that have been taken or translated from other sources - including electronic media - in terms of wording or meaning have been identified as such by citing the source.

In addition, I declare that when using AI-supported writing tools or AI-supported other tools/aids, I have listed them in full in the "Overview of used aids" with their product name, my source of supply and an overview of the range of functions used in this thesis - stating all adopted text modules or other modules. If the university has citation requirements in this regard, I have complied with them.

This thesis has not yet been submitted to any other examination authority in the same or comparable form or in parts. This thesis has not yet been published.

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